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The Journal of Positive Psychology and Counselling

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A moderated mediation model of mental health problems among Nigerian youths

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Abstract

This study examined the mediating role of negative family relations in the relationships of family instability and mental health (internalising and externalising) problems and whether the mediating process was moderated by adolescents' self-control. A sample of 565 Secondary School SS II adolescents randomly selected from ten secondary schools in Ibadan, Nigeria completed questionnaires on family instability, self-control, negative family relations and mental health problems.

After controlling for age, gender and socio-economic status as covariates, it was found that negative family relations partially mediated the relationship between family instability and adolescents' mental health problems. Furthermore, self-control moderated the relationship between negative family relations and adolescents' mental health problems.

These findings contribute to the understanding of the mechanisms of family risk factors and self-control in youth development. Also, the findings have implications for the prevention of adolescents' mental health problems.

Keywords: Family instability, Negative family relations, Self-control, Mental health problems, Adolescents.

Introduction

Mental health is a state of well-being in which the individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to contribute to his or her community (WHO, 2001). Mental health problems mean problems associated with mental health. Some researchers have identified some indicators of positive mental health which included sense of control, self-esteem, sense of coherence, optimism and mental health distress that included psychological distress, suicide, self-inflicted injury and suicidal ideation (Kovess-Masfety, Murray & Gureje, 2005; Zubrick & Kovess-Masfety, 2005). In this study, mental health problems refer to internalising and externalising problems. Most phases of human development from childhood to adulthood experience mental health problems but it is during the adolescence that the problems reached its peak. Probably, this could be due to the dramatic changes in social, psychological, emotional and physical maturity of the young person and the concomitant challenges of meeting societal demands and personal needs giving rise to delinquent and antisocial behaviours (Salami, 2013). The negative consequences of mental health problems among the Nigerian youth are social violence, poor academic performance, armed robbery, mental disorders, lack of respect for elders, suicidal attempt, drug addiction and even death (Ugwuoke & Duruji, 2015), unemployment and physical illness (Raphael, Schmolke & Wooding, 2005).

Given that Nigeria's precarious economic situation may contribute to the incidences of mental health problems among the youth, some socio-cultural practices such as collectivism, interdependence, respect for the elders and family members and extended family relationship which involves bearing the financial responsibilities of one's immediate and extended family members, helping to raise, educate, discipline and support the adolescents (Salami & Ajitoni, 2015) are expected to help reduce the incidence of

internalising and externalising problems among them. Despite these efforts, incidences of mental health problems are on the increase among secondary school adolescents in Nigeria (Salami, 2013). Although some researchers have examined the determinants of mental health problems such as demographic variables, stressful life events, social support, quality of life, income and social status, and biology and genetics (Zubrick & Kovess-Masfety, 2005), less research attention has been paid to the relationship between family instability and mental health problems of the adolescents (Ackerman, Kogos, Youngstrom, Schoff & Izard, 1999; Bakker, Ormel, Verhulst & Oldehinkel 2011; Forman & Davis, 2003). Indeed, little research to date has examined specific factors that contribute to this process. Consequently, the present research focuses on the relationship between family instability and mental health problems of adolescents and the mediating role of negative family relations and moderating role of self-control.

Family instability is the degree, to which the family fails to provide continuity, cohesiveness and stability for children (Forman & Davies, 2003). Family instability have been shown to be associated with both internalising and externalising problems during adolescence (Ackerman et al., 1999; Bakker et al., 2011; Forman & Davies, 2003). It represents a chronically chaotic and unpredictable family environment. Some indicators of family instability are residential mobility, number of intimate adult relationships involving the primary caregiver, parental divorce, parental addiction, number of families with whom the child has lived, serious childhood illness and other recent negative life events such as deaths of relatives, changing jobs etc (Ackerman et. al., 1999; Forman & Davies, 2003). Therefore, being exposed to family adversity or instability poses serious challenges for adolescents (Bakker et al., 2011; Forman & Davies, 2003) which deserves the attention of researchers.

Literature on mental health problems suggests that negative parenting may aggravate the individual's engagement in mental health problems (Fauber, Forehand, Thomas & Wierson, 1990; Forman & Davies, 2003; Loukas, Realson & Herrera 2010; Sun, Li, Zhang, Bao & Wang, 2015). Therefore, there is need to examine the potential for negative family relations to mediate the relationship between family instability and mental health problems. The risk-buffering model proposes that favourable individual characteristics mitigate the effects of family instability on mental health problems (Bakker et al., 2011; Veenstra, Lindernberg, Oldehinkel; De Winter & Ormel, 2006; Wills, Sandy, Yeager & Shinar, 2001). Although, some studies have examined some favourable characteristics that could make adolescents resilient to family adversity or instability, few studies have examined good self-regulation or self-control as key protective factor to adapt well to adversity or instability (Bakker et al., 2011; Buckner, Mezzacappa & Beardslee, 2003, 2009; Langua, Bush, Long, Kovacs & Trancik, 2008).

Despite the large number of researches that has examined the direct effects of family instability, negative family relations and self-control independently on mental health problems, little research has investigated the moderating effects of self-control on the indirect effects of family instability on internalising and externalising problems via negative family relations. Thus, the purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between family instability and mental health problems of secondary school adolescents and the mediating effects of negative family relations and the moderating role of self-control in the mediated relationship.

This study makes some contributions to earlier research on adolescents' mental health problems. First, this study examined a sample of adolescent boys and girls instead of only one gender as done by Feldman and Weinberger (1994). Second, this study identified a variable (negative family relations) that partially mediated the relationship between family instability and mental health problems. The partial mediation showed that there are other

mediators such as aggression, stress and depression which could increase incidence of mental health problems among the adolescents. Third, this study used mean standardised parents and adolescents' self-report instruments. Fourth, this study conducted a moderated mediation analysis of the relationship between family instability and adolescents' mental health problems using self-control as the moderator on which little is known. Most previous studies have examined the moderating role of self-regulation capacities (Bakker et al., 2011), ethnicity or gender (Ackerman et al., 1999), on the relationship between family instability and mental health (internalising and externalising) problems.

Theoretical framework

This study was based on the risk-buffering model which states that favourable individual characteristics mitigate the effects of family adversity on mental health problems (Bakker et al., 2011; Veenstra, et al., 2006). Some studies have examined favourable factors that could make children and adolescents resilient to family adversity (Li-Grining, Votruba-Drzal, Bachman & Chase-Landsdate, 2006; Wills et al; 2001). Good self-regulation was proposed to be a key protective factor to adapt relatively well to adversity (Buckner et al., 2003; Lengua et al., 2008). Bakker et al. (2011) found that self-regulation capacities moderated the relationship between family adversity and mental health problems. In this study, the family risk factors are family instability and negative family relations while the behaviour problems are internalising and externalising problems and the moderator (buffering factor) is adolescent self-control. The results of this study will provide a better understanding of the risks and protective factors that influence the mental health problems of Nigerian adolescents thereby giving valuable information about effective prevention and intervention methods.

Conceptual model development

The model in Figure 1 represents the processes through which family instability and self-control relate with adolescents' internalising and externalising problems. The model proposes that family instability would be indirectly related to adolescents' internalising and externalising problems through its influence on negative family relations. That is, family instability arouses negative family relations which will lead to greater adolescent internalising and externalising problems. Self-control is expected to buffer the effects of negative family relations on internalising and externalising problems. These hypothesised relations represent moderated mediation model and the model proposes that the relationship between family instability and adolescent problem behaviours is contingent on levels of adolescents' self-control.

Figure 1: Conceptual model for moderated indirect effect of family instability on mental health problems through negative family relations. WAR = Warmth; TRU = Trust, TOG = Togetherness, FUN = Fun between the adolescent and his/her parents, ANX = Anxious/Depressed, WDR = Withdrawn/Depressed, SOM = Somatic complaints, AGG = Aggressive Behaviour, RBB = Rule-Breaking Behaviour, SED = Self-Discipline, IMP = Impulsive Control, HAB = Healthy habits, SRE = Self-Regulation in work, REL = Reliability, *p<.05

Hypotheses

1. Negative family relations will mediate the relationship between family instability and internalising and externalising problems of the adolescents.
2. Self-control will moderate the relationship between family instability and negative family relations.
3. Self-control will moderate the relationship between negative family relations and internalising and externalising problems of adolescents.
4. Self-control will moderate the indirect association between family instability and internalising and externalising problems of adolescents via negative family relations.

Method

Research Design

This study employed survey research design in obtaining data from the participants.

Participants

Participants were 565 secondary school SS II students (male = 285, female = 280) randomly selected from ten secondary schools (mixed) from five local government areas in Ibadan metropolis, Oyo state, Nigeria. Sixty secondary school II students were randomly selected from each of the ten schools making up to 600 students. From the 600 students, 575 questionnaires were collected. Of the 575 returned, 565 questionnaires that were properly filled were used for analysis giving a participation or response rate of 94.16%. The students' mean age was 18.33 years (S.D. = 2.42). Considering the demographics of the sample, 58% of their fathers and 67% of their mothers had less than secondary school education; 34% of their fathers and 60% of their mothers had unskilled or semi-skilled occupation. In respect of the socio-economic status of the respondents' parents, 48% of their parents belong to low socio-economic status, 42% of them belong to middle socio-economic status while 10% belong to high socio-economic status.

Measures

Family instability

Family instability was measured by means of an adapted version of the Family Instability Index (Ackerman et al., 1999). This measure consists of nine items measuring the number of times the family experienced disruptive life events in the past five years in five family domains viz: (a) changes in residence, (b) changes in primary caregiver, and (c) transitions in romantic relationships of the primary caregiver (dissolution of marriage, divorce), remarriage, (d) job and income loss and (e) death or serious illness of a close family member. The sum of number of times family experienced disruptive life events represents the score for the family instability. Some items were reworded reflect the Nigerian cultural milieu. The adolescents and their parents (mothers, fathers or caregivers) each completed the family instability scale. The average score of the adolescents on the adolescent-rated family instability scale and the parent-rated family instability scale represented the adolescents' family instability score. Confirmatory factor analysis indicated that the model adequately fit to the data: $\chi^2(151, N = 565) = 298.30$, CFI = .89, TLI = .89, SRMR = .05, RMSEA = .046, with confidence interval (.045, .060). The mean score of each item was calculated and family instability was used as a single indicator variable. The validity of this measure is supported by its significant correlations with adolescent disengagement from the family ($r = .19$), parental conflict ($r = .20$) and adolescent internalizing ($r = .28$) and externalising ($r = .37$) symptoms (Ackerman et al., 1999; Forman & Davies, 2003). For this study, the internal consistency reliability obtained was 0.70.

Negative family relations

Negative family relations were measured with six items adapted by Metzler, Biglan, Ary and Li (1998). The items assess the degree of warmth, trust, togetherness and fun between the adolescent and his /her parents. The responses were rated on a 5-point scale ranging from 1 = Never true to 5 = always true. Some items were reworded reflect the Nigerian cultural milieu. For this study, items were reverse scored and averaged so that higher scores reflect more negative family relations. The adolescents and their parents (mothers and fathers) each completed the negative family relations questionnaires. The average score of the adolescents on the adolescent-rated negative family relations questionnaires and the parent-rated negative family relations questionnaire represented the

adolescents' negative family relations score. Confirmatory factor analysis indicated that the four-factor model adequately fit the data: $\chi^2(151, N = 565) = 263.40$, CFI = .92, TLI = .90, SRMR = .04, RMSEA = .05, with confidence interval (.046, .062). The mean score of each factor was found and served as the four factor manifest indicators of the negative family relation latent variable. The internal consistency reliability of the six-item scale was 0.85. For this study, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient obtained was 0.83.

Self-control

Self-control was assessed with 13-item Brief Self-Control Scale adapted from Tangney, Baumeister, and Boone (2004). The items adopted a 5-point scale ranging from 1 = Not at all like me to 5 = Very much like me. Some items were reworded reflect the Nigerian cultural milieu. Three items were reverse scored such that high scores reflect high self-control. The adolescents and their parents (father and mother) each completed the self-control scales. The average score of the adolescents on the adolescents-rated self-control scale and the parent-rated self-control scale represented the adolescents' self-control score. Confirmatory factor analysis indicated that the scale has five dimensions viz: self-discipline, impulsive control, health habits, self-regulation and reliability. The five-factor model had good fit to the data: $\chi^2(151, N = 565) = 208.52$, CFI = .91, TLI = .90, SRMR = .04, RMSEA = .046, with confidence interval (.041, .052). The mean score of each factor was found and served as the five manifest indicators of the self-control latent variable. Cronbach's alpha for the Brief Self-Control Scale was 0.85. The concurrent validity of the self-control scale used was established by administering the self-control scale by Grasmick, Tittle, Bursick and Arneklev (1993) to some of the adolescents who completed the self-control scale by Tangney, Baumeister and Boone (2004). The correlation coefficient obtained between the two scores was 0.72. For this study, the Cronbach's Alpha obtained was 0.83.

Mental Health Problems

Mental health problems were measured with the internalising problems and externalising problems adapted from of the Youth Self Report (YSR) (Achenbach, 1991b) and parent-rated Child Behaviour Checklist (CBCL) (Achenbach, 1991a). Adolescent Internalising scale comprises three sub-scales: Anxious/Depressed, Withdrawn/Depressed and Somatic complaints which consist of 31 items $\alpha = 0.89$ while externalising problems comprises Aggressive Behaviour and Rule-Breaking Behaviour. Confirmatory factor analysis showed that the three-factor model had good fit to the data: $\chi^2(151, N = 565) = 283.04$, CFI = .90, TLI = .91, SRMR = .04, RMSEA = .045, with confidence interval (.042, .048). The mean score of each factor was found and served as the three manifest indicators of the internalising problems latent variable. The YSR externalising scale comprises two sub-scales: Aggressive Behaviour and Rule-Breaking Behaviour consisting of 32 items, $\alpha = 0.88$. The items have responses anchored on a 3-point scale ranging from 1= not true, 2 = sometimes true, 3 = often true. Some items were reworded reflect Nigerian cultural milieu. Confirmatory factor analysis showed that the two-factor model adequately fit the data: $\chi^2(151, N = 565) = 253.42$, CFI = .89, TLI = .87, SRMR = .05, RMSEA = .048, with confidence interval (.045, .058). The mean score of each factor served as the two manifest indicators of the externalising problems latent variable. For this study, the Cronbach's Alpha for this scale was 0.87.

The agreement between parent-reported (CBCL) and adolescent reported (YSR) internalising and externalising problems was moderate ($r=0.24 - 0.35$) for internalising problems and ($r=0.36 - 0.40$) for externalising problems. According to Noordhof, Oldehinkel, Verhulst and Ormel (2008) mental health problems rated by multiple informants (parents and adolescents) were better than problems rated by only one informant. So, the mean of the standardised parent and adolescent scores as a measure of internalising and externalising

problems was used in this study. Regarding the parent-rated child behaviour checklist (CBCL) the CBCL-externalising scale has 35 items and cronbach's alpha of 0.90 while CBCL internalising scale has 32 items and Cronbach's alpha of 0.85. The confirmatory factor analysis for the externalising scale of CBCL showed that the two-factor model adequately fit the data $X^2(151, N=565) = 240.30$, CFI = .90, TLI = .86, SRMR = .05, RMSEA = .049, with confidence interval (.043, .056). The confirmatory factor analysis for the internalising scale of CBCL showed that the three-factor model adequately fit the data $X^2(151, N=565) = 270.50$, CFI=.90, TLI=.90, SRMR=.043, RMSEA=.044, with confidence interval (.040, .045).

Parental socio-economic status

Parental socio-economic status was measured with socio-economic status scale developed by Salami (2000). The scale items consist of three sections that asked for personal data of the parents' education, occupation, and income which were scored. The adolescents and their parents (father and mother) each completed the parent socio-economic status scale. The average score on the parental socio-economic status scale for the adolescent-rated scale and the parent-rated report represented the adolescents' parent socio-economic status score. Confirmatory factor analysis showed that the three-factor model adequately fit the data: $x^2(151, N = 565) = 254.20$, CFI = .90, TLI = .91, SRMR = .043, RMSEA = .044, with confidence interval (.043, .050). The mean score of each factor parent's education, occupation and income served as the three manifest indicators of socio-economic status latent variable.

The scores on these items were summed to give a total score. The Cronbach's alpha of this scale was 0.76. For this study, the Cronbach's alpha obtained for the socio-economic status scale was 0.79. This scale has been used with success among Nigerian samples by Salami & Ajitoni (2015).

Covariates

Based on previous research that suggested that mental health was correlated with age, gender of adolescents and socio-economic status of their parents, these variables were included in the analysis as covariates.

Procedure

Some research assistants who were guidance and counselling undergraduate and postgraduate students helped in the administration of the research instruments. Before the administration of the questionnaires in the selected schools, the assistance and consents of the school administrators and students were obtained. The purpose and procedures of the study were described to the adolescents and they were told that they were free to choose whether to participate. The adolescents were asked to obtain the permission of their parents to participate and they were told that participation was voluntary and that there were no negative consequences for not participating. This facilitated the informed consent of the participants and their parents. The students were assured of the anonymity and confidentiality of their responses. The questionnaires were distributed to the students in their classrooms in the schools involved in the study in a face-to-face manner. The students were also given the parent-rated Child Behaviour Checklist, parents-rated self-control scale, parents-rated negative family relations, parent-rated socio-economic status scale, and parent-rated family instability scale to be filled by their parents and the students returned the five parent-rated questionnaires to the researcher after completion the following day. Of the 600 questionnaires distributed to the students, 575 were returned giving a participation rate of

94.16%. Of the 575 questionnaires returned, 565 questionnaires that were properly completed were used for analysis.

Methods of Data analysis

Structural equation modeling (SEM) was performed in two steps using Mplus 7.1 (Muthen & Muthen, 1998-2012) to analyse the data obtained. There were no cases of attrition, missing data or outliers in all the variables. Full maximum likelihood method and chi-square was used to test the hypothesized model. To reduce multi-collinearity all the variables were centred.

Confirmatory factor analysis was performed to evaluate the measurement model. SEM modelling was performed to test the mediating effects of negative family relations and moderating effects of adolescents' self-control with maximum likelihood estimation. Since some of the latent variable indicators were not normally distributed (e.g. family instability and internalising and externalising problems), bootstrap analysis was conducted to test the significance of the indirect effects. This analysis was repeated with 5,000 samples to obtain a parameter estimate of both the total and specific indirect effects. A 95% bias-corrected confidence interval for the parameter estimate that does not contain zero showed that the indirect effect was statistically significant which indicated a mediating effect. Latent moderated structural equation (LMS) method was used to test the latent variable interaction. In this test, significant non-zero product term shows the presence of an interaction.

Model fit was assessed using multiple fit indices that included comparative fit index (CFI), Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), Root Mean Square error of approximation (RMSEA), and the standardised root mean square residual (SRMR). Based on Tabachnick and Fidell (2007), a good fit was obtained in a model that show simultaneous values of TLI and CFI ≥ 0.90 , RMSEA ≤ 0.05 , SRMR ≥ 0.08 and χ^2/df ratio less than 3.0.

When specifying a latent interaction term in a model, the model fit indices cannot be estimated due to lack of a comparative model. As such, the procedure used by Sun, Li, Zhang, Bao and Wang (2015) and Perren, Ettekal and Ladd (2013) was used to test two models. The first model was tested without latent variable interaction (restricted model); the second model with the latent variable interaction (full model) was later tested. The nested model Likelihood Ratio Test [$LR = -2 (\text{LogLR}_{\text{Restricted}} - \text{LogLR}_{\text{Full}})$] was used to compare the difference between the two models. If the first model had adequate overall model fit and the LR test showed that adding latent variable interaction significantly improved model fit, we could then conclude that the second model had an adequate model fit (Sun et. al., 2015).

Results

Descriptive statistics

The mean, standard deviations and correlations of all the variables are presented in Table 1. The indicators were related to each other showing significant correlations. For example, family instability was significantly and positively correlated with the indicators of negative family relations. Also, indicators of family instability and negative family relations were significantly correlated with the indicators of internalising and externalising problems. The indicators of self-control were negatively related to indicators of negative family relations and adolescents' mental health problems. The prevalence of internalising and externalising problems was 3.0% and 4.0% respectively.

Measurement model test

Before running the SEM analyses to test the hypotheses, a measurement model was first established for all the latent variables using confirmatory factor analyses. The model fit the data adequately $\chi^2 (122, N = 565) = 265.07$, CFI = .92, TLI = .95, SRMR = .038, RMSEA

= .045 with confidence interval (.035, .056). The standardised factor loadings of each indicator were significant at $p < .05$.

Table 1: Mean, Standard Deviations and Zero-order Correlations among all Variables in Final Model

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	
1. Age	-																				
2. Gender	.03	-																			
3. Parents' education ^{al}	.05	.02	-																		
4. Parents' Occupation ^a	.07	.03	.02	-																	
5. Parents' Income ^a	.06	.02	.03	.04	-																
6. Family Instability ^a	.09	.03	.05	.03	.05	-															
7. Warmth ^a	.10	.08	.16	.15	.14	.21	-														
8. Trust ^a	.11	.15	.09	.13	.12	.24	.24*	-													
9. Togetherness ^a	.08	.03	.05	.06	.07	.19	.23*	.26*	-												
10. Fun ^a	.04	.02	.04	.07	.08	.20	.30	.24*	.19	-											
11. Self-discipline ^a	.10	.03	.05	.10	.07	.06	.04	.03	.05	.12	-										
12. Impulsive control ^a	.07	.04	.06	.07	.08	.05	.03	.02	.04	.07	.28*	-									
13. Healthy habits ^a	.05	.02	.01	.08	.09	.04	.02	.05	.03	.06	.23*	.21*	-								
14. Self-Regulation ^a	.06	.05	.02	.07	.07	.02	.04	.03	.05	.08	.19*	.19*	.35*	-							
15. Reliability ^a	.03	.08	.10	.03	.06	.12	.03	.01	.07	.04	.20*	.22*	.26*	.22*	-						
16. Anxious/Depressed ^a	.05	.03	.02	.05	.03	.21	.25*	.19*	.20	.22	-.25*	-.20*	-	-	-.40*	-					
17. Withdrawn/Depressed ^a	.12	.06	.08	.06	.05	.19	.23*	.21*	.23	.25	-.24*	-.22*	-	-	-.30*	-.26*	-				
18. Somatic Complaints ^a	.13	.04	.05	.03	.07	.20	.22*	.20*	.19	.24	-.22*	-.23*	-	-	-.32*	-.24*	-.22*	-			
19. Aggressive Behaviour ^a	.09	.02	.07	.02	.06	.24	.20*	.22*	.21	.25	-.23*	-.19*	-	-	-.40*	-.30*	-.24*	-.21*	-		
20. Rule-Breaking ^a	.04	.03	.02	.04	.07	.26	.24*	.23*	.19	.20	-.26*	-.20*	-	-	-.23*	-.35*	-.23*	-.30*	-.33*	-	

					*			*	*			.24*	.30*							
Mean	18.3	-	3.3	3.4	3.4	3.1	.50	.51	.52	.53	.67	.65	.68	.64	.63	3.01	3.10	3.13	5.30	5.3
	3		0	5	0	2														2
S. D.	2.42	-	2.3	2.3	2.3	2.4	1.20	1.21	1.2	1.2	1.50	1.58	1.53	1.56	1.53	2.60	2.50	2.71	3.15	3.1
			1	0	2	0			3	4										0

Note: N = 565, S.D. = Standard Deviation, Gender was dummy coded: 0 = female, 1 = male, * p< .05
a = score based on the mean standardised parent and adolescent reports.

Testing the mediating effects of negative family relations

The 95% bias-corrected bootstrap confidence intervals were used to test the significance of the direct, indirect and total effects in the mediation model because some latent variable indicators were not normally distributed (e.g. family instability and internalising and externalising problems). In Step 1, baseline models (covariates and family instability) was used to examine the direct effects of family instability on adolescents' mental health problems. The model fit the data adequately: $\chi^2(151, N=565) = 256.67$, CFI=.92, TLI = .90, SRMR = .050, RMSEA = .052, 90% RMSEA confidence interval (.046, .064). This showed that family instability significantly and positively predicted the adolescents' internalising and externalising problems with 9.8% and 8.7% of the variance explained in internalising and externalising problems respectively. In step 2, Negative family relations was added to the baseline model and this model also indicated a good fit to the data: $\chi^2(151, N=565) = 202.03$, CFI = .92, TLI = .93, SRMR = .045, RMSEA = .050, 90% RMSEA confidence interval (.045, .063), thereby indicating that negative family relations partially mediated the effects of family instability on adolescents' mental health problems. The variance explained in the prediction of negative family relations, internalising problems and externalising problems was 7.5%, 15.0% and 18.3% respectively.

As shown in Figure 2, family instability had significant direct effect on negative family relations ($\beta=.58$, $p<.05$). Negative family relations had significant direct effects on internalising problems ($\beta=.28$, $p<.05$) and externalising problems ($\beta = .22$; $p<.05$). Family instability has moderately significant direct effect on internalising problems ($\beta=.19$, $p<.05$) and there was significant indirect effect (family instability \rightarrow negative family relations \rightarrow internalising problems ($\beta=.15$, $p<.05$)). There was significant direct effect for the link between family instability and externalising problems ($\beta=.20$, $p<.05$). Similarly, there was significant indirect relations between family instability through negative family relations to externalising problems ($\beta=.13$, $p<.05$). To satisfy the final criterion for full mediation, it is required that the magnitude of direct paths between the predictor (i.e. family instability) and outcome (i.e. adolescents' mental health problems) are substantially reduced after the proposed mediators (negative family relations) are estimated in the model. In support of this requirement, the direct paths between family instability and adolescents' mental health problems that were significant when the proposed mediational paths in the model were constrained (i.e. values in brackets in Figure 2), were reduced when the mediational paths were estimated (β s=.14, and .15 for internalising and externalising problems respectively). If the attenuation of direct paths approached a size that is close to zero, it suggests that the mediators fully account for the relation between the predictor and the outcome (Hoyle & Smith, 1994). However, the direct paths from family instability to mental health problems declines but remains significant or clearly non-zero, suggesting that the mediator partially accounts for the predictor-outcome relation. These results partially support the first hypothesis which states that family instability would be indirectly related to adolescent internalising and externalising problems through its influence on negative family relations. As such, there was partial mediation of the relationship between family instability and each of internalising and externalising problems through negative family relations.

Figure 2: Standardised path coefficients for parsimonious model with mediated effects. Path coefficients in brackets are derived from the analysis of an unmediated model in which only direct paths from family instability to internalising and externalising problems were allowed. Age, gender and parents’ socio-economic status were included as covariates in this model, but were not shown in this figure. Curved arrows between internalising and externalising problems represent correlated errors. WAR = Warmth, TRU = Trust, TOG = Togetherness, FUN = Fun between the adolescent and his/her parents, ANX = Anxious/Depressed, WDR = Withdrawn/Depressed, SOM = Somatic complaints, AGG = Aggressive Behaviour, RBB = Rule-Breaking Behaviour, * $p < .05$

Testing the moderating effect of adolescents’ self-control

To test the hypothesised moderating effects of adolescents’ self-control, two models were estimated. In the first model, the main effects of self-control in the prediction of internalising and externalising problems were added to the mediation model. This model had adequate model fit: $\chi^2 (151, N=565) = 224.51$, CFI = .92, TLI = .91, SRMR = .53, RMSEA = .045, a 90% RMSEA confidence interval (.045, .063). The percent variance accounted for in the prediction of internalising problems and externalising problems improved to 47.3% and 35.2% respectively. In the second model, one latent interaction effect (family instability x self-control) was added to the first model. Likelihood ratio tests were used to compare if inclusion of the interaction term improved the model fit. The model with latent interaction effect (LogLFull = -8540.52) and the model without the interaction effect (LogLRestricted = -8547.26) indicate that including the interaction effect improved the overall model fit; LR (df = 2) = 13.48, $p < .05$. These results indicate that including the interaction effect improved the overall fit.

Figure 3 indicates that family instability and self-control had significant negative interaction effects on negative family relations ($\beta = -.22$, $p < .05$). This result shows that

adolescents' self-control served as a buffer that ameliorates the adverse effects of family instability on negative family relations. This result supported Hypothesis 2 that states that self-control will moderate the relationship between family instability and negative family relations.

Figure 3: Unstandardised path coefficients for structural model with latent interaction effects. Age, gender and parent socio-economic status were included as covariates in this model, but are not shown in this figure. Curved arrows among latent variables represent correlated errors. WAR = Warmth; TRU = Trust, TOG = Togetherness, FUN = Fun between the adolescent and his/her parents, ANX = Anxious/Depressed, WDR = Withdrawn/Depressed, SOM = Somatic complaints, AGG = Aggressive Behaviour, RBB = Rule-Breaking Behaviour, SED = Self-Discipline, IMP = Impulsive Control, HAB = Healthy habits, SRE = Self-Regulation in work, REL = Reliability, $*p < .05$

As shown in Figure 3, negative family relations and self-control demonstrated significant negative interaction effect in the prediction of both internalising problems ($\beta = -.18$, $p < .05$) and externalising problems ($\beta = -.20$, $p < .05$), thereby showing that adolescents' self-control served as a buffer that mitigates the adverse effects of negative family relations on problem behaviours. The latent interaction explained additional 3% and 5% of the variance in internalising problems and externalising problems respectively. These results supported the third hypothesis (Hypothesis 3).

To evaluate the significant interaction between negative family relations and self-control as well as between family instability and self-control, the procedures described by Aiken and West (1991) were used. Figure 4 presented slopes or associations between the outcome variables (mental health problems) by levels of independent variable at high and low levels of the moderator (1SD above the mean and 1SD below the mean). Latent variable indicators of

internalising problems and externalising problems were centred in the moderation analysis. Top half of Figure 4 showed that for adolescents with low self-control, higher negative family relations was strongly significantly related to higher internalising problems ($b = .26, p < .05$). However, negative family relations were moderately significantly associated with internalising problems for adolescents having high self-control ($b = .16, p < .05$). This result indicates that self-control is a protective factor mitigating against the risk factor of negative family relations. Bottom half of Figure 4 indicates that externalising problems is a function of negative family relations and adolescents' self-control. The positive relation between negative family relations and externalising problems was lower for adolescents with high self-control ($b = .19, p < .05$) than for those with low self-control ($b = .35, p < .05$). This result also indicates the risk-buffering nature of self-control in the relationship between negative family relations and externalising problems among the adolescents.

The indirect relationship between family instability and internalising and externalising problems via negative parent relations were moderated by self-control. These results support Hypothesis 4. The results for testing hypothesis 4 are shown on Figure 3 which is a moderated mediation model. The main effect of family instability ($b = .67, p < .05$) and interactive effect of family instability and self-control ($b = -.22, p < .05$) were significantly associated with negative family relations (See figure 5 for graphical illustration).

The association between negative family relations and internalising ($b = -.20, p < .05$) and externalising problem ($b = -.18, p < .05$) were also moderated by self-control. The effect of negative family relations was higher in adolescents with higher self-control. The paths between negative family relations and internalising and externalising problems were moderated by self-control. Therefore, Hypothesis 4 was fully supported.

Figure 4: Self-control as a moderator between negative family relations and internalising and externalising problems

Figure 5: Self-control as a moderator between family instability and negative family relations.

Figure 5 indicates that for adolescents with low self-control, higher family instability was strongly related to higher negative family relations ($b=.24, p<.05$). However, family instability was moderately significantly associated with negative family relations of adolescents with high self-control ($b=.17, p<.05$). This result shows that self-control is a protective factor mitigating against the risk factors of family instability.

Discussion

The mediating effect of negative family relations

The purpose of this study was to investigate the mediating role of negative family relations in the relationship between family instability, self-control and adolescent internalising and externalising problems. The moderating effect of self-control on this relationship was also examined.

Results from the present study demonstrated that family instability, self-control and negative family relations predicted internalising and externalising problems. These findings supported those of researchers who reported that internalising and externalising problems were predicted by family instability (Ackerman et. al., 1999; Bakker et. al., 2011; Forman & Davies, 2003). Furthermore, findings from this study agreed with those of previous researchers who found that internalising and externalising problems were predicted by self-control (Bakker et. al., 2011; Gottfredson & Hirschi, 1990; Pung et. al., 2015); and negative family relations (Ackerman et. al., 1999; Forman & Davies, 2003; Loukas et. al., 2010). The explanation for these findings could be that family instability and negative family relations involve unpredictable family environment, conflicts and negative life events that can pose challenges to adolescents which can motivate them to engage in internalising and externalising problems. In the same vein, low self-control can aggravate adolescents' internalising and externalising problems.

Findings from this study indicated that negative family relations partially mediated the relationships between family instability and each of internalising and externalising problems in support of Hypothesis 1. These findings supported the work of previous researchers who found that negative family relations/parenting partially mediated the association between family instability and mental health (internalising and externalising problems) (Conger, Patterson & Ge, 1995; Fauber et. al., 1999; Forman & Davies, 2003). In the present study, family instability indirectly affected adolescents' internalising and externalising problems through negative family relations. That is, family instability may produce deteriorated parents' mental health by increasing their negative family relations, which may in turn lead to more adolescents' internalising and externalising problems. One can explain these findings claiming family instability and negative family relations involve unpredictable family environment, conflicts and negative life events that can pose challenges to adolescents which can motivate them to engage in internalising and externalising problems.

The moderating effect of adolescents' self-control

In support of Hypothesis 2, it was found that self-control moderated the relationship between family instability and negative family relations. The explanation for this finding is that self-control acts as a protective factor by mitigating the impact of family instability on negative family relations. For adolescents with low self-control, higher family instability was strongly related to higher negative family relations. In the case of adolescents with higher self-control, family instability was moderately associated with negative family relations. These results agree with those of previous researchers who reported that self-control, self-regulation or resiliency factor act as protective factor that promotes adolescent resistance to negative family relations and other family risk factors (Bao, Li, Zhang & Wang, 2015; Li, Li, Wang, Zhao, Bao & Wen, 2013; Sun et al., 2015).

Consistent with Hypothesis 3, findings from this study showed that self-control moderated the relationship between negative family relations and adolescents' internalising and externalising problems. These findings suggest that adolescents' self-control is a protective factor in the relationship between negative family relations and youths' mental health problems. These findings are in support of the risk-buffering model of self-control which was proposed to explain how protective factors operate to alter the paths from risk exposure negative family relations to negative outcomes mental health problems (Gerard & Buehler, 2004; Li, Nussbaum & Richard, 2007; Sun et. al., 2015).

The explanation for the findings obtained in this study could be derived from the risk-buffering model which holds that favourable individual characteristics such as self-control mitigate the effects of negative family relations on mental health problems (Bakker et al., 2011; Veenstra et al., 2006). As such, the adolescents involved in this study had high self-control (a favourable individual characteristic) which helped to mitigate the effects of negative family relations on mental health problems. This is in line with the assumptions that under demanding and changing family circumstances self-control assists the adolescents in handling frustration and anger in appropriate ways (Bakker et al., 2011).

In agreement with Hypothesis 4, in this study, self-control was found to moderate the indirect relationship between family instability and internalising and externalising problems via negative family relations. The moderating effect of self-control was not only shown in the relationship between family instability and negative family relations, but also in the relationship between negative family relations and internalising and externalising problems. Effect of high family instability was stronger on negative family relations for adolescents with low self-control.

Invariably, these results indicated that high family instability has more effect on adolescents with low self-control than for adolescents with high self-control. Lower family instability can help adolescents with poor self-control to experience less negative family relations. So, it is less likely that they will experience negative family relations. For students with high self-control their self-regulation ability will serve as a protective factor that helps them to cope with risks family relations. They may suffer less from family instability compared with the adolescent with poor self-control. One can conclude from these results that self-control attenuated the relationship between family instability and negative family relations. Therefore, high self-control is a protective factor on the relationship between family instability and negative family relations.

It was also found that self-control moderated the relationship between negative family relations and internalising and externalising problems. The relationship was strong when the levels of self-control was low but much weaker at high self-control levels. These results concord with those of previous researchers (Gardner, Dishion & Connell, 2008; Goodnight, Bates, Newman, Dodge & Pettit, 2006). Adolescents having low self-control have been found to be more susceptible to experiencing negative family relations and thus they were likely to have more problem behaviours (Goodnight et. al., 2006; Loukas, Roalson & Herrera, 2010). Also, adolescents with high self-control might experience high level of guilt and shame which could protect them from problem behaviours even if they experience negative family relations (Bao et. al., 2015). It could be concluded from these findings that high self-control acts as resilience factor in adverse environments and can protect adolescents from internalising and externalising problems in family risk factors.

Further explanation for the moderation by self-control of the indirect path from family instability to mental health problems via negative family relations is due to the Nigerian culture that is collectivistic in nature which emphasises the importance of conformity to societal and in-group rules and norms. The individual's ability to inhibit one's emotions and behavioural tendencies in situations that require behaving in socially appropriate manners is highly valued and encouraged in Nigerian culture. For example, when adolescents experience family instability and negative family relations, self-control and collectivistic cultural orientation can serve as moderators and prevent them from mental health problems.

Theoretical and practical implications

This study makes some contributions to existing literature in respect of the effects of family instability, self-control, and negative family relations on adolescents' mental health problems. From the theoretical perspective, this study contributes to mental health problem research by providing evidence that negative family relations mediated the relationship between family instability and mental health (internalising and externalising) problems and that self-control moderated the mediated relationship. Hitherto, most research on the correlates of mental health problems have examined the direct effects with few using gender, ethnicity and self-control as moderators of the relationship between family instability and mental health problems and came out with equivocal results (Bakker et al., 1999; Ackerman et al., 1999). The moderated mediation results obtained in this study can assist researchers in having deeper understanding of the mechanisms through which family instability and negative family relations could be buffered by self-control to reduce mental health problems. The partial mediation obtained in this study showed that there are other factors (mediators) such as aggression, depression and stress in addition to negative family relations which may increase the incidence of mental health problems. Therefore, in future research on mental health problems, aggression, depression and stress factors should be included.

About practical perspective, this study has shown the importance of family instability, negative family relations and self-control in preventing mental health problems among adolescents. Intervention programmes such as behaviour modification techniques and teaching of coping strategies designed by counselling psychologists for parents and adolescents that focus on coping with family instability and improving positive family relations and development of self-control skills are likely to be effective in preventing adolescents' internalising and externalising problems.

Strengths and Limitations

This study has some strengths and limitations. To avoid inflated correlations due to shared method variance bias, multi-informant data were used. Mental health problems (YSR and CBCL), family instability, negative family relations, self-control and parental socio-economic status were assessed through parents' reports and adolescents' self-reports. In this study, the mean of the standardised parents' and adolescents' scores were used as measures of the instrument. Also, the present researcher worked to minimize this bias by ensuring that respondents' anonymity was protected and evaluation comprehension was reduced. The respondents were told to answer the questions as honestly as possible and that there were no right or wrong answers. Ambiguous items were removed from the questionnaires. Each point on the response format was labeled instead of only the end points to minimize ambiguity. Different scale formats were used for the predictors and criterion variables in the questionnaires as recommended by Podsakoff, Mackenzie and Podsakoff (2012). The instruments had good construct validity. Cross-sectional data were used for analysis as such one cannot undertake causal interpretations in this study. Future researchers may conduct longitudinal study to be able to make casual inferences.

Conclusion

Despite these limitations, an important strength of this study is that it has demonstrated that self-control moderated the indirect paths from family instability to mental health problems through negative family relations. Overall, the findings of this study have implications for the prevention of adolescents' mental health problems.

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Perceived knowledge of causes and prevention strategies for sexual violence among university students in Niger Delta region of Nigeria

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Abstract

Sexual violence is a major public health problem that disregards basic human rights globally. Worldwide, mass media reports have shown an increased rate of sexual violence in higher institutions of learning, therefore exploring the knowledge of causes and strategies in prevention of sexual violence among undergraduate students is crucial in order to promote a coordinated movement against it. This descriptive cross-sectional study is aimed at assessing the knowledge of causes and strategies employed in prevention of sexual violence among undergraduate students in Niger Delta region of Nigeria.

Data were collected using the questionnaire and a multistage sampling technique was used to obtain a sample of 400 respondents from the population. Data analysis was done using SPSS version 20.0 at a 5% level of significance. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data collected. These were presented in tables and figures.

All the respondents have heard of sexual violence and opined that sexual violence is prevalent in the university. Most of the respondents demonstrated adequate knowledge on sexual violence but poor knowledge of where to report cases of sexual violence in the university. The major causes identified were Inadequate Punishment of perpetrators (100%), Keeping silent and not reporting the offenders 392 (98.0%), Portrayal of women as sex objects in the media (96.5%), Alcohol and drugs (95.5%), Inadequate security on campus (99.5%), Indecent dressing 374 (93.5%). The major strategies identified for preventing sexual violence include severe punishment for perpetrators/offenders (100%), adherence to dress code of the school (99.0%), mass campaigns against sexual violence (98.5%), enact laws prohibiting pornography (98.5%), avoid late night outing/party (97%), provision of adequate security on campus and avoid walking alone on lonely path (96.5%).

Keywords: Sexual violence factors, Sexual Violence mitigation, Undergraduates

Introduction

Sexual violence does not only have a profound impact on the physical and mental health of an individual but it is also a serious violation of human rights associated with an increased risk of sexual and reproductive health consequences; both immediate and long-term (WHO, 2018).

Sexual violence is any sexual act or attempt to obtain a sexual act by violence or coercion, unwanted sexual comments or advances, or acts to traffic, or otherwise, directed against a

person's sexuality using coercion, by any person regardless of their relationship to the victim, in any setting, including but not limited to home and work. Sexual violence ranges from forcible rape to non-physical forms of pressure, psychological intimidation, blackmail, harassment or other threats that compel persons to engage in sex against their will (Sendo & Meleku, 2015). It also includes forced kissing, forced breast and genital fondling, attempted rape and forced exposure to pornography (Eze, 2013).

Awosusi. and Ogundana (2015) pointed out that overwhelming effect of sexual violence is much on the victim and could affect the trust and feeling of safety irrespective of age, gender or socio-economic status of the victim. Also, the damaging effect of sexual violence could spread to the parents, spouse, friends, co-workers or children of the victims. Nevertheless, sexual violence has serious health consequences which has been linked directly or indirectly, with adverse reproductive and mental health problems including, unwanted pregnancy, unsafe abortion, gynecological complications, STIs including HIV/AIDS infections, suicide, frigidity among others in survivors (Matthew, Avid, Jama, Curtis, James, Linda, et.al 2011; Bekele, Kaso, Gebremariam & Deressa, 2015; Sendo & Meleku, 2015) .

Globally, an estimated one in three women are sexually abused, and the incidence is not restricted to any age group. Although, studies have shown that the prevalence of sexual violence is more among students (Smit & Plessis 2011, Awosusi & Ogundana, 2015). Sexual violence is a major issue in tertiary institutions of education worldwide with one in five experienced rape or attempted rape in their lifetime (Bekele et al., 2015). One in five college females are victims of acquaintance rape during their academic career and less than 5% of college women who are victims of sexual assault report their victimization globally (Sendo & Meleku, 2015; Dills, Fowler, & Payne, 2016). Approximately 37% of female rape victims were first raped between the ages of 18-24years while 19% experienced attempted or completed sexual assault after entering college (CDC, 2014). Krebs, et al., (2016) also reported a prevalence rate 10.3%, of sexual violence among female undergraduate with completed rape constituting 4.1%. For men, the study showed 3.1% sexual violence with 0.8% experienced rape (Krebs, Lindquist, Berzofsky, Shook-Sa, Peterson, Planty et.al, 2016).

Furthermore, Gross, Winslett, Roberts, and Gohm, (2006) reported that 27% of college females have experienced some form of unwanted sexual contact. Both male and females are victims of sexual violence but it is more common in females than males with an estimate of 18.3% in females and 1.4% in males (WHO, 2010; Black, Basile, Breiding, Smith, Walters, Merrick, & Stevens, 2011). Evidence in existing literature buttressed the fact that women and children are mostly at risk of sexual violence, and some are more vulnerable than others, especially young girls, women with disabilities, indigenous women, women from culturally and linguistically diverse backgrounds (Sendo & Meleku, 2015; Awosusi & Ogundana, 2015; Abrahams, Devries, Watts, Pallitto, Petzoid, Shamu, & Garcia-Moreno, 2014; Onah, 2010). However, the reported figures on sexual violence are said to be inaccurate and often underestimate, as studies have indicated that most cases of sexual violence are under-reported by the victims because of the associated stigma, closeness of the assailant or the difficult legal requirements needed to prove the cases leading to limited access to justice (Ezechi, Adesolamusa, David, Wapmuk, Gbajabiamila, Eugeniaidigbe, et.al, 2016; Abdulkadir, et al. 2011; Kullima, Kawuwa, Audu, Mairiga & Bukar, 2010).

According to Cullen, Fisher and Turner (2000), more than 90% of sexual assault victims on college campuses do not report the assault. Odu, Falana and Olotu, (2014) affirmed that non-disclosure of sexual violence has been linked with shame, fear of rejection among colleagues, stigmatization, humiliation, guilt, fear of not being believed and cultural belief. Most cultures

have always projected sexual violence especially rape as shame rather than a huge crime (Awosusi & Ogundana, 2015). Sometimes, the perpetrators are exonerated and the victims are blamed as having encouraged the act through questionable character, action or mode of dressing. This tends to fuel the practice of crime and promote non-disclosure by victims. The perpetrators of the sexual violence tend to be someone well known to the victims from the environs like boyfriends, colleague, family members or sometimes strangers. Krebs, Lindquist, Warner, Fisher & Martin (2007) stated that eight out of 10 victims knew the person who sexually assaulted them. However, in higher institutions of learning, studies have shown older male students, peers, lecturers and administrative workers of universities as perpetrators of sexual violence (Adamu & Abebe, 2016; Chikwiri & Lemmer, 2014; Iliyasu, Abubakar, Aliyu, Galadanc, & Salihu, 2011). This violent incident most often takes place in the victim's home, lonely area, office or school environment, in the house of a friend, relative or neighbour (Matthew et.al., 2011; Bekele et.al., 2015)

Nevertheless, various evidences have shown that, sexual violence is on the increase in Nigerian higher institutions of learning and the major individuals at risk were the weak female students which both, the lecturers and fellow male students take undue advantage to abuse (Abubakar, Mohammed, Bala, Abdulkarim, & Mohammed, 2010). Therefore, exploring knowledge on the causes and strategies to curb sexual violence among undergraduate students is a crucial step in the primary prevention of sexual violence in tertiary institutions of learning

Materials and method

A descriptive cross-sectional survey design was used to assess the knowledge of causes and strategies used in the prevention of sexual violence among undergraduate students.

Study Setting and Population

The study was carried out at the Niger Delta University (NDU) Amassoma, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The university has twelve faculties, forty-four departments and four campuses. It has over ten thousand students living both in and off campus. The target population of the study is the undergraduate students of Niger Delta University.

Sample and sampling technique

The sample size of this study was determined using Fishers formula.

$$n = \frac{Z^2 P(1-p)}{d^2}$$

Multistage sampling technique was used to select respondents for the study population.

First stage: A random sampling technique, the “fishbowl technique” was used. All the names of the faculties were written on slips and put in a bowl. The slips were drawn from the bowl one at a time to select the 5 faculties required for the study. The selected faculties include Management Science, Engineering, Pharmacy, Education, and Agricultural Technology

Second stage: A disproportionate stratified random sampling technique was used. A list of various departments in each of the faculties selected was obtained and seven of these departments were selected using disproportionate stratified sampling. The selected departments include: Banking/Finance, Mechanical Engineering, Petroleum Engineering, Pharmacy, Educational Foundation, Vocational/Industrial Education and Crop and soil science

Third stage: 400 respondents were conveniently selected from the selected departments. Questionnaires were administered to these respondents. These respondents were met in their classrooms between 9.00am and 5.00pm daily from Monday to Friday. The data collection took four weeks.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument used for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was divided into four sections namely: section A elicited information on the demographic data of the respondents, section B was on level of knowledge on sexual violence, section C was on the causes of sexual violence, while section D composed of questions on strategies to prevent sexual violence. Face and content validity of the research instrument was done by colleague and experts in the field of study, while the Cronbach’s alpha result for reliability test was found to be 0.84.

Data analysis

The data obtained was analyzed using Statistical Product Service Solutions (SPSS) version 20.0. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were employed in analyzing the data collected and level of significance was set at 5% (0.05) such that significant associations were established when $p < 0.05$

Ethical consideration

A letter was written to the university management. An approval was given to the researchers through the students’ affair unit. All information concerning the research was thoroughly explained to the participants and freedom of withdrawal at any point was also emphasized. Respondents consent was obtained. Information given by the participants was treated with outmost confidentiality and anonymity was maintained as participants’ names were not required while completing or filling the questionnaires.

Results

Table 1: Socio-demographic data of respondents

VARIABLES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
AGE IN YEARS		
18-20	26	6.5
21-25	204	51.0
26-30	138	34.5
Above 30	32	8.0
SEX		
Male	168	42.0
Female	232	58.0
MARITAL STATUS		
Single	336	84.0
Married	60	15.0
Widowed	4	1.0
RELIGION		
Christianity	356	89.0
Islam	44	11.0
ETHNICITY		
Ijaw	196	49.0
Hausa	18	4.5
Yoruba	44	11.0
Ibo	54	13.5
Others	88	22.0

Table 1 shows that half of the respondents 204 (51.0) were between the ages of 21-25years with a mean age of 25years. More than half of the respondents 116(58%) were females while 84(42%) were males, 168 (84%) were singles and 178(89%) were Christians

Figure 1 shows that majority 240(60%) of the respondents heard of sexual violence from mass media, 48(12%) from seminar and family each, 36 (9.0%) from health facility and 28(7.0%) from literature.

Table 2: Knowledge on Sexual Violence among respondents (n=400)

Knowledge Questions	Response	Frequency	Percentage	Decision
Have heard of sexual violence	Yes	400	100	Good
	No	0	0.0	
Sexual violence is on the increase in higher institutions	Yes	398	99.5	Good
	No	2	0.5	
Sexual violence is a criminal offence	Yes	400	100	Good
	No	0	0.0	
Sexual violence is worth reporting to relevant authorities?	Yes	326	81.5	Good
	No	74	18.5	
Awareness of proper channel to report cases of sexual violence on campus	Yes	195	48.7	Poor
	No	205	51.3	
Sexual violence increases sexual and reproductive health problems	Yes	394	98.5	Good
	No	6	1.5	
Do you know anyone who is a victim of sexual violence on campus	Yes	400	100.0	Good
	No	0	0.0	
Gender of the known victims	Female	399	99.8	Good
	Male	1	0.2	
Males can be victims of sexual assaults	Yes	322	80.5	Good
	No	78	19.5	
Coercion into sexual acts in return for good scores or gift is a form of sexual violence.	Yes	198	49.5	Poor
	No	202	50.5	

Table 2 shows that all respondents 400 (100%) have heard of sexual violence and knew that it is a criminal offence. Majority of the respondents 398 (99.5%) were of the opinion that sexual violence is on the increase in higher institutions of learning and 326 (81.5%) said that sexual violence is worth reporting to relevant authorities. However, more than half of the respondents 205 (51.3%) have poor knowledge on where to report cases of sexual violence on campus. All respondents knew at least one victim of sexual violence on campus and affirmed that 399 (99.8%) of them were females, despite this fact; majority 322 (80.5%) attested that males can also be victims of sexual violence. Half of the respondents 202 (50.5%) did not see coercion into sexual acts in return for good scores or gift as a form of sexual violence.

Table 3: Causes of Sexual Violence (n=400).

Causes of sexual violence	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Alcohol and drugs	Yes	382	95.5
	No	18	4.5
Inadequate Punishment for perpetrators	Yes	400	100.0
	No	0	0.0
Violence and conflict on campuses	Yes	332	83.0
	No	68	17.0
Beliefs that students have no right to refuse sexual advances	Yes	358	89.5
	No	42	10.5
Attending late night parties/ classes	Yes	346	86.5
	No	54	13.5

Inadequate security on campus	Yes	398	99.5
	No	2	0.5
Portrayal of women as sex objects in the media	Yes	386	96.5
	No	14	3.5
Keeping silence and not reporting the offender	Yes	392	98.0
	No	8	2.0
Indecent dressing can lead to sexual violence	Yes	374	93.5
	No	26	6.5
Lack of moral on the part of the perpetrators	Yes	302	75.5
	No	98	24.5
Children sexually violated are more prone to be perpetrators of sexual violence	Yes	154	38.5
	No	246	61.5

With regards to the causes of sexual violence, majority of the respondents 382 (95.5%) stated that alcohol and drugs play a role in sexual violence; 400(100%) opined that inadequate punishment for perpetrators, 332 (83.0%) said violence and conflict on campuses, 358 (89.5%) were of the opinion that the belief that students have no right to refuse sexual advances can lead to sexual violence, 346 (86.5%) opined that attending late night parties/ classes can predispose one to sexual violence, 398 (99.5%) mentioned inadequate security on campus, 386(96.5%) said portrayal of women as sex objects in the media, 392 (98.0%) said keeping silent and not reporting the offenders, 374 (93.5%) mentioned indecent dressing, 302 (75.5%) said lack of morals on the part of the perpetrators while only 154(38.5%) opined that children sexually violated are more prone to be perpetrator of sexual violence later in life

Table 4: Strategies for Preventing Sexual Violence (n=400).

Strategies preventing sexual violence	Frequency	Percentage
Mass campaigns against sexual violence on campus	394	98.5
Avoiding private meetings with strangers	376	94.0
Provision of adequate security on campus	386	96.5
Severe punishment for perpetrators	400	100.0
Avoid late night outing/party	388	97.0
Enact laws prohibiting pornography	394	98.5
Provision of street lights	384	96.0
Cultural and societal norms promoting sexual violence against women should be discouraged	390	97.5
Adherence to the dress code of the school	396	99.0
Avoid walking alone on lonely path	386	96.5
Orientation of students on safety measures to prevent sexual violence	328	82.0

Table 4 shows that 394 (98.5%) of respondents identified mass campaigns against sexual violence on campus as one of the strategies for preventing sexual violence, 376 (94.0%) said avoiding private meetings with strangers, provision of adequate security on campus 386 (96.5%), 400 (100%) suggested severe punishment for perpetrators/offenders, 388 (97.0%) said avoidance of late night outing/party, 394 (98.5%) said government should enact laws prohibiting pornography, 384 (96.0%) said provision of street lights at night, 390 (97.5%) said that cultural and societal norms promoting sexual violence against women should be discouraged, 396

(99.0%) said adherence to the dress code of the school, 386 (96.5%) mentioned avoiding walking alone on lonely path while 328 (82.0%) opted that orientation of students on safety measures can help prevent sexual violence on campus.

Table 5: Relationship Between respondents’ level of Knowledge and Some demographic variables (gender and marital statuses) (n=400).

Variables		Knowledge on sexual violence		Total	Pearson’s chi-square			Remark
		High	Low		X ²	df	P-value	
Gender	Male	142	26	168	0.740	1	0.140	Not significant
	Female	192	40	232				
Marital Status	Single	278	58	336	0.910	2	0.674	Not significant
	Married	52	8	60				
	Widowed	2	2	4				

Table 5 shows that there is no significant relationship between gender of respondents under study and their level of knowledge of sexual violence with $X^2 = 0.740$; $P\text{-value} = 0.140 > 0.05$. Also, no significant relationship was found between marital status of respondents under study and their level of knowledge of sexual violence with $X^2 = 0.910$; $P\text{-value} = 0.674 > 0.05$. This implied that the level of knowledge of the respondents was independent of their gender and marital status, Hence, both null hypotheses were accepted.

Discussion of finding

In this study, half of the respondents were between the ages of 21-25 years and were single. This shows that majority of the respondents were in their 20s which is the usual age range for the university students. Boba and Lilley, (2009) stated that individuals between the ages of 16-24 experience sexual violence at rates four times higher than the rate for all individuals.

The study revealed that all respondents were of the opinion that sexual violence is on the increase in higher institutions and it is a criminal offence that is worth reporting to relevant authorities. However, existing literatures showed that about 50 to 90% of all victims may not report or disclose sexual violence that they have experienced due to shame, humiliation, guilt, fear of the perpetrator, cultural taboos; backlash, character assassination, victimization at the hands of other lecturers, co-students and society at large (Eguagie, 2016; Odu, Falana, & Olotu, 2014; Ado, Njoku & Bako 2010; Green, Adriana, & Mavis, 2001). Mouzos et al. (2004) affirmed that some victims do not even consider the incident serious enough to warrant reporting, let alone as a criminal offence.

All respondents knew at least one victim of sexual violence on campus and affirmed that 99.8% of them were females, despite this fact; majority (80.5%) attested that males can also be victims of sexual violence. This implies that sexual violence is strongly gendered with females mostly affected, which is in line with the study conducted by Eguagie, (2016) where all the sexual violence victims were female students. Of which majority did nothing after being raped, and

others made some kind of feeble report of being raped to friends, while very few reported to either course adviser, parents or guardians (Eguagie, 2016; Awosusi & Ogundana, 2015).

The study also showed that majority of the respondents opted that alcohol and drugs are major causes of sexual violence. This is corroborated by Grisso, Hirschinger, and Anderson (2009), who reported that alcohol and hard drugs have been shown to play a role in sexual violence as it provides opportunity for antisocial behaviors. This implies that people are more likely to act violently under the influence of alcohol or psychoactive drugs because they do not consider that they will be held accountable for their behavior (Katy & Trevor, 2017; Grisso et.al, 2009).

It is worthy to note that half of the respondents did not see sexual acts in return for good scores or gift as a form of sexual violence. This implies that socio economic problems can exert huge pressures on students making them submissive in the face of social challenges and cannot perceive it as sexual violence. Thus, there is need to equip and empower the girl child. Sendo and Meleku (2015) buttressed the fact that 29.9% of the sexually active female students had begun sexual activity with strangers for the exchange of gifts or money. However, female students, who came from lower income families, are tempted into sexual liaisons by gifts and other promises from boyfriends, teachers and others in most societies. Furthermore all respondents concurred that lack of morals is a reason for sexual violence. This corroborates the study of Fahmy et al. (2014), who reported that the motive for occurrence of sexual harassment/violence were lack of religious consciousness followed by a lack of supervision on the internet and media.

The World Health Organization (2010) stated that social and cultural gender norms place women and girls at increased risk of sexual violence and support the acceptability of sexual violence. This was also pointed out by the respondents, as majority maintained that portrayal of women as sex objects on the media and indecent dressing increase sexual violence. Therefore, the key element in the primary prevention of sexual violence is changing social norms that support sexual violence in any form (WHO, 2010).

Most of the respondents opined that a place where violence and conflict occur breeds sexual violence. According to MADRE (2011), areas where major disasters or conflicts occur can play a key role in increasing rates of sexual violence since access to justice may either be reduced or destroyed. Most of the respondents were of the opinion that children sexually violated are more prone to be perpetrators of sexual violence. This is in harmony with Borowsky and Hogan (2007) who stated that about one in five sexually abused children continue in later life to molest children themselves. Such experiences may lead to a pattern of behavior where the perpetrator regularly justifies being violent, denies doing wrong, and has false and unhealthy notions about sexuality.

In all, most of the respondents demonstrated adequate knowledge on causes of sexual violence but poor knowledge of where to report cases of sexual violence in the university. This may be due to the fact that student handbooks and codes of conduct for staff and students are generally 'silent' on this (Okakwu, 2015).

The study also revealed major strategies for preventing sexual violence which include, severe punishment for perpetrators/offenders (100%), adherence to the dress code of the school (99.0%), mass campaigns against sexual violence (98.5%), enact laws prohibiting pornography (98.5%), avoid late night outing/party (97%) Provision of adequate security on campus (96.5%), avoid walking alone on lonely path (96.5%), and Provision of street lights at night (96.0%). This corroborates similar study conducted among female students in tertiary institutions in northern part of Nigeria where respondents suggested enforcement of dress codes, punishment of offenders, sex education and awareness, improving security and advocating for legislation

against sexual assault as critical steps toward preventing sexual violence among the students (Abubakar et.al, 2010).

Conclusion

Sexual violence is a major public health problem which is highly prevalent in Nigerian higher institutions of learning. Therefore, critical analysis of the causes and strategies is the initial step in planning interventions to eradicate sexual violence among university students. The finding from this study had revealed that the respondents had poor knowledge on where to report cases of sexual violence on campus despite the good knowledge on causes of sexual violence and strategies to curb it.

Notwithstanding, all forms of sexual violence need the urgent attention of family, institutions, government, non government organization and the international community in other to eradicate sexual violence in educational institutions as well as society at large.

Recommendation

Based on the findings in this study, the following recommendations were made:

- Nurses and other healthcare practitioners in collaboration with the ministry of justice and education, and other nongovernmental organizations should design programs to raise awareness and discourage many of the tales that hinder people from reporting sexual violence.
- Ministry of Justice should ensure severe penalties for offenders and perpetrators.
- The university authority should have an accessible Committee that look into all forms of sexual violence where the victims can report without victimization
- Provision of adequate security measures such as Close Circuit Television (CCTV), street lights and armed security men etc by the school authority.

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The relative influence of psycho-demographic factors on perceived psychological well-being of adolescents with hearing impairment in Southwest Nigeria

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Abstract

This study, investigated some psycho-demographic variables on the perceived psychological well-being of hearing-impaired adolescents in south-west Nigeria. The study adopted survey research design of ex-post facto type. Purposive sampling was used to select eight Senior Secondary Schools and 491 adolescents with hearing impairment using a battery-operated audiometer. Data were analysed using multiple regression statistics. The relative contributions of the independent variables to the variance of perceived psychological well-being were in the following order of magnitude: locus of control ($\beta = .291$, $t = 7.090$, $P < 0.05$); meaning of life ($\beta = .186$, $t = 3.942$, $P < 0.05$); self-concept ($\beta = .129$, $t = 2.643$, $P < 0.05$); self-efficacy ($\beta = .116$, $t = 2.759$, $P < 0.05$); age ($\beta = .054$, $t = 1.250$, $P < 0.05$); gender ($\beta = .054$, $t = 1.241$, $P < 0.05$); socio-economic status ($\beta = .045$, $t = 1.076$, $P < 0.05$) and emotional intelligence ($\beta = .003$, $t = .065$, $P < 0.05$). Psycho-demographic variables (locus of control, meaning of life, self-concept, self-efficacy, age and gender), influenced perceived psychological well-being of adolescents with hearing impairment. Service providers could, therefore, take into cognisance the relative influence of the variables when rendering professional help to adolescents with hearing impairment. Intervention programmes could also be designed on the factors to enhance the perceived psychological well-being of this category of adolescents.

Keywords: Perceived Psychological well-being, Adolescents, Hearing impairment, Locus of control, Meaning of life

Introduction

The quantity of individuals suffering one form of impairment or the other in Nigeria and the classifications are not exactly known but rather it has been assessed that there are somewhere in the range of 13,000,000 and 14,000,000 people with impairments in the nation (Nwuga, 2006). It has additionally been evaluated that 7,980,000 of this all-inclusive community representing 57% are adolescents (Nwuga, 2006).

In any case, the breakdown of kinds of handicap for adolescents aged 12-19 detailed by the 2006 enumeration uncovered that the most widely recognized sort of inability is deafness (30%), to which ought to be included the individuals who are both hard of hearing and unable to speak (an extra 14%). This insight, along these lines, subsumes the general figure of 14.1 million (fourteen point one million) of all classifications of handicapped individuals independent of nature of incapacity in Nigeria (Source: 2006 Census (NpopC, J2008). The measurable inference that could be drawn from these figures as revealed by the 2006 evaluation is that, Nigeria has the

aggregate number of 4.794 million (four point seven hundred and ninety-four million) hearing impaired adolescents.

The foregoing measurements bear witness to the predominance of different forms of impairments in Nigeria, most particularly among adolescents. The specialist psychological impacts of this could be debilitating in form of social alienation, self-pity and rejection, emotional damage and withdrawal symptoms. These could aggregately influence the perceived psychological well-being of adolescents, for the most part, those with hearing impairment.

In addition, adolescents with hearing impairment often confront more than the issue of acknowledgment, in that they want to escape from the biases and discriminations that have had the impact of casting them into a minority (Nagler, 1992). In this light, adolescents with hearing impairment could likewise be faced with a few difficulties like social alienation, self-pity and rejection, emotional damage and withdrawal manifestation and demonization; which could have impacts on their psychological well-being (Nagler, 1992).

Psychological well-being is generally tended to as a result build in youngster improvement (Balatsky and Diener, 1993; Belsky, 1998; Brown, Wallace Jnr and Williams, 2001). Albeit psychological well-being is a basic component for individual improvement, analysts have not had an accord about the definition and even the segments of psychological well-being (Lorion, 2000). In any case, it is an imperative develop in Psychology. Keyes, Shmotkin and Ryff (2002) distinguish abstract well-being from psychological well-being by stating that emotional well-being is assessment of life as far as fulfillment and harmony among positive and negative effect, while psychological well-being involves view of engagement with existential difficulties of life. Another regular method to survey psychological well-being is by measuring negative attributes, for example, depression as opposed to positive parts of well-being (Flouri and Buchanan, 2003; Lawton, 1984; Moore, Evans, Brooks-Gunn and Roth, 2001). Subsequently, there are numerous elements that could add to a higher or lower level of perceived psychological well-being in adolescents.

In 1977, Albert Bandura at Stanford University introduced the concept of perceived self-efficacy with regards to intellectual conduct alteration. It has been discovered that a solid feeling of individual efficacy is identified with better wellbeing, higher accomplishment, and more social integration (Zimmerman, 2000). This concept has in this way, been connected to such assorted territories as school accomplishment, emotional clutters, mental and physical wellbeing, vocation decision, and sociopolitical change. As a multidimensional develop, it influences human functioning straightforwardly and indirectly through its influence on different determinants, for example, inspiration, self-direction, attribution and emotion (Bandura, 1997). While result anticipations allude to the impression of the conceivable outcomes of one's activity, perceived self-efficacy pertains to individual activity control or agency. A man who has faith in being ready to cause an occasion can lead a more dynamic and self-determined life course. (Bandura,1995; Wallston and Wallston, 1994). Self-efficacy levels can upgrade or obstruct the inspiration to act. Individuals with high self-efficacy perform additionally challenging errands. They set themselves higher objectives and stick to them (Locke and Latham, 1990). Activities are pre-formed in thought, and individuals foresee either hopeful or critical situations in line with their level of Self-efficacy. Once a move has been made, high self-strong people invest more exertion and persevere longer than those with low Self-efficacy. At the point when difficulties happen, the former recoup all the more rapidly and maintain the duty to their objectives (Locke and Latham, 1990). Self-efficacy likewise enables individuals to choose challenging settings, investigate their surroundings, or make new circumstances. A feeling of ability can be procured

by dominance encounter, vicarious experience, verbal influence, or physiological criticism (Bandura, 1977).

Emotional Intelligence (EI) as a variable in this investigation is an omnibus develop that fits into each life attempt. Goleman's (1995) study of guardians uncovered that there is an overall pattern for the present age of kids to be more vexed emotionally than the past age: lonelier and more discouraged, angrier and unrulier, more anxious and inclined to stress, more imprudent and forceful. He indicates that there is an increasing need to address the emotional wellbeing of adolescents. The test in addressing this issue, anyway is learning how to manage adolescents regarding sound emotional improvement. Goleman (1995), states that understudies who have emotional capability can all the more likely manage weights of companion governmental issues, the higher demands required for psychological well-being, scholastics, and the enticements of liquor, medications and sex.

Meaninglessness is amazingly, one more issue facing adolescents. Reker, Peakcock and Wong (1987) define meaning which is another variable of interest in the examination as making sense, request, or rationality out of one's presence, and to having a reason and objective toward which one can endeavor. Meaninglessness in adolescents is additionally intensified through the psychology of progress at this period. For instance, the period is described by beginning of pubescence, physical and sexual development, improvement of self-distinguishing proof, increased interest in sex, and extraordinary associations with inverse sex; and most importantly, the weakness to peer influence as to image and social conduct. Qualities furnish one with a blueprint for life lead; values disclose to one why one lives as well as how to live (May and Yalom, 1995). For adolescents, meaning is made by their exertion in trying to build up a firm personality, meaningful connections and to be beneficial and imaginative individuals (Erickson, 1963).

Locus of control (LOC) which was additionally investigated as a variable of interest in the examination created to portray the job of reinforcement in conduct. In this hypothesis, it is the estimation of the objective towards which one is striving in combination with the anticipation that a given conduct will prompt an attractive result that determines conduct. Perceived control of reinforcement is depicted as the way an individual view the association between his or her conduct and the event of remuneration or discipline (Phares, 1996).

Self-concept is the following in the variety of psychological variables for this investigation. A man's self-concept, by ethicalness of it being a rundown formulation of his or her status, is in the bargain an outline formulation of his or her perceived conduct conceivable outcomes, and of the cutoff points on these (Ossorio, 1978, 1998; Roberts, 1995).

Among a few variables affecting psychological well-being, socio-economic status (SES), gender and age have been perceived as the extensive influences on kids' psychological well-being in social psychology (McLeod and Owens, 2004). Felner Brand, Dubois, Adan, Mulhall and Evans (1995) give proof that low financial influenced the level of school performance/accomplishment and socioemotional worry for immaturity. As of late, it was affirmed again that family income was related with the level of externalizing and internalizing issues, for example, defiance, impulsivity, nervousness, depression, and so forth in puberty (Dearing, McCartney, and Taylor, 2006) Moreover, McLeod and Owens (2004) uncover that destitution history in early youth was adversely connected with scholarly accomplishment and self-regard in later immaturity.

Not at all like the past factor of socio-economic SES (destitution) which have an immediate association with psychological well-being, the investigations about gender and psychological well-being show blended outcomes (Woody and Green, 2001; Mcleod and Owens, 2004; Seo, 2007). By and large, past examinations have demonstrated that young ladies have better

psychological well-being or less emotional/conduct issues than young men (Eme, 1979). Then again, there is proof that young ladies have more psychological issues than young men do. Nolen-Hoeksema (2001) contend that more immature young ladies detailed depression than young men and conveyed chance elements for depression.

At present, older individuals are thought to have higher levels of psychological well-being up to a certain age (Isaacowitz & Smith, 1999). With regard to depressive symptoms among adolescents and adults, adolescents were found to exhibit high levels of depressive symptoms, and the elderly showed low levels of depressive symptoms (Nolen-Hoeksema, 2001). It is certain that older individuals do not suffer from many events that are uncontrollable or duplicate, and therefore have no greater risk of depression. The literature corresponds to higher levels of negative emotional responses in the elderly. The researchers found that younger people tend to report lower levels of satisfaction with life over time. These studies combine to show that adults in the older age group have higher levels of satisfaction with life.

From the above, it is appropriate to examine the relative contributions of each psychodemographic variable to the perceived psychological well-being of adolescents with hearing disabilities. This is one of the other reasons for the lack of research in the region in Nigeria on the effect of variables in this study on the perceived psychological well-being of hearing impaired adolescents.

Research Question

What are the relative contributions of each of the independent or explanatory variables to the prediction of perceived psychological well-being of the hearing-impaired adolescents?

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted *ex-post facto* research design. It is a type of design that seeks to establish cause-effect relationships but the researcher usually has no control over the variables of interest and therefore cannot manipulate them.

Population

The target population for this study consisted of all hearing-impaired adolescents in Ekiti, Lagos, Ogun, Ondo, Osun and Oyo states of Nigeria. These states are in the south western part of Nigeria.

Sampling Procedure and Samples

The purposive sampling technique was used to select participants for the study. Four hundred and ninety-one (491) hearing impaired adolescents were sampled using a battery-operated audiometer (as identification instrument); from Senior Secondary I to Senior Secondary II in eight schools for the disabled in Ekiti, Lagos, Ogun, Ondo, and Oyo States of Nigeria. Osun state earlier slated for study was precluded owing to non-existence of the senior secondary school for the handicapped in the state as at the time of this research.

Instrumentation

The instruments adapted consist of Section A which is on Hearing Impaired Adolescents' Socio-Economic Status Scale ($r=0.90$). Section B comprises items on Emotional Intelligence scale ($r=0.90$); section C, General Perceived Self Efficacy Scale ($r=0.75$); section D, Rotter's

Locust of Control Inventory and Survey ($r=0.76$); section E, Adolescent Personality Data Inventory (APDI) – Self-Concept Sub-Scale ($r=0.74$); section F, Well-being Manifestation Measure Scale ($r=0.89$) and section G, Personal Meaning Profile ($r=0.93$).

Procedure for Data Collection

The administration of the questionnaire lasted for five weeks. The participants were informed about the study and their rights regarding participation. The researchers then administered the questionnaire packet. The researchers sought the permission from the parents or sponsors, and school authorities of the participants for the administration of the questionnaire. To facilitate the administration, two research assistants were trained and used for the study. Specifically, in order to resolve the problem of communication between the researchers and the participants who were hearing impaired, sign language interpreters were utilized that doubled as research assistants and communication facilitator. During the period of administration of instruments in each state, the samples complained that the items on the questionnaires were too many. In order to reduce attrition, students were provided with incentives to motivate and sustain their interests while completing the instruments. Also, on completing each section of the questionnaire, participants were asked to rest at intervals since they have short-span attention.

Data Analysis

The data collected were analyzed using Multiple regression. Multiple regression analysis was used to determine the relative contributions of each of the eight independent variables in predicting hearing impaired adolescents perceived psychological well-being.

Results

Research Question

What are the relative contributions of each of independent variables to the prediction of psychological well-being of the hearing-impaired adolescents in southwest Nigeria?

The parameter estimates of the contributions of each of the selected variables to the prediction of psychological well-being of the hearing-impaired adolescents in Southwest Nigeria.

Table 1 Relative Contributions of the Eight Independent Variables on Psychological Well Being of the Hearing-Impaired Adolescents

Factors	B	Std. Error	Beta B	Rank	T	Significance
(Constant)	-37.004	12.483			-2.964	.003
1. Age	.309	.247	.054	5 th	1.250	.212
2. Gender	1.961	1.579	.054	5 th	1.241	.215
3. Socio-economic status						
4. Self Concept	-214	.199	.045	7 th	-1.076	.283
5. Personal Meaning of Life	.157	.059	.129	3 rd	2.643	.008*
6. Emotional Intelligence						.000*
7. Self Efficacy	.139	.035	.186	2 nd	3.942	
8. Locus of Control	3.188E-03	.049	.003	8 th	.065	.948
	.452	.164	.116	4 th	2.759	.006*
	2.002	.282	.291	1 st	7.090	.000*

* Significant at $p < .05$

Table 1 reveals that the beta (β) weights of the paths (path coefficients) give the estimates of the strengths of the causation. The entire psycho-demographic variables were found to contribute differentially to psychological well-being of the hearing-impaired adolescents. Specifically, locus of control made the greatest contribution, which is significant, to psychological well-being of the hearing-impaired adolescents ($\beta = .291$; $P < .05$). This variable is followed in magnitude of Beta weights by personal meaning of life ($\beta = .186$; $p < .05$) while self concept came third in the order of magnitude of contributions to the dependent measure ($\beta = .129$; $p < .05$). Both of these are also significant.

Next in the decreasing order of contributions made is self efficacy ($\beta = .116$; $p < .05$) which is also significant. Age ($\beta = .054$; $p > .05$) and gender ($\beta = .054$; $p > .05$) made contributions which are not significant. The lowest two contributions in terms of magnitude are those made by socio-economic status ($\beta = .045$; $p > .05$) and emotional intelligence ($\beta = .003$; $p > .05$). These are also non-significant contributions.

This order could be summarized as: Locus of Control > Personal Meaning of Life > Self Concept > Self Efficacy > Age=Gender > Socio-Economic Status > Emotional Intelligence.

Discussion

The research question stated what are the relative contributions of each of independent variables to the prediction of psychological well-being of the hearing-impaired adolescents in Southwest Nigeria?

To this end, locus of control, self-concept, meaning of life, self-efficacy made significant contributions to the subordinate variable. For example, the adolescent's internal control center, which can be changed, has made the highest contribution to the state of mental happiness of adolescents with hearing impairment. The result of this finding is a confirmation of previous studies; the fact that adolescents tend, with an internal control center, to take responsibility for their actions, absorb their problems, and deal with the challenges that may arise from various coping skills (Strickland 1965). In exercising control of their environment through their increased confidence (Phares, 1996). With this result again, it becomes clear that with the control center that registers such an important contribution in adolescents with visual impairment, there is scope for improving mental health among adolescents (Bakare, 2010).

Clearly, the meaning of life is the following in the contribution size of the dependent variable ($\beta = .86$; $p < .05$). It is clear that previous studies (Debker, Drost & Prartho, 1995; Shek, 1992, Rathi & Rastogi 2007; Recker, Peacock & Wong, 1987; Zika & Chamberlain, 1992) found a suitable place to support this outcome as life is definitively certain Mental. The harmony between the two is further enhanced because if a person feels his life to be meaningful, he will feel that he will become more psychologically effective than those who do not consider their lives meaningful. As well as the fact that a purposeful and purposeful life enhances the psychological well-being of people (Bakare, 2010).

In the case of important conceptual self-contributions, it is in line with previous studies that have demonstrated that the concept of self precedes psychological well-being (Fernandez, Castro, 2003, Bincourt and Sorensen, 2001; Rios & Godoy, 2007; Kim, 2003). Also, Bakare (2010) emphasizes that individuals who consider themselves self-sufficient, self-confident and in what they can do to overcome the challenges posed by life's obstacles, are likely to be in a state of improved mind and mental state. Finally, among the explanatory factors that contribute to predicting the perceived mental health of adolescents with hearing loss is self-efficacy, the fourth in size. This result is consistent with the results of Fleury, (2004; Flori and Buchanan, 2003) and Rural, (1989).

Age, however, in chronological order, was present at all before the deaf individual was aware of his perceived psychological well-being; a large contribution was made low. The contribution level cannot be ignored to the child variable. Thus, these results disturb previous studies (Flouri & Buchanan, 2003; Thomas & Hughes, 1986; Diener, Suh, Lucas & Smith, 1999; Isaacowitz and Smith, 1999; Nolen-Hoeksema, 2001) Between age and psychological comfort. So, the result corresponds to the maximum of the fool in forty is a fool forever. Also, this reinforces the fact that chronological age differs from mental performance.

Gender equality and age make a significant contribution to perceived psychological well-being. This finding invalidates previous findings (Mcleod & Owens, 2004; Seo, 2007; Woody & Green, 2001), which showed a positive relationship between gender and psychological well-being. Moreover, this unrelated outcome between the two coincides with studies on sex and psychological well-being which have shown mixed results. For example, Amy (1979) shows that girls have better psychological / behavioral disposition than boys; Mookherjee (1997) found that women reported higher levels of life satisfaction than men. Studies using NSFH data also showed that adolescent girls showed fewer external problems and independence than boys in families with two families. On the other hand, there is evidence that girls face more psychological problems than boys. The number of teenage girls reporting depression is higher than that of boys and they carry risk factors for depression, says Noelen-Hoxma (1994).

The lowest two contributions in terms of magnitude are those made by socio-economic status and emotional intelligence The low contribution of socio-economic status to the dependent

variable contradicts earlier studies (Marmot & Wilkinson, 2006; Mcleod & Owens, 2004; Adler & Ostrove, 1999) which initially, lent support to harmonious relationship between socio-economic status and psychological well-being. Also, emotional intelligence, a psychological construct, made the least contribution to the dependent variable. Thus, studies by Bellamy, Gore and Sturgis, (2008) and Murphy, (2006) are inconclusive on the role of emotional intelligence on perceived psychological well-being.

Conclusion and Recommendations

All the psychological and demographic variables were found to contribute differently to the perceived psychological perception of hearing-impaired adolescents. Some variables are more important than others in determining adolescent mental health in southwestern Nigeria. For example, locust control is the most important factor. In particular, emotional intelligence has formed the least contribution towards the mental health of hearing-impaired adolescents.

Adolescents with hearing impairment should give serious attention to all psychological demographics, most importantly factors that have significant and significant effects on their mental health. Intervention programs can be designed through counseling, government, policy makers, social workers and private educators on the above factors to promote the psychological well-being of hearing-impaired adolescents in southwestern Nigeria. For example, control locusts, the most important factor that not only has the greatest predictability of adolescent psychological well-being, should also be given the highest impact on its improvement and support. Finally, to help promote the psychological well-being of adolescents, they need to imbibe good locus of control, self-concept, meaning of life and self-efficacy.

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Impact of study habits and emotional intelligence on academic performance of secondary school students in Akoko South-west of Ondo state, Nigeria

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Abstract

One of the problems attracting public outcry in Nigeria today is the academic performance of secondary school students which on the long run determines their academic achievements. This study examined the impact of study habits and emotional intelligence on academic performance of secondary school students. Six hypotheses guided this study. A descriptive research design of survey type was employed for this study. The population comprised all senior secondary school students in Akoko South-West, Ondo State, while the sample consisted of 200 students randomly selected from four secondary schools. Data collected were analyzed using inferential statistics and the hypotheses were tested using t-test at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that study habits significantly influenced academic performance of secondary school students and that emotional intelligence significantly influenced academic performance of secondary school students. It was recommended that teachers and school counsellors should ensure that emotional intelligence of the students is enhanced through appropriate techniques.

Keywords: Study Habits, Emotional Intelligence, Academic Performance, Secondary school students

Introduction

In recent times, there seems to be tremendous pressure on secondary school students to earn good grades in their final examinations. Academic performance at this level is assumed to possess predictive value and it is used as the basis for securing admission to the higher institutions in Nigeria (Sharma, 2005). Parents desire that their children perform very well by the end of their secondary school education. This desire puts a lot of pressure on students, teachers, schools and the entire education system in general to ensure good academic performance of students. Parents' desire of good academic performance for their children seems to be one of the major factors responsible for the migration of many students from public to private secondary schools.

The trend in the academic performance of secondary school students in Nigeria in the last two decades has become a major source of concern to all stakeholders in the education sector.

This is so because of the great importance attached to education as the basis for national development. According to Ayeni (2018), the trends in students' academic performance in the year 2011 to 2016 in Nigeria showed the following percentage points: 30.99% (2011), 38.81% (2012), 36.57% (2013), 31.28% (2014), 38.68% (2015) and 52.97 percent in 2016. The levels of performances reported above revealed the percentage of students who obtained credit level passes in five subjects and above, including English Language and Mathematics in the Senior School Certificate Examinations conducted by the West African Examinations Council, was below 53 percent (Owadiae, 2011; Owadiae, 2012; Eguridu, 2014; Eguridu, 2015; Adenipekun, 2016).

Academic failure is not only frustrating to the students and the parents, its effects are equally grave on the society. Several factors have generally been identified as causes of poor academic performance. In a research carried out by Nuthana and Yenagi (2009), the causes of poor academic performance among Nigeria students were thoroughly examined. Some of these factors identified include; low students' intellectual ability, achievement motivation, lack of goals, low self-esteem, low socio-economic status of the family, poverty and so on. Other factors include; state of health, anxiety and state of mind, conducive and suitable environment for studying, availability of textbooks and well equipped libraries. In recent time, it has been realized that students who possess adequate mental abilities sometimes do not perform well in their academic work. This is a clear indication that there are other factors influencing academic performance apart from the mental abilities. Therefore, this study explored such factors as study habits and emotional intelligence on students' academic performance.

Study habits are learning tendencies that enable students to work privately. Azikiwe (1998) described the study habits as the adopted way and manner a student plans his private readings, after classroom learning so as to attain mastery of the subject. Aquino (2011) defined the term study habits as students' way of study whether systematic, efficient or inefficient and so on. Going by this definition it literally means that good study habits produces positive academic performance while inefficient study habits leads to academic failure.

Adeniyi (2011) maintained that good study habits allow students to study independently at home and aspire for higher educational career. Effective study habits include demonstrating high motivation, avoiding distraction, right learning styles with concentration, interest, ability to remember facts studied, and time management. According to Nneji (2002), study habits are those learning tendencies that enable students to work privately. Thus, study habits are a well-planned and deliberate pattern of study which has attained a form of consistency on the part of the students toward understanding academic subjects and passing in examination.

The general belief is that students who exercise good study habits are likely to excel than those with poor study habits. According to Okegbile (2007), academic achievement is a pedagogical terminology used while determining learner's success in formal education. Some researchers (Ayodele & Adebisi, 2013a; Ogoemeka, 2013; Thomas, Omotoke & Ademola, 2016) found poor study habits as one of the major factors responsible for poor academic performance among Nigerian students. Other Researchers (Ogunmakin, 2001; Kumar, 2002; Gbore, 2006; Oluwatimilehin & Owoyele, 2012; Ayodele & Adebisi, 2013b; Sanchez, 2016) agreed that good study habits have positive effects on performance. Mark and Howard (2009) are of the opinion that the most common challenge to the success of students in all ramifications is a lack of effective or positive (good) study habits. They further maintain that if students can develop a good study habits and with good discipline, they are bound to perform very well in their academic pursuit.

Onwuegbuzie (2001) conducted a study to find out the relationship between academic success and study habits. The study reported positive relationship between the two variables (academic success and study habits). In like manner, Omotere (2011) conducted a study to ascertain the relationship between study habits and the academic performance of the students. Findings of the study revealed a positive correlation between study habits and academic achievement. The relationship that existed between study habits and academic performance shows that if a student develops good study habits, his/her academic performance would be enhanced. Nevertheless, and in spite of the studies reviewed, there is still a need to further investigate the relationship of study habits with academic performance. Studies indicating a close connection between study habits and academic performance in Ondo State are few.

Another variable of interest is emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence is the ability to monitor one's feelings and that of others, to discriminate among them and to use this information to guide one's feeling and thinking (Salovey & Mayer, 1990). Emotional safety is important at each stage of development. These same skills and competencies are critical to achieving academic and career excellence in life. The development of emotional intelligence is an intentional, active and engaging process (Salovey & Mayer 1990).

Research in the area of academic success has shown that students with higher emotional intelligence scores also tend to be more successful academically (Parker, Creque, Barnhart, Harris et al., 2004; Vela, 2004; Walker, 2006). Oyinloye (2005) attributes the problem of poor academic performance to low level of emotional intelligence among secondary school students. He believes that students who lack emotional intelligence show some adjustive challenges or in some ways fail to handle effectively the demands of school work. Cherniss (2004) stated the importance of emotional intelligence as necessary to improving performance and psychological well-being in school work. If emotional intelligence skills are developed, strengthened and enhanced, students may demonstrate increased levels of personal, academic and career achievement (Vela, 2004). Emotional intelligence as determined by Nelson and Low (2005) has four major skills dimensions of emotional competencies namely-interpersonal skills, leadership skills, self-management skills and intrapersonal skills.

It is clear from the literature that emotional intelligence is an important psychological factor that has a profound effect on abilities and performances. There are a number of studies that demonstrated the predictive effects of emotional intelligence on academic achievement. However, by contrast, some studies have provided evidence of limited or no relationship between students' emotional intelligence and academic performance. Koifman (1998) and Zee, Thijs, and Schakel (2002) found no relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement. No significant relationship was found between emotional intelligence and academic performance of high school students by Azimifar (2013) and Lawrence and Deepa (2013). Yahaya, Hashim and Nor (2009) found no significant relationship emotional intelligence and academic performance. Adil, Amjad, Muhammad, (2012) also reported no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic performance.

It is evident from studies that mixed results were found by researchers on the influence of emotional intelligence on academic performance. Hence, more research in this area is needed to fortify the existing ones on the relationship between emotional intelligence and academic performance. In addition, previous research on emotional intelligence revealed that emotional intelligence resulted in certain work related outcomes. However, there has been limited research which clearly and succinctly proves that emotional intelligence is directly linked to positive work related outcomes, particularly in educational sector. Hence, this study examined the impact of study habits and emotional intelligence on academic performance of secondary school students.

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were generated for this study:

1. Study habits do not significantly influence academic performance of secondary school students.
2. Study habits do not significantly influence academic performance of male secondary school students.
3. Study habits do not significantly influence academic performance of female secondary school students.
4. Emotional intelligence does not significantly influence academic performance of secondary school students.
5. Emotional intelligence does not significantly influence academic performance of male secondary school students.
6. Emotional intelligence does not significantly influence academic performance of female secondary school students.

Methods

Design and Population

The study investigated the impact of study habits and emotional intelligence on the academic performance of secondary school students in Akoko South-West of Ondo State, Nigeria. This study adopted descriptive research design of survey type. The target population comprised students in public secondary schools in Akoko South-West of Ondo State, Nigeria. Stratified random sampling technique was used to select two hundred (200) secondary school three (SSS 3) students [Male = 83 (41.5%); Female = 117 (58.5%)] that participated in the study. The mean age of the sample was 15.44 years (SD = 2.86).

Measures

The "Study Habits Inventory" (SHI) developed by Bakare (1977), "Emotional Intelligence Scale" (SMQ) developed by Law, Wong and Song (2004) and "Students' Academic Performance Proforma" (SAPP) were used to collect data. The Study Habits Inventory by Bakare (1977) is made up of 45 items that covers eight (8) areas of study namely; homework and assignment, time allocation, reading and note-taking, study period procedures, concentration, written work, examinations, and teacher consultation. The responses to each item are graded on a five-point rating scale. The possible responses to each item on the questionnaire are five (almost never, less than half of the time, about half of the time, more than half of the time, and almost always) with scores 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5, respectively, for a positive question and the scores reversed for a negative question. The scale was chosen for use in this study because of its high reliability estimate and it was also validated on Nigerian subjects. The internal reliability coefficient for the Study Habit Inventory was 0.76 in the current study

Emotional Intelligence Scale developed by Law, Wong and Song (2004) was used to measure the emotional intelligence levels of the respondents. It is a popular self-report measure of emotional intelligence. It is a 16 item scale with 4 sections viz.: SEA (self-emotional appraisal, 4 items), OEA (other emotional appraisal, 4 items), UOE (use of emotions, 4 items), and ROE (regulation of emotion, 4 items). The scale adopted a 5-point scale ranging from "1=strongly disagree" to "5 = strongly agree" for this study. The Cronbach's alpha of the 4 subscales ranged from 0.83 to 0.90. The validity of the scale has been reported by Law, Wong and Song (2004). The internal reliability coefficient for Wong and Long Emotional Intelligence Scale was 0.87 in the current study.

"Students' Academic Performance Proforma" (SAPP) designed and validated by the researchers was used to collect the available records of the students' performance from the

official students’ records in their respective schools. The average scores participants’ English Language and Mathematics in the Joint Senior Secondary School Two Promotion Examination (JSSSTPE) were used to determine their academic performance.

Two trained research assistants helped the researcher in the administration of instruments. Data collected were analysed using student t-test at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Hypothesis 1: Study habits do not significantly influence academic performance of secondary school students.

The results obtained from the data analysis regarding study habits are presented in Table 1 below.

Table I: t-test Summary of the Influence of Study Habits on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students.

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	t.cal	t-cri	P
Poor Study Habits	98	45.29	10.614	198	8.31	1.96	Sig
Good Study Habits	102	57.95	10.920				

*significant at $p < 0.05$

As revealed in Table I, the influence of study habits on academic performance of students was found to be significant (Poor and Good Study Habits, $N_1 = 98$, $N_2 = 102$, $\bar{X}_1 = 45.29$, $\bar{X}_2 = 57.95$, $df = 198$, $t = 8.31$, $p < 0.05$). The hypothesis was rejected because a significant difference in academic performance of students with poor study habits and their counterpart with good habits was established.

Hypothesis 2: Study habits do not significantly influence academic performance of male secondary school students.

Table II: t-test Summary of the Influence of Study Habits on Academic Performance of Male Secondary School Students.

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t.cal	t-cri	P
Poor Study Habits	42	44.40	9.329	81	6.01	1.99	Sig
Good Study Habits	41	58.32	11.661				

*significant at $p < 0.05$

Table II shows the influence of study habits on academic performance of male secondary school students. Study habits were found to be significant (Poor and Good Study Habits, $N_1 = 42$, $N_2 = 41$, $\bar{X}_1 = 44.40$, $\bar{X}_2 = 58.32$, $df = 81$, $t = 6.01$, $p < 0.05$). Thus, the hypothesis which states that study habits do not significantly influence academic performance of male secondary school students was rejected.

Hypothesis 3: Study habits do not significantly influence academic performance of female secondary school students.

Table II: t-test Summary of the Influence of Study Habits on Academic Performance of Female Secondary School Students

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t.cal	t-cri	P
Poor Study Habits	56	45.45	11.523	115	5.78	1.98	Sig
Good Study Habits	61	57.70	10.485				

*significant at $p < 0.05$

Table III shows the influence of study habits on academic performance of female secondary school students. Study habits were found to be significant (Poor and Good Study Habits, $N_1 = 56$, $N_2 = 61$, $\bar{X}_1 = 45.45$, $\bar{X}_2 = 57.70$, $df = 115$, $t = 5.78$, $p < 0.05$). Thus, the hypothesis which states that study habits do not significantly influence academic performance of female secondary school students was rejected.

Hypothesis 4: Emotional intelligence does not significantly influence academic performance of secondary school students.

Table IV: t-test Summary of the Influence of Emotional Intelligence on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students.

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	t.cal	t-cri	P
Low Emotional Intelligence	93	41.10	7.397	198	18.60	1.99	Sig
High Emotional Intelligence	107	61.00	7.676				

*significant at $p < 0.05$

As revealed in Table IV, the influence of emotional intelligence on academic performance of students was found to be significant (Low and High Emotional Intelligence, $N_1 = 93$, $N_2 = 107$, $\bar{X}_1 = 41.10$, $\bar{X}_2 = 61.00$, $df = 198$, $t = 18.60$, $p < 0.05$). The hypothesis was rejected because a significant difference in the emotional intelligence of secondary school students on academic performance was established.

Hypothesis 5: Emotional Intelligence does not significantly influence academic performance of male secondary school students.

Table V: t-test Summary of the Influence of Emotional Intelligence on Academic Performance of Male Secondary School Students.

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t.cal	t-cri	P
Low Emotional Intelligence.	39	40.95	7.022	81	11.084	1.99	Sig
High Emotional Intelligence.	44	60.43	8.761				

*significant at $p < 0.05$

Table V shows the influence of emotional intelligence on academic performance of male secondary school students. Emotional intelligence were found to be significant (Low and High Emotional Intelligence, $N_1 = 39$, $N_2 = 44$, $\bar{X}_1 = 40.95$, $\bar{X}_2 = 60.43$, $df = 81$, $t = 11.084$, $p < 0.05$). Thus, the hypothesis which states that emotional intelligence does not significantly influence academic performance of male secondary school students was rejected.

Hypothesis 6: Emotional intelligence does not significantly influence academic performance of female secondary school students.

Table VI: t-test Summary of the Influence of Emotional Intelligence on Academic Performance of Female Secondary School Students.

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t.cal	t.cri	P
Low Emotional Intelligence	54	41.20	7.720	115	14.975	1.99	Sig
High Emotional Intelligence	63	61.40	6.864				

*significant at $p < 0.05$

Table VI shows the influence of emotional intelligence on academic performance of female secondary school students. Emotional intelligence were found to be significant (Low and High Emotional Intelligence, $N_1 = 54$, $N_2 = 63$, $\bar{X}_1 = 41.20$, $\bar{X}_2 = 61.40$, $df = 115$, $t = 14.975$, $p < 0.05$). Thus, the hypothesis which states that emotional intelligence does not significantly influence academic performance of female secondary school students was rejected.

Discussion of the Findings

This study carefully looked into the impact of study habits and emotional intelligence on the academic performance of secondary schools students. The findings based on the tested hypotheses revealed the significant influences of study habits on academic performance of secondary school students irrespective of their gender. This has again strengthened previous findings on the influence study habits on academic performance. The results of this study corroborated the finding of Onwuegbuzie (2001) who conducted a study on the relationship between academic success and study habits and found a significant positive relationship between the two variables (study habits and academic performance). In like manner, Omotere (2011) conducted a study to ascertain the relationship between study habits and the academic performance of the students and found a significant positive correlation between study habits and academic achievement. In addition, the outcome of this study agreed with Ramaswamy (1990) who found a significant relationship between study habits and academic achievement in high and low achieving boys and girls of 11th standard in Madurai district, Tamil Nadu, India.

The significant influence of study habits on academic performance of secondary students found in this study agreed with other previous research outcomes (Ogunmakin, 2001; Onwuegbuzie, 2001; Kumar, 2002; Adeyemo, 2005; Gbore, 2006; Omotere, 2011; Oluwatimilehin & Owoyele, 2012; Ayodele & Adebisi, 2013; Ogoemeka, 2013; Thomas, Omotoke & Ademola, 2016) Sanchez, 2016). This finding is not surprising because students with good study habits are well organized, know teachers and parents expectations, designate a study area, develop a study plan, think positively, create a study group, practice active listening, review test-taking strategies, read actively, look to the future. All these qualities would enhance academic performance of students with good study habits better than their counterparts with poor study habits.

The finding of this study also agreed with Haddadi (2004) that found a significant influence of emotional intelligence on academic performance of male and female secondary school students. The result of this study agreed with the findings of Jenaabadi, Shahidi, Elhamifar and Khademi (2015) that revealed a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of students at the 95 percent significance level. The finding is in consonance with the results of Rahnama and Abulmaleki (2009) and Samari and

Tahmasbi (2007) that established a significant influence of emotional intelligence on academic performance.

The significant influence of emotional intelligence on academic performance as revealed in this study showed that emotional intelligence plays important role in the academic success of secondary school students. This outcome is not surprising because emotional intelligence is crucial to a student's personal health and college success (Low & Nelson, 2006). Students with emotional intelligence skills are better able to cope with demanding and complex secondary school experience. When individuals are able to lead their life successfully in the school environment, they would focus on their learning and perform very well in their studies. In addition, emotionally intelligent students have better interpersonal and intrapersonal skills than their counterparts with low emotional intelligence. They are more adaptable and perform better in managing stress.

Conclusion

It is evident from this study that study habits was a major factor influencing academic performance of secondary school students irrespective of their gender. Students that maintained good study habits significantly performed better than their counterparts with poor study habits. In addition, emotional intelligence level of a secondary school student is another important variable influencing academic performance. The academic performance of students with high emotional intelligence was significantly better than their colleagues with low emotional intelligence. Hence, both study habits and emotional intelligence were strong indicators of academic performance of students in secondary school.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. The school counsellors should use appropriate therapeutic interventions such as group and individual counselling in helping students to develop and maintain good study habits.
- ii. Parents, teachers and school administrators should create conducive environment for students to study very well at home and in school.
- iii. School counsellor should interact with parents and guardians on the role they should play in helping the students to develop good study habits.
- iv. The Federal Ministry of Education should implement orientation services in schools on the impact of good study habits and emotional intelligence on students' over all development and academic performance.
- v. Counselling psychologists should also use appropriate counselling interventions to enhance the emotional intelligence of the students.

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Nexus of mindfulness and counsellor self-efficacy of pre-service counsellors in a south-west tertiary institution, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the correlates between mindfulness and counseling self-efficacy among the pre-service counselors. The study used a total sample of 200 final year students in the Department of Educational Foundations and Counseling Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo, Nigeria. Two standardized and validated scales were used for the collection of data (mindfulness scale, $r = 0.71$; counsellor activity self-efficacy scale, $r = 0.72$). Three null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

The findings indicate that a significant correlation was found between mindfulness and counseling self-efficacy of the participants, significant difference also exists in the levels of mindfulness and counseling self-efficacy of the participants, with high mindfulness performing better than the moderate and the low mindfulness individuals. Results further reveals the participants mindfulness was the same irrespective of their gender. Implications of mindfulness on counseling self-efficacy of students at all levels generally and some effective ways of promoting of mindfulness were suggested.

Keyword: Mindfulness, Counselling self-efficacy, Pre-service counsellors

Introduction

Counsellor self-efficacy is a crucial factor for pre-service counsellors to be well prepared upon entering the profession to work effectively with clients and providing good quality services. Counsellor self-efficacy has been the focus of many researches in the past couple of decades. It is defined as one's beliefs or judgments about his or her capabilities to effectively counsel a client in the near future (Larson & Daniels, 1998). The concept describes the degree to which a counsellor considers self as capable of counselling activities. Studies have demonstrated a high correlation among counsellor self-efficacy, positive counsellor and client outcomes (Larson & Daniels, 1998). Researchers have found that counsellor self-efficacy is positively related to counsellor training level and experience (Bischoff, Barton, Thober, & Hawley, 2002; Tang, Addison, LaSure-Bryant, Norman, O'Connell & Stewart-Sicking, 2004). It has also been shown to be associated with counsellor development (Leach, et al., 1997), and expectations of counselling outcomes (Sipps, Sugden, & Faiver, 1988). Hence, counselling self-efficacy is a major factor to be considered in training of counsellors.

Unfortunately, counsellor self-efficacy of pre-service counsellors is greatly hindered by several factors with their attendant grave consequences to the society. For instance, in the training of counsellors, researchers have found that current counsellor education methods are effective in teaching discrete behavioural skills such as reflection of feelings and attending

behaviour (Hill & Lent, 2006). However, less is known about the development of internal (such as cognitive) counselling skills. Literature (such as, Bentley, 2007; Al-Darmaki, 2004) suggests that there is little guidance in counsellor education on how to prepare students in the habits of mind and ways of being, such as attention control and empathic understanding. At this point, self or personal development is required from every counsellor trainee as not all skills particularly cognitive skills can be learnt in the classroom or laboratories. It appears that a conceptualization of how these essential skills develop is less clear and, as of yet, less researched. The role of mindfulness for this development is less known, accepted or researched.

In the last two decades, mindfulness has become the focus of considerable attention by a large community of clinicians and to a less extent, empirical psychology. Mindfulness has been described as a process of bringing a certain quality of attention to moment-by-moment experience (Kabat-Zinn, 1990). Practices designed to cultivate this type of awareness have been used for thousands of years to help train the mind to stay non-judgmentally focused on the present moment and to increase compassion (Germer, 2005; Kabat-Zinn, 1990, 1994, 2003; Olendzki, 2005). According to Silananda (1990), mindfulness in Buddhist tradition occupies a central role in a system that was developed as a path leading to the cessation of personal suffering. Mindfulness in contemporary psychology has been adapted as an approach to increasing awareness and skilful responding to mental processes that contributes to emotional distress and maladaptive behaviour.

Researchers and clinicians have applied the techniques of mindfulness to the treatment of such physical and mental health issues as fostering tobacco cessation (Asuzu, & Agokei, 2012), depressive relapse (Ma & Teasdale, 2004) and generalized anxiety disorder (Semple, Reid, & Miller, 2005) with significant results. In addition to client training in mindfulness, a number of scholars have suggested that counsellor mindfulness may be an essential ingredient of clinical practice that cuts across all theoretical orientations and that mindfulness training and practice may be an untapped resource for developing core counselling skills as well as the person of the counsellor (Fulton, 2005; Morgan & Morgan; 2005; Walsh & Shapiro, 2006).

Further, mindfulness practices provide opportunities to gain insight into the nature of thoughts and feelings as passing events in the mind rather than inherent aspects of the self or valid reflections on reality (Segal, Williams & Teasdale, 2002). Mindfulness is considered a capacity available to everyone, although individuals differ in their propensity or willingness to be mindful (Brown & Ryan, 2003; Kabat-Zinn, 2003). Both conceptual and empirical literature suggest that mindfulness practice helps to increase attentive presence, acceptance, empathy, and self-awareness, as well as reduce stress (Baer, 2003; Bishop et al., 2004; Brown & Ryan, 2004; Fulton, 2005; Shapiro, Astin, Bishop & Cardova, 2005; Valente & Marotta, 2005).

Empirical research suggests that mindfulness-based interventions hold promise for a variety of outcome objectives, including counsellor training (Adeyemo & Agokei, 2011). These findings suggest that mindfulness may be an important tool for cultivating attentional competencies, which are relevant in counselling. Mindfulness practices may help counsellors attend completely even when the session feels tedious or boring. Furthermore, because counsellors need to pay attention to both internal and external stimuli, broad awareness techniques such as mindfulness may be more helpful in cultivating this attentional capacity than strict concentrative practices.

Although current mindfulness research suggests some links between mindfulness and key counsellor-training outcomes (Shapiro et al, 2005), there is little research specifically on counsellor mindfulness. In a state of mindfulness, the emphasis is simply on noticing either internal or external experience without making judgments, reacting in habitual ways to the

stimulus, or elaborating on the meaning of the event (Bishop et al., 2004). As these are all skills that are considered fundamental for effective counselling (Orlinsky, Grawe & Parks, 1994), the use of mindfulness training in counsellor education holds promise as an important tool for facilitating the development of potentially increasing counselling self-efficacy.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study is to find out the correlation between mindfulness and counsellor self efficacy; and in addition examine whether gender difference exist in mindfulness among counsellors in a population of Nigerian pre-service counsellors.

hypotheses

To achieve the purpose of this study the following hypothesis were generated;

1. There will be no significant correlation between mindfulness and counsellor self efficacy.
2. There will be no significant difference in the counsellor self efficacy of the participants based on their level of mindfulness (low, moderate and high).
3. There will be no gender difference in the mindfulness of the participants.

Method

The study adopted a [AO1]descriptive research design approach. This does not involve the manipulation of any variables.

Population

The population for this study was all counselling students in Adeyemi College of Education who were in their final year and those who have completed the mandatory six weeks counselling practicum exercises. This population was 282 counsellor trainees who are currently registered students in the Department of Educational Foundations and Counselling in the School.

Sample and sampling technique

The sample for this study was randomly 200 randomly selected final year counselling students in Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo State. The participants were consisting of 73 males and 127 females. The participants' age ranged from 21-30 years with mean age of 25.5.

Instrumentation

Two validated and standardized scales were used in this study. Below is their description.

The Counsellor Activity Self-Efficacy Scale (CASES): The scale is a 41 item self-report measure of counselling self-efficacy developed by Lent et al. (2003). It consists of with a 10-point scale in which respondents rate their confidence from 0 (no confidence at all) to 9 (complete competence). The CASES has been reported to have a high reliability with a Cronbach alpha of 0.97 (Lent et al., 2003). A pilot test with pre-service counsellors from a university other than those in this study produced a scale alpha of 0.72.

Mindfulness scale: The measure was the 20 item Mindfulness scale by Baer, Smith, Hopkins, Krietemeyer, and Toney, (2006). Typical examples of the items are: "I make judgments about whether my thoughts are good or bad", "I criticize myself for having irrational or inappropriate emotions". It has a reliability coefficient of 0.7 using Cronbach-alpha method. The scale demonstrated at 0.71 two-week test re-test reliability coefficient for this study

Procedure

The researcher personally distributed and collected the completed questionnaire from the participants. Permissions were obtained from significant authorities to facilitate the process.

Participation in this study was strictly voluntary, and no incentives were offered. Participants were adequately informed of confidentiality and the need to be precise and truthful in filling the questionnaire. The questionnaires were then filled and returned by the participants after adequate understanding.

Method of Data Analysis

Data was analyzed, using Pearson Product Moment Correlation to determine the relationship among the variables investigated. Analysis of variance, multiple comparison and t-test statistical tools were also used.

Results

The results of the analysis are presented as follows:

Hypothesis 1: There will be no significant correlation between mindfulness and counseling self-efficacy

Table 1. Correlation between mindfulness and counseling self-efficacy

Variables	N	X	SD	R	p
Mindfulness	200	52.1	11.4		
Counseling self-efficacy	200	177.8	10.6	0.71	<0.05

Table 1 above shows that there is significant positive correlation between mindfulness and counseling self-efficacy with $r = 0.71$. This implies that the more the mindfulness with the participants procrastinate the more their counseling self-efficacy.

Hypothesis 2: There will be no significant difference in the counseling self-efficacy of the subjects based on their level of mindfulness (Low, Moderate and High).

Table 2. Level of Mindfulness and Counseling self-efficacy.

Source of variance	Sum of squares	df	Mean squares	F	P
Between Groups	409.42	2	204.71		
Within Groups	1498.62	197	7.61	26.91	<0.05
Total		199			

Table 2 above shows that there is a significant difference in the level of mindfulness and counseling self-efficacy of the participants with $F_{obs} = 26.91$ at $P < 0.05$ with 2 degree of freedom. To identify the mindfulness group that has a better counseling self-efficacy over the other, t-test analysis was carried out in pairs. The result is shown in table 3. From table 3 below high mindfulness had a mean counseling self-efficacy of 174.61 and a standard deviation of 8.47 while moderate mindfulness had a mean of counseling self-efficacy of 172.67 and a standard deviation of 9.34. The difference between the mean values of the two groups (1.94) is statistically significant at 0.05 levels. This indicates that a significant difference exists between the counseling self-efficacy of high and moderate mindfulness with high mindfulness performing better than the moderate mindfulness. Furthermore, data on the counseling self-efficacy of high mindfulness ($x = 174.61$, $SD = 8.47$) were compared with those of low mindfulness ($x = 172.53$, $SD = 8.11$). This analysis showed a mean difference of 2.08, which is significant at 0.05 levels. This

indicates that the counseling self-efficacy of high mindfulness as measured by their counseling self-efficacy were better than those of low mindfulness ($P < .05$). On the other hand, another comparison of the mean counseling self-efficacy of moderate mindfulness ($X = 172.67$, $SD = 9.34$) and low mindfulness ($X = 172.53$, $SD = 8.11$) showed a mean difference of 0.14 which is not significant at 0.05 level. This perhaps suggests that the counseling self-efficacy of moderate and low mindfulness is not different despite that the moderate mindfulness recorded a higher counseling self-efficacy than the low mindfulness.

Table 3. Multiple comparison of counseling self-efficacy of participants and their levels of mindfulness.

LEVEL OF MINDFULNESS	NO	X	SD	Mean difference	Std. error	P
Low Mindfulness	81	172.53	8.11	0.14	0.142	<0.05
Moderate Mindfulness	72	172.67	9.34			
Low Mindfulness	81	172.53	8.11	2.08	0.278	<0.05
High Mindfulness	57	174.61	8.47			
Moderate Mindfulness	72	172.67	9.34	1.94	.111	<0.05
High Mindfulness	57	174.61	8.47			

Hypothesis 3: There will be no significant gender difference in the academic procrastination of the participants.

Table 4. Gender difference and Mindfulness.

Variables	No	X	SD	df	t.obs	t. crit	P
Male	73	50.5	8.74	198	1.332	1.96	<0.05
Female	173	52.22	9.48				

From the result in table 4, it shows that the hypothesis of no gender difference existing in mindfulness between male and female is accepted. This is because the calculated t, (t.obs) 1.33 is lesser than the t critical, (t.crit) 1.98. This implies that both male and participants exhibit the same level of mindfulness with its attending influence accordingly.

Discussion

The result of this study provides significant insight to the relationship between mindfulness and counseling self-efficacy. The first hypothesis tested that there is no significant correlation between mindfulness and counseling self efficacy was not supported. In other words, the result indicated that there is a significant correlation between counseling self efficacy and mindfulness. The result of this study in congruence with prior studies (Adeyemo & Agokei, 2010, 2011; Bentley, 2007) that found mindfulness technique to be fostering counsellor self-efficacy. Adeyemo and Agokei (2011) noted that this effectiveness of mindfulness in fostering counsellor self efficacy could be traced to direct outcome of the internal behaviours of intentionally and non-judgmentally attending to the present moment. This meta-mechanism overarches other

hypothesized mechanisms of change, including exposure, self-regulation and self-management, values clarification, relaxation, and acceptance (Baer, 2003; Shapiro et al., 2006).

The result of the study also indicated a significant difference between mindfulness and counseling self efficacy, with student with high mindfulness having a higher counseling self-efficacy than participants with moderate and low levels of mindfulness. This has a very significant implication for the quality and number of students that will be available for counseling studies. This result is easily explainable bearing in mind that conceptual and empirical literature suggest that mindfulness practice helps to increase attentive presence, acceptance, empathy, and self-awareness, as well as reduce stress. In a state of mindfulness, the emphasis is simply on noticing either internal or external experience without making judgments, reacting in habitual ways to the stimulus, or elaborating on the meaning of the event (Bishop et al., 2004). At this point, insight into the nature of thoughts and feelings as passing events in the mind rather than inherent aspects of the self or valid reflections on reality are gained. An adequate, relaxing and potentially successful approach to client's challenge is developed for the counsellor. Questioning, probing, reflecting, counter-transference, para-phrasing are easily and readily made by the counsellor in synchrony with the client's challenge. As these are all skills that are considered fundamental for effective counselling (Orlinsky et al., 1994), little wonder that with high mindfulness levels a potentially increased counsellor self-efficacy among pre-service counsellors is gained.

The hypothesis that gender would have an effect on mindfulness was not supported by the result. The result indicated that mindfulness is independent of gender. This means that both male and female exhibit mindfulness in like manners. It is pertinent to note that gender exerts considerable influence over motives to teach including counseling considering it is an educational centeredness and focus. Females are encouraged into the counseling profession because it is regarded as undemanding, feminine and compatible with domesticity. The daily work schedules appear convenient, and the holidays are long, allowing more time with their children. Hence, most women become counsellors because of a sense of job compatibility, less work demand seems much easier a schedule. However, mindfulness as shown in the result above has no significant compatibility with being male or female as it is a phenomenon that transcends counseling. Mindfulness is noted to be the gap between perceiving and responding appropriately, a trait requisite for accurate empathy. The ability to attend to and experience the client on a deeper level would improve as this basic task becomes automatic. Therefore, the combination of being able to non-judgmentally and be purposively attentive which is not peculiar to being male or female offer plausible explanation for the finding.

Conclusion

A review of the literature reveals that in counsellor education, insufficient attention has been paid to cultivate the internal "habits of mind" and cognitive skills necessary for sustainable counsellor efficacy. In view of this, counsellor education programmes leave much cognitive skill development to chance with gave consequence resulting in production of ill-equipped counsellors with poor self-image, incompetence, hostile environment where clients feel unsafe, unwelcome, unaided, misguided and potentials untapped. This study investigated the correlates of mindfulness and counselling self efficacy of pre-service counsellors. Counsellor self-efficacy has been the focus of many researches in the past couple of decades. Being efficacious to a large extent describes the typified performance of the counsellor. In other words, counselling self-efficacy emphasizes mastery and performance competence with clinical finishing accruing from the belief of efficaciousness. Despite the numerous factors that impede the positive development

of counselling self-efficacy, this study has shown that with increasing levels of mindfulness, counselling self-efficacy among pre-service counsellors can be increased.

Mindfulness fosters the mental space necessary to reflect on values more objectively. Mindfulness practice is a systematic mental training in noticing when attention has strayed from the present moment, sustaining attention on all aspects of the here-and-now, and quietening the mental noise of subjective analysis, elaboration, or negative self-talk. This is further emphasized in the counselling relationship which tests the ability of the counsellor to actively and non-judgmentally attend to a client. When counseling students engage in mindfulness periodically especially with their day to day activities, observing and modifying their use of being mindful, counselling self-efficacy may be increased to the maximum for optimum functioning in counselling. Therefore, mindfulness holds a significant benefit in counsellor education and should be promoted.

Recommendations

In order to enhance the counselling self-efficacy of pre-service counsellors, the following recommendations are made, that, significant stakeholders should utilize for effectiveness and efficiency.

1. Mindfulness and counselling self-efficacy should be evaluated at all levels of university development to ensure, encourage and foster its development among counsellor trainees.
2. Mindfulness should be synergize into the curricula advancement of counsellor trainees in the universities
3. A package integrating mindfulness interventions should be developed for fostering counsellor efficacy among trainees.
4. Pre-service counsellors should be encouraged to become more mindful in their everyday activities in other to provide the opportunity of personal and cognitive development in counsellor efficaciousness.
5. Academic values and practices that encourage the development of emotional intelligence, counsellor self-efficacy and effectiveness should be encouraged.

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Schema therapy and life-skills training in enhancing identity formation of in-school adolescents in Ilorin, Kwara state, nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the effects of Schema Therapy (ST) and Life-skills Training (LST) in enhancing identity formation among in-school adolescents. The moderating effect of gender and self-efficacy were also examined. One hundred and fifty-seven SS2 students (males = 97, females = 60) were randomly selected from three secondary schools in Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria. A 3x2x3 factorial pretest-posttest experimental control group design was adopted for the study. There were two experimental groups and a control group. Analysis of Covariance and Scheffe post-hoc test were used for data analysis. The result showed a significant main effect of treatment on identity formation of in-school adolescents ($F_{2,140}=72.73, \eta^2= .51$). Participants in ST ($\bar{x}=261.03$) had a higher enhanced identity status than those in LST ($\bar{x}=243.14$) and control ($\bar{x}=183.59$) groups. Gender and self-efficacy had no significant main effects on treatment outcome, while there were no significant interaction effects of treatment and gender, treatment and self-efficacy as well as treatment, gender and self-efficacy on identity formation. Based on this findings, schema therapy and life-skills training were recommended in enhancing identity formation of in-school adolescents in Nigeria.

Keywords: Schema therapy, Life-skills training, Identity formation, In-school adolescents.

Introduction

Identity formation is the major critical task of the adolescents. Flum and Kaplan (2012), described identity formation as the process in which individuals build sense of self and personality based on a combination of individual uniqueness as well as the feedback they receive in their relationship with significant others within their social setting. The failure to deal with this task usually affects the psychosocial functioning of an individual in the society. In Nigeria, it has been established that the adolescents are desperately searching for identity (Chudi-Oji, 2013) and majority of the adolescents are yet to form a stable identity (Salami, 2008). Ozele (2008), Osimen, Balogun and Adenegan (2013) also note that Nigerian adolescents have problem of identity crisis as they could not form a coherent sense of self.

The ill effect of falling to resolve identity issues cannot be overemphasised. Weissmann (1985) notes that those adolescents whose identities have not been formed are deeply engrossed in emotion-focused coping strategies such as wishful thinking, blaming oneself and keeping to oneself. He further reveals that such an individual will not be able to seek for social support when necessary and also find it difficult to cope with stress in life. According to Schuster and Ashburn (1992), the adolescents who failed to form their identity may use tactics to avoid the pain attached to it.

Some of the tactics include the use of drugs and alcohol, engaging in crime, absenteeism as well as academic failure, delinquency, generalised depression, aggressive behaviour and

conflicts with parents. Inability to form one's identity also lead to poor peer and family relationships, mood swing, depression, risky sexual behaviour and other bad behaviours such as abusing substance, engaging in crime, and performing poorly in school. During the peak of reliance on group acceptance, illness may crystallise underlying fears of being unwanted, alienated, and flawed (Hazen, Schlozman & Beresin, 2008).

Moreover, identity has been found to be associated with some other psychological variables. Some researchers have established the relationship between identity and some personality quality such as self-esteem, locus of control and high-level of moral reasoning (Omidian, 2009). Also, adolescents with identity diffusion are likely to experience problems in adjusting to school setting (Berzonsky, 2003). Identity confusion leads to a stern psychological pain where one failed to adapt to various aspects their personality. This crisis is characterised by doubt in various identity-related area such as enduring goals, career choice, patterns of friendship, values and commitment (Pourafkari, 1997 cited in Abdi & Bagheri, 2012). Brito, Schoen, Marteleto and Oliveira-Monteiro (2017) verified difficulties in adapting to the conventional society by the adolescents with diffused identity after leaving schools.

Several researches have focussed on the factors that could influence adolescents' identity formation, some of the identified factors include school environment (Abbassi, 2016), peers (Ragelienė, 2016), parental privacy invasion (Becht, Breddels, Hoogendoorn, Meijer & Hawk; 2012), family environment (Sartor & Youniss, 2002), self-esteem and ego resiliency (Grotevant 1987), formal operation skills (Matteson, Archer & Orlofsky in Sandhu & Tung; 2007) creativity (Berman, Schwartz, Kurtunes & Berman; 2000) and parenting styles (Romano, 2004) among others.

Although, previous researchers have worked on the factors that can influence identity formation, few studies have dwelt on appropriate intervention and to the best of the researchers' knowledge; none has considered the use of schema therapy and life skills training in enhancing identity formation. These two techniques were considered appropriate because of their capacity to change behaviour and cognition that have their root in the past experiences and its ability to enhance the adolescents with the skills necessary to handle life challenges. Therefore, the focus of this study is on utilising the tools of schema therapy and life skills training in enhancing identity formation of in-school adolescents.

Schema therapy is an integrated therapeutic approach by Young (1990). It was initially developed as an extension of cognitive-behavioural therapy. It combines vital aspect of behaviour therapy, cognitive therapy, object relations, gestalt as well as psychodynamic therapy into one united and organized approach to healing although the basic frame in the therapy is based on cognition. According to Granvold (1994), Schemas contain internal beliefs extracted from past and early-life experiences and so provide the basis of one's interpretation of oneself, others and the environment. Schema therapy aimed at weakening core beliefs about self, others and the world and replace self-destroying thoughts, feelings and behaviour with adaptive ones. (Bernstein, 2005 cited in Strack, 2005).

Some researchers have established the effectiveness of schema therapy on borderline personality disorders (Farrell, Shaw & Webber, 2009; Nadort et al., 2009), anger and hostility (Aghayousefi, Amirpour, Alipour, Zare & Badri (2015) and eating disorders Simpson, 2012), anxiety (Montazeri, Neshatdoost, Abedi & Abedi, 2014), Depression and anxiety (Lobbestael et al., 2005), Mood and anxiety disorder (Hawke & Provencher, 2011), the available sorted researches did not focus on identity formation. However, its established effectiveness on personality disorders can as well be used as a proof because it has been confirmed by Hal (2008) that some personality disorder arises as a result of failure to complete the process of identity

formation. This seems to create a relationship between identity formation and personality disorder.

Life Skills Training (LST) was developed by Botvin (1980). It is a programme originally designed to reduce the use of alcohol, tobacco, marijuana and rate of violence by focusing on the psychological and social factors that support the initiation of those behaviours. It was also designed to offer adequate information in relation some of the cogent life issues that adolescents face on a daily basis. The ten core life skills strategies and techniques are self-awareness, empathy, problem solving, decision-making, critical thinking, creative thinking, effective communication skills, interpersonal relationship skills, coping with stress and emotion. LST helps in understanding oneself, friends and the world.

The effectiveness of life skills training has been established by some researchers on emotional adjustment, educational and total adjustment, self-esteem and empathy (Pooja & Naved, 2009), Identity self concept (Sandhya & Shivani, 2012), Self-efficacy and self-esteem (Muafi, Anis & Hendri, 2010). It is expected that life-skills training will be potent in enhancing identity formation.

The Purpose of the Study

This study was designed to utilise schema therapy and life-skills training in enhancing identity formation of in-school adolescents in Nigeria.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant main effect of treatment on identity formation of in-school adolescents.
2. There is no significant main effect of gender on identity formation of in-school adolescents.
3. There is no significant main effect of self-efficacy on identity formation of in-school adolescents.
4. There is no significant interaction effect of treatment and gender on identity formation of in-school adolescents.
5. There is no significant interaction effect of treatment and self-efficacy on identity formation of in-school adolescents.
6. There is no significant interaction effect of gender and self-efficacy on identity formation of in-school adolescents.
7. There is no significant interaction effect of treatment, gender and self-efficacy on identity formation of in-school adolescents.

Research Methodology

This study adopted a pre-test, post-test, control group quasi experimental design with 3x2x3 factorial matrix which consists of two experimental groups and one control group. The two treatment groups were Schema Therapy (ST), group 1 and Life-skills training (LST), group 2, with the control, group 3 which constituted the rows while gender of the participants (male and female) and self-efficacy (low, moderate and high) constituted the columns.

Participants

The population of this study comprises all in-school adolescents in Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria. Three senior secondary schools were randomly selected for the study, each from the three local government that constitute Ilorin (East, South and West). A simple random sampling technique was adopted in selecting sixty (60) participants with low identity status (screened through the diagnostic instrument) from each of the three secondary schools. A total of one hundred and eighty (180) participants were selected and distributed to two experimental and a control group. However, only one hundred and fifty seven (157) participants completed the sessions (97 males and 60 females). Sixty (60) participants were trained on schema therapy from Bishop Smith Memorial School, forty-three (43) participants in life-skills training at the C&S College, and fifty four (54) participants were in control group from Ilorin Grammar School. Each treatment group had ten sessions.

Instrumentation

Extended Objective Measure of Ego Identity Status (Revised Extended Version-2)

Extended Objective Measure of Ego Identity (EOM-EIS II) was used to measure identity formation of in-school adolescents in this study. EOMEIS 2 was developed by Grotevant and Adams (1984), revised by Bennion and Adams (1986). This scale was used to categorise people into any of the identity statuses: diffusion, moratorium, foreclosure and achieved. The instrument comprises 64 items and assesses the identity formation of an individual across two domains (32 items each). The ideological domains include religion, occupation, politics and philosophical lifestyle while the interpersonal domain also includes 8 items each on areas of recreation, friendship, dating and sex roles. The response format for this scale is 6 points.

The scale has been utilised on adolescents by Graf (2003). Rahiminezhad and Almadi (1995) report the Cronbach alpha of 0.59-0.81. Sandhu, Singh, Tung and Kundra (2012) also report test re-test reliability of .79. Teimouri, Bagheri and Farokhi (2013) report the validity and reliability test by Cronbach alpha to be 0.82. Salami (2008) reported the internal consistency coefficient of .85. In this study, the reliability cronbach alpha of .76 was recorded.

Concerning norms and scoring method, EOMEIS items were scored weighing the “strongly disagree” response with a value of one and “strongly agree” with a value of six. Thus, the score on each subscale could range from a low of 8 to high of 48. All the items response scores will be added and compared to the norm, the cut off mark of the mean of the subscales score given by the author to classify each of the participants into any of the identity statuses with 73.0 for identity achieved, 63.0 for moratorium, 53.0 each for foreclosure and diffusion (Adams, 1998).

Some modifications were done on 15 items of this scale by rephrasing some of the statement to make the scale appropriate for the Nigerian participants. E.g: mosque was made an additional place of worship, “lifestyle” was changed to “way of life”, “folks” was changed to “friends” and “dating” was “changed to going out with opposite sex”.

General Self-efficacy Scale

GSES was developed by Schwarzer and Jerusalem (1995) and was developed to assess a general sense of perceived self-efficacy to predict coping with daily problems and adaptation after experiencing all types of stressful life events. This tool was used to measure self-efficacy of adolescents within the school in this study.

The scale contains 10 items, designed for general population and has been translated into 30 other languages apart from English. The scale have been developed with response of 4 points

format and normed by Karami (2004) cited in Teimouri, Bagheri and Farokhi (2013) reporting the validity of 0.91 through Cronbach's alpha coefficient recorded from the pilot study for this study was .77.

The scale is worded positively with a value of 4 for "Exactly true response" and value of 1 for "Not at all true" response. It is scored by summing up all responses with a range between 10 to 40 scores. High scores signify high self-efficacy while low scores signify low self-efficacy.

Ego Identity Process Questionnaire (EIPQ)

Ego Identity Process Questionnaire (EIPQ) was developed by Balistreri, Busch-Rossnagel and Geisinger in 1995. It was designed to identify people's identity status and for the purpose of this study, it was used to screen the in-school adolescents for identity formation. The EIPQ has two subscales identity exploration and identity commitment. The instrument comprises 32 items with 16 of the items measuring identity exploration and 16 items also measuring identity commitment. The item response format is a 6-point scale.

The scale has been used by several researchers, its psychometric property has been affirmed. Cronbach's alpha for the exploration subscale has been reported to be .86 with a test-retest reliability of .76. Cronbach's alpha for the commitment subscale has been reported to be .80 with a test-retest reliability of .90 (Balistreri, et.al, 1995). Berman and Kamps (2011) recorded internal consistency reliability as .78 for the commitment subscale and .77 for the exploration subscale. Cyr (2012) also recorded Cronbach's alpha of .71 for exploration and .70 for commitment.

The instrument was negatively and positively worded. Positive worded items were scored such that 1 signified strong disagreement and 6, strong agreement while the negative worded items scoring were reversed such that 6 signified strong disagreement and 1, strong disagreement. Scores could range from 16 to 96. To determine the identity statuses of the participants, the commitment score of 62, and exploration score of 66.5 was used to identify low or high commitment and exploration. These scores were selected by the author because they represented the median scores for their sample.

For this study, participants were classified into different identity statuses based on median split procedure. Those that fell under foreclosed and diffused status were selected for this study as the absence of exploration signifies identity crisis. In this study, the internal consistency of Cronbach's alpha obtained from pilot study is .65 for commitment scale and .60 for exploration scale. Three items were modified in this instrument to make it appropriate for Nigerian participants. For example, "dating relationship" was changed to "outing with opposite sex"

Procedure

A letter of introduction was submitted to the administrative office of the selected secondary schools. The researchers visited the selected secondary schools to obtain permission for the students' participation in the study after informing the administrative staff about the purpose of the research and what they stand to gain from it. Each school's SS II has six arms (A to F), after administering the screening instrument to all the SS2 students in experimental group, students with low exploration and commitment were selected. The researcher held an average of one hour training session with each of the experimental groups for 10 weeks while the control group was engaged with placebo in form of improving their performance in academic. The adolescents were administered with the same pre-test and post-test instruments. After each training session, the participants were given biscuits as incentive.

Experimental Group 1: Schema Therapy

Session 1: Introduction and pre-test administration.

Session 2: The meaning of schema and categories of schema.

Session 3: Early maladaptive schema and their origin.

Session 4: Continuation of early maladaptive schema and their origin.

Session 5: Schema domains.

Session 6: Coping styles.

Session 7: Schema modes.

Session 8: Replacing Early Maladaptive Schemas

Session 9: Behaviour modification.

Session 10: Overall review, post-experiment test administration and conclusion.

Experimental Group Two: Life Skills Training

Session 1: Introduction and pre-test administration.

Session 2: The meaning of life skills training.

Session 3: Self awareness.

Session 4: Empathy

Session 5: Creative thinking and critical thinking.

Session 6: Problem-solving

Session 7: Effective communication and Interpersonal skills.

Session 8: Coping with emotion and coping with stress.

Session 9: Behaviour modification.

Session 10: Overall review, post-experiment test administration and conclusion.

Data Analysis

The data were analysed using the Analysis of Covariance at 0.05 level of significance while Scheffe Post hoc was also done to clarify the margin of difference between the treatment groups and control group.

Results

Hypothesis One: There is no significant main effect of treatment on identity formation of in-school adolescents.

Table 1 shows there is significant main effects of treatments on identity formation of in-school adolescents ($F_{(2,140)} = 72.731, p < .05, \eta^2 = .510$). This implies that there is a significant impact of the treatment on identity formation of in-school adolescents. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected, the table also reveals the contributing effect size of .510. Considering hypothesis two and three which states that there will be no main effect of gender and self-efficacy respectively on identity formation of in-school adolescents, Table 4 further reveals that there was no significant main effect of gender and self-efficacy on identity formation, thereby accepting hypotheses two and three. The fourth hypothesis asserts that there will be no interaction effect of treatment, gender and self-efficacy on identity formation of in-school adolescents. Table 1 showed that there was no significant interaction between treatment, gender and self-efficacy. This hypothesis was therefore retained, implying that gender and self-efficacy do not combine to influence identity formation of the in-school adolescents.

Table 1: ANCOVA of the Significant Main and Interaction Effects of Treatment, Gender and Self-efficacy on Identity Formation of In-school Adolescents

Source	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Eta ²
Corrected Model	197301.754	16	12331.360	26.024	.000	.748
Pretest Identity Formation	793.473	1	793.473	1.675	.198	.012
<i>Main Effect:</i>						
Treatment	68925.693	2	34462.846	72.731	.000	.510
Self-Efficacy	1374.666	2	687.333	1.451	.238	.020
Gender	.74.301	1	374.301	.790	.376	.006
<i>2-way Interactions:</i>						
Treatment x Self-Efficacy	3177.793	4	794.448	1.677	.159	.046
Treatment x Gender	2010.244	2	1005.122	2.121	.124	.029
Self- Efficacy x Gender	770.716	2	385.358	.813	.445	.011
<i>3-way Interaction:</i>						
Treatment x Self-Efficacy x Gender	92.502	2	46.251	.098	.907	.001
Residual	66337.495	140	473.839			
Total	263639.248	156				

R.squared =.748 (Adjusted R squared = .720)

Table 2: Scheffe Post-Hoc Pair wise analysis showing the significant differences among various treatments and the control group

Treatment	N	Subset for alpha = .05	
		Mean difference	Std. Error
Control	54	183.5926	
Life-skill training	43	243.1395	
Schema therapy	60	261.0333	1.000

Table 2 shows that after controlling for the effect of pre-identity formation of in-school adolescents, experimental group I (schema therapy) mean of 261.03 is higher than the experimental II (Life-skills training) mean which is of 243.14 and control group mean of 183.6. This shows that schema therapy is more potent in enhancing identity formation of in-school adolescents than life-skills training. The coefficient determination (Adjusted R-squared =.720) overall indicates that the differences that exist in the groups account for 72% in the variation of students’ identity formation.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant main effect of gender on identity formation of in-school adolescents.

The results from Table 1 indicate there was no significant main effect of gender on identity formation of in-school adolescents ($F_{(1,140)} = .790, p > .05, \eta^2 = .006$). Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. Meaning that there is was significant difference between male and female in-school adolescents in their identity formation.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant main effect of self-efficacy on identity formation of in-school adolescents.

The result from Table 1 reveals there was no significant main effect of self-efficacy on identity formation of in-school adolescents ($F_{(2,140)} = 1.451, p > .05, \eta^2 = .020$). The null

hypothesis is therefore accepted; implying that there was no significant difference between the levels of self-efficacy on identity formation of in-school adolescents.

Hypothesis Four: There is no significant interaction effect of treatment and gender on identity formation of in-school adolescents.

Table 1 shows there was no significant interaction effect of treatment and gender on identity formation of in-school adolescents ($F_{(2,140)} = 2.121, p > .05, \eta^2=.029$). The null hypothesis is accepted; this shows there was no significant interaction effect of treatment groups and gender on identity formation of in-school adolescents.

Hypothesis Five: There is no significant interaction effect of treatment and self-efficacy on identity formation of in-school adolescents

The results from Table 1 indicate there was no significant interaction effect of treatment and self-efficacy on identity formation of in-school adolescents ($F_{(4,140)} = 1.677, p > .05, \eta^2=.046$). The null hypothesis is accepted; implying that there was no significant interaction effect of treatment and self-efficacy on identity formation of in-school adolescents.

Hypothesis Six: There is no significant interaction effect of gender and self-efficacy on identity formation of in-school adolescents.

Table 1 reveals there was no significant interaction effect of gender and self-efficacy on identity formation of in-school adolescents ($F_{(2,140)} = .813, p > .05, \eta^2=.011$). The null hypothesis is accepted; therefore, there was no significant interaction effect of gender and self-efficacy on identity formation of in-school adolescents.

Hypothesis Seven: There is no significant interaction effect of treatment, gender and self-efficacy on identity formation of in-school adolescents.

It was signified in Table 1 that there was no significant interaction effect of treatment, self-efficacy and gender on identity formation of in-school adolescents ($F_{(16,140)} = .098, p > .05, \eta^2=.001$). The null hypothesis is accepted; meaning that there was no significant interaction effect between treatment, gender and self-efficacy on identity formation of in-school adolescents.

Discussion

Schema therapy and life-skills training were effective in enhancing identity formation of in-school adolescents. Table 2 clearly shows the marginal difference of the intervention groups are higher the control group. Although the existing and sorted literature available to the researcher has not used schema therapy in enhancing identity formation, this study has successfully established the effectiveness of schema therapy in enhancing identity formation. Kellogg and Young (2006) find schema therapy effective for the treatment of borderline personality disorder. It was believed that the major problem with these patients were distorted thinking and emotional reactions.

Giesen-Bloo et al, (2006), Waller, et.al. (2000) and Simpson (2012), Farrell, Shaw and Webber (2009) also confirm the effectiveness of schema therapy. Mokhatari, Bahrami, Padash, Hosseinian and Soltaniadeh (2012) further confirmed the effectiveness of schema therapy on marital satisfaction of couples. Hosseinifardi, et.al (2011) affirm the efficacy of schema therapy in treating women with dysthymia disorder. Montaseri et.al (2013) also support the effectiveness of schema therapy on obsessive compulsive personal disorder and depression. Kellogg and Young (2006) affirm the efficacy of schema therapy on substance abuse. Sabet, Nejad and

Khalatbari (2016) confirm that schema therapy is very effective in treating depression in women engaging in high-risk sexual behaviors.

This study also notes that life-skill training is effective in enhancing identity formation of in-school adolescents. This finding aligns with Yadav and Igbal (2009) that life-skills training is a potent tool to increase on self-esteem, emotional adjustment, educational adjustment, total adjustment and empathy of adolescents. Further, the finding of this study corroborates that of Anderson (2009) that life-skills training is effective in facilitating self-awareness. This study also supports Friesenhahn (1999), Winkleby et.al. (2004) cited in Yadav and Igbal (2009) who also affirm the effectiveness of life-skills training on self-esteem. This study also corroborates Prajapati, Sharma and Sharma (2017) which affirms life skill education helps in imparting the adolescents to develop social, emotional and thinking skills as they are the important building blocks for a dynamic citizen, who can cope up with future challenges, and survive well.

To find plausible explanations to the findings of this study, the researcher is of the opinion that schema therapy was very effective because it helps people identify their own schemas by understanding their origins and relating their schemas to their perception of self and then using different mechanisms such as imagery, letter writing and re-parenting to replace maladaptive coping styles with healthier behaviour which will also reflect on their perception of self.

However, gender differences have no significant impact on identity formation of in-school adolescents. The report of this study aligns with that of Louis and Lieum (2005) that there was no difference between men and women overall identity scores. This study also confirms the finding of Salami (2008) who reports there is no gender difference in identity status of adolescents. This study is also consistent with that of Makhubela and Debusho (2013), Imtiaz and Nagvi (2012), Khodarahirni and Cothran (2009), Kumru and Thomson (2003) as well as Meeus et.al (1999) who also reported a non significant difference of gender with respect to identity formation.

In giving justification to this result, the process of proceeding through identity status is similar for males and females, implying that genders involve themselves in the identity process similarly. Another reason for the non-significance effect of gender on identity formation could probably be as a result of the fact that females gender role seems to be in conformity with that of males. This idea is in line with that of Steinberg and Morris (2001). The main goal of identity formation in adolescence is to develop a distinct sense of self. This is done by trying to play different roles in different places such as home, schools, churches, mosques, according to gender expectations. Apparently, in the contemporary society, gender expectations and gender roles seems not to be different anymore.

In the same vein, there was no significant main effect of self-efficacy on identity formation of in-school adolescents. The result of this study corroborates that of Allan, Johnson and Szostak (2009) that there is no direct effect of academic self-efficacy on identity status of adolescents.

The explanation for the non-significance of self-efficacy on identity formation in this study could be as a result of the fact that self-efficacy is not based on illusions or unrealistic optimism but strictly on experience leading to venturesome behaviour within the reach of one's capacity. Some people might believe in their ability to perform a certain task but when the time comes for them to perform, they might not be able to successfully do so. Although high self-efficacy positively affects motivation and commitment, there is still a gap between self-efficacy and performance of the task. This is in support of the findings of Vancouver, Thompson, Tischner and Putka (2002) cited in Redmond (2015) who stated that self-efficacy does not imply improved performance.

Similarly, there was no significant interaction effect of treatment and gender on identity formation of in-school adolescents. This result contradicts that of Louis and Liem (2005), Bergh and Erling (2005), Sandhu and Tung (2006), Imitiaz and Nagvi (2012), Johnson, Kent and Yale (2012) who report significant effect of gender on identity development. Despite the inconsistency in the literature pertaining to the effect of gender on identity formation, this finding aligns with that of Makhubela and Debusho (2013) that there is non-significant effect of gender on identity status of secondary school adolescents. The findings of this study did not show any gender difference in the effects of treatments on identity formation of in-school adolescents possibly because the content of the treatment package in ST and LST did not give any consideration to the gender of the participants. Participants were given equal treatment regardless of their gender.

Furthermore, there was no significant interaction effect of treatment and self-efficacy on identity formation of in-school adolescents. This result aligns with that of Adediwura (2012) who reported a non significant interaction effect of treatment and self-efficacy and self-autonomy in the learning of mathematics after the use of peer and self-assessment. This finding opposes that of Teimouri, Bagheri and Farokhi (2013), Gushue, Clarke, Oantzer and Scanlan (2006) and Bandura in Abdi et al (2008) who report self-efficacy as influence of identity formation.

From the above studies, although the levels of self-efficacy could strongly affect the formation of one's identity, the fact remains that they are two different main constructs which could either influence each other or not, depending on the participants and considering other external factors such as peer influence, socioeconomic status, parenting styles, family type and the likes which the participant and researcher have no influence over which could have been the basis for this result. The outcome of this study could be tied to parental influences (social class) as development is triggered by experiences and discriminations.

Similarly, there was no significant interaction effect of gender and self-efficacy on identity formation of in-school adolescents. It is difficult to compare the result of this finding with past studies on interaction effect of gender and self-efficacy on identity formation of in-school adolescents because there has been paucity of research on this relationship. The researcher's justification for this result is that though distinct gender roles socialisation prevails in some culture, the fact remains that girls and boys are capable of making equitable and consolidated commitment for having distinct but compatible opportunities. Self-efficacy and identity formation might also be mediated by certain personal characteristics not considered in this study.

Lastly, there was no significant interaction effect of treatment, gender and self-efficacy on identity formation of in-school adolescents. This study corroborates that of Nbina and Vico (2010) and Ewumi, Viatonu and Olagunju (2013) that there is no significant interaction effect of treatment, gender and academic self-efficacy. This finding also aligns with Falaye and Okoye (2011). The possible explanation of the results of this study is that adolescents are faced with the same developmental tasks irrespective of their and they both experience the same environmental issues in school and at home, peer pressure and influences with the same expectations from teachers, parents and the society. This may account for the insignificance of interaction effect of treatment, gender and self-efficacy on identity formation of in-school adolescents, permitting just main effect of treatment on identity formation of in-school adolescents.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Schema therapy and life-skills training were effective in enhancing identity formation of in-school adolescents. Although, the two treatments were effective in enhancing identity formation among in-school adolescents, schema therapy was more effective. The packages of this study can

be incorporated into senior secondary school curriculum by policymakers, counsellors and school service providers should utilise these strategies to improve identity status of adolescents.

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Anxiety and warmth as correlates of expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers in Owerri

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Abstract

This study investigated anxiety and warmth as correlates of expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers in Owerri. Using correlation design, one research question was answered and two hypotheses were tested. Three standardized questionnaires (Relationship Satisfaction Scale $\alpha=.90$; Non-Specific Anxiety Scale (NSAS) $\alpha=.76$ and Self-reported Warmth Scale $\alpha=.91$), were used to collect data from one hundred and fifty (150) purposively selected married expectant mothers attending antenatal clinic in government health institutions on Owerri Municipal Council Area of Imo State. Data collected was analysed at 0.05 level of significance using Multiple Regression Analysis and Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistical tools. Result of the study revealed that anxiety and warmth correlate significantly with expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers. Therefore, it is recommended that Spouses should endeavour to be supportive of each other in marital relationship as to develop trust and confidence that will help reduce fear and possible anxiety.

Keywords: Anxiety, Expectant Mothers, Marital Satisfaction, Married, Warmth and Owerri

Introduction

Marriage is the institutional bedrock for the formation of a family unit whose functional interaction is hinged on formidable relationships and communication among members. Family interactions among couples at the event of pregnancy could signal the beginning of a new concern as pregnancy is an exciting developmental experience associated with significant transition into motherhood/fatherhood. For married women, this experience is often an overwhelming event with physical, emotional, and social effects that could have implications on their marital satisfaction. This assertion is made considering the fact that marital satisfaction during pregnancy could be influenced by expressed spousal interactional dispositions which if ignored could have devastating impact on marital life of couples. According to Zare, Golmakani, Shareh, Shakeri and Khadem (2014) positive socio-emotional and religious inclination expressed by spouses has implication on their feeling of marital satisfaction. Also, Flores (2008) posited that when married couples are satisfied with their life experience, they relate well with each other, reason together and support each other to raise a functional family they will be proud of. In view of this context, this study investigates anxiety and warmth as correlates of expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers in Owerri Imo state Nigeria.

Sanders (2010) affirmed that marital satisfaction is essential in preserving a marital relationship and could be expressed in line with the feeling of personal accomplishment and contentment with their new life experience in an interactional context. Interaction between spouses most especially when the woman is pregnant could make them feel happy being married or mar their feeling of satisfaction. For example, when a pregnant woman criticizes or nags

probably due to her new physiological experience, could lead to initial criticism and disengagement that would fuel family discord. Thus, as expectant married mothers' transit experiencing developmental concern that gives sense of joy, accomplishment, belongingness and satisfaction, they put in their best to project positive family and societal values that would make them emotionally stable and happier relating to their spouse and family members. However, when behavioural dispositions go contrary to normative expectations, it could have implications on the wellbeing of spouses (Sanders, 2010).

Abedi, Bakhshani, Mohebbi, Mahmudian, Ahovan and Mokhtari (2015) asserted that when expectant mothers' are not happy in their marriage, they could become anxious and emotionally unstable. However, when they feel satisfied they relate well with their spouses and family members. Also, Yeniel (2014) reported that negative bilateral relationship interface among expectant mothers' and their marital environment has grave implication on their body physiology, mental state of mind and sexual satisfaction. When pregnant women are dissatisfied with their family environment, their anxiety increases, they express mood swing and are easily irritated (Afrakoti & Shahhosseini, 2016). Expressed anxiety of expectant married mothers reflects the expression of uneasiness or apprehension experienced before or during delivery (Okoiye, 2011). The most common challenging concern of some expectant mothers' that could make them dissatisfied of their developmental experience is the expression of anxiety due to fear of the unknown (Gold, Sen & Hayward, 2010). For instance, as reported by Stutzman (2009) some expectant mothers' experience environmental stress that put them at risks of being anxious or depressed.

Also, warmth is an important factor that is required to stimulate affection, confidence; trust and genuine feeling of attachment expressed through verbal and non-verbal communication. Expressed feeling of warmth by spouse to their expectant wife ignites in them joy and a sense of satisfaction as regards their choice of husband. It enables couples to feel free and happy to relate with each other and disclose possible challenges that could have degenerated to conflict. It is a dynamics for emotional stability, purposeful and functional relationship for example couples found of kissing each other or using humour and patient listening to themselves speak and criticizing less are easily attached, satisfied with their marriage and bond together in love (Stutzman, 2009). This implies that couple's verbal and non-verbal behavioural disposition has significant impact on their level of satisfaction. Thus, when couples interpersonal relationship is positive, it ignites pleasant emotions, promotes intimate understanding, self-satisfaction and healthy psychological wellbeing (Kim, Capaldi & Crosby, 2007).

Warmth can only be expressed through communication either verbal or non-verbal. This indicates that expressed positive warmth is an important mechanism that can be used to foster and sustain functional marital relationship that will be satisfying to couples. Communication takes off the burden of suspicion, fear; anxiety and enshrine the feeling togetherness and satisfaction of being married. This implies that when expectant mothers and spouse develop a stimulating warmth relationship early anchored on effective verbal and non-verbal communication system (posture, gestures), it increases their possibilities of interaction. This experience enables them to hear each other, to question and comment on topics for which there is personal interest, they can collaborate and interact optimally, so that each of them is stimulated to evolve and to experience satisfaction. Expression of warmth by spouses is gear towards positively reinforcing high interpersonal functioning level echoed in the psycho-emotional level of expressed marital satisfaction and emotional balance. Warmth expression in marital relationship translates into mutual affection and a central foundation for stability and functionality (Rodica, 2013).

The focus of this study is consistent with the contextual postulation of the theory of reason action. This theory affirms the fact that the intention to behave in a particular way is determined by an individual's comprehension of the possible resultant consequence and impact on wellbeing. This means that couples that desire to be happy will reason in a positive and purposeful manner to achieve satisfaction by disposing positive attitude (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1980). Therefore, the desire to experience marital satisfaction could propel expectant mothers and their spouse to work towards achieving it by disposing positive attitude that will reinforce pleasant feeling and stimulate memorable experience. The stronger the intention, the more they would show commitment to achieve it. This assertion makes this theory applicable to this study.

Marital dissatisfaction can be an unpleasant experience for the developmental wellbeing of expectant married women mostly when it is due to the inability of their spouse to express warmth gestures such as hugging, fondling, caressing, approving glances, kissing, smiling, indications of endearment, support, praising, and complimenting expressed through verbal and non verbal communication. The absence of these could generate anxiety as a result of possible ill-thought and negative insinuations. When this occurs, the experience could mar marital bliss and the wellbeing of an expectant mother considering the fact that expressed attitudinal disposition in the marital environment could change negatively. In view of this context, this study investigated anxiety and warmth as correlates of marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers in Owerri Imo state Nigeria.

Research Question

What relationships exist between anxiety, warmth and expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers?

Hypotheses

1. There will be no significant relationship between anxiety and expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers
2. There will be no significant relationship between warmth and expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers

Methodology

A correlation design was adopted using questionnaires to elicit response from respondents. Convenience sampling technique was used to purposively select one hundred and fifty (150) married expectant mothers attending antenatal clinic in government health institutions on Owerri Municipal Council Area of Imo State Nigeria.

Marital Satisfaction was measured using Relationship Satisfaction Scale. It is a standardised instrument that has been used across culture. Response to the items requires individuals used for the study to rate how happy and satisfied they are with their relationship with their spouse. High rating signifies satisfaction. It has a co-efficient of $\alpha=.90$ (Cutrona, Russell, Abraham, Gardner, Melby, Bryant & Conger 2003).

Anxiety of expectant mothers was measured using the Non-Specific Anxiety Scale (NSAS), by (Stutzman, 2009). It is a standardised Likert scale whose items elicit response to determine the extent to which expectant mothers behavioural disposition is impaired by expressed anxiety in their everyday relationship with their immediate environment. High score indicates high level of expressed anxiety. It has a coefficient of $\alpha=.76$.

Feeling of warmth of expectant mothers was measured using (Conger & Elder, 1994) warmth scale with nine self reported response items that addresses behavioural dispositions depicting the extent to which expectant mothers experience support, show of concern, understanding, care and expressed affection from their husbands. The scores attained indicate the level of feeling of warmth experienced by expectant mothers. It has a coefficient of $\alpha=.91$.

Procedure

Researcher sought permission to conduct the study from health centre authorities and equally explained the intention of the study to expectant mothers used for the study. Expectant mothers were given the required questionnaires to fill. The filled questionnaires were used for data analysis.

Data Analysis

The statistical tools used to analyse data for the study were Pearson Product Moment Correlation and Multiple regression at 0.05 level of significance

Results

Research Question

What relationships exist between anxiety, warmth and expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers?

Table 1: Showing relationship between the variables

Variables	N	X	Std Dev	1	2	3
Expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers	150	28.21	6.11	1.000		
Anxiety	150	22.18	4.23	.314	1.000	
Warmth	150	24.37	4.61	.526	.419	1.000

Table 1 highlights the level of correlation between the variables (anxiety, warmth and expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers) if significant or not. The result revealed in order of magnitude that warmth, (R=0.526, p<0.05) and anxiety (R=0.314, p<0.05) has significant correlation with expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers. Thus, when expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers is high, their expressed anxiety about themselves or environment will be low. Likewise, when expressed warmth gestures among spouses are high, marital satisfaction of expectant married mothers will be high. However, when anxiety is high and expressed warmth low, marital satisfaction of expectant married mothers will be low.

Ho1: There will be no significant relationship between anxiety and expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers

Table 2: Showing correlation between anxiety and expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers

Variables	N	X	SD	R	df	P
Expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers	150	28.21	6.11	0.314	148	Sig
Anxiety	150	22.18	4.23			

Table 2 shows that the variable anxiety correlates significantly with expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers, r (148) = 0.314, p<.05. Hypothesis is therefore rejected. This implies that low anxiety impacts positively on expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers.

Ho2: There will be no significant relationship between warmth and expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers

Table 3: Showing correlation between warmth and expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers

Variables	N	X	SD	R	df	p
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expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers	150	28.21	6.11	0.526	148	sig
Warmth	150	24.37	4.61			

Table 3 shows that warmth correlates significantly with expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers, $r(148) = 0.526, p < .05$. Hypothesis is therefore rejected. This highlights the fact that when expressed spouse's warmth is high and affectionate, expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers will be high.

Discussion of Results

The result of the research question revealed that positive relationship exist between anxiety, warmth and expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers. This development indicates that when expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers is high, their expressed anxiety about themselves or environment will be low. Likewise, when expressed warmth gestures among spouses are high, marital satisfaction of expectant married mothers will be high. However, when anxiety is high and expressed warmth low, marital satisfaction of expectant married mothers will be low. This assertion is made considering the fact that marital satisfaction during pregnancy could be influenced by expressed spousal interactional dispositions which if ignored could have devastating impact on marital life of couples. According to Zare, Golmakani, Shareh, Shakeri and Khadem (2014) positive socio-emotional and religious inclination expressed by spouses has implication on their feeling of marital satisfaction. Also, Flores (2008) posited that when married couples are satisfied with their life experience, they relate well with each other, reason together and support each other to raise a functional family they will be proud of. In support, Sanders (2010) affirmed that marital satisfaction is essential in preserving a marital relationship and could be expressed in line with the feeling of personal accomplishment and contentment with their new life experience in an interactional context. Interaction between spouses most especially when the woman is pregnant could make them feel happy being married or mar their feeling of satisfaction. For example, when a pregnant woman criticizes or nags probably due to her new physiological experience, could lead to initial criticism and disengagement that would fuel family discord. Thus, as expectant married mothers' transit experiencing developmental concern that gives sense of joy, accomplishment, belongingness and satisfaction, they put in their best to project positive family and societal values that would make them emotionally stable and happier relating to their spouse and family members.

Also, anxiety correlates significantly with expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers, $r(148) = 0.314, p < .05$. The result indicates that low anxiety impacts positively on expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers. Also, it indicates that women with lower marital satisfaction experience a greater amount of anxiety during pregnancy. For example, Abedi, Bakhshani, Mohebbi, Mahmudian, Ahovan and Mokhtari (2015) asserted that when expectant mothers' are not happy in their marriage, they could become anxious and emotionally unstable. However, when they feel satisfied they relate well with their spouses and family members. Also, Yenieli (2014) reported that negative bilateral relationship interface among expectant mothers' and their marital environment has grave implication on their body physiology, mental state of mind and sexual satisfaction. When pregnant women are dissatisfied with their family environment, their anxiety increases, they express mood swing and are easily irritated (Afrakoti & Shahhosseini, 2016). Expressed anxiety of expectant married mothers reflects the expression of uneasiness or apprehension experienced before or during delivery (Okoiye, 2011).

Likewise, warmth correlates significantly with expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers, $r(148) = 0.526, p < .05$. This finding revealed that when expressed spouse's warmth is high and affectionate, expressed marital satisfaction among married expectant mothers will be high. This projects the fact that the expression of warmth feelings through effective communication towards one's partner can foster better appreciation and understanding of developmental needs of pregnant women and spouse within marital relationship. Expressed feeling of warmth by spouse to their expectant wife ignites in them joy and a sense of satisfaction as regards their choice of husband. It enables couples to feel free and happy to relate with each other and disclose possible challenges that could have degenerated to conflict. It is a dynamics for emotional stability, purposeful and functional relationship for example couples who are found of kissing each other or using humour and patient listening to themselves speak and criticizing less are easily attached, satisfied with their marriage and bond together in love (Stutzman, 2009). This implies that couple's verbal and non-verbal behavioural disposition has significant impact on their level of satisfaction. Thus, when couples interpersonal relationship is positive, it ignites pleasant emotions, promotes intimate understanding, self-satisfaction and healthy psychological wellbeing (Kim, Capaldi & Crosby, 2007). This further indicates that when expectant mothers and spouse develop a stimulating warmth relationship early anchored on effective verbal and non-verbal communication system (posture, gestures), it increases their possibilities of interaction. This experience enables them to hear each other, to question and comment on topics for which there is personal interest, they can collaborate and interact optimally, so that each of them is stimulated to evolve and to experience satisfaction.

Conclusion and Recommendations

When couples are satisfied with their marital experience, they tend to live in harmony, functional, less anxious, loving and productive as the feel of satisfaction in a marriage reinforce warmth positive attitudinal disposition and reduce marital anxiety.

The experience of marital satisfaction fosters positive developmental experience of spouses and further enhances expectant mothers' wellbeing; therefore, spouses should ensure love prevails in their union.

Spouses should endeavour to be supportive of each other in marital relationship as to develop trust and confidence that will help reduce fear and possible anxiety.

Spouses should endeavour to express warmth gestures using effective verbal and non-verbal measure of communication to reinforce the feelings of marital affections and satisfaction.

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Influence of Social Intelligence and EPQ Personality Dimensions on Religious Tolerance among Cadets of Nigeria Police Academy

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Abstract

Toleration of another's religious creed is a sine qua non for good leadership. Similarly, certain personality traits facilitate or hinder the expression of good leadership qualities. The aim of this study is to isolate a few established personality traits believed to be associated with leadership qualities and determine if they are related to tolerating others' religions. Specifically, religious tolerance was regressed on the dimensions of Social Intelligence and that of EPQ among the police cadets (N= 227, Age range = 17 to 27 years, Mean = 23.01, Standard Deviation =3.433, 80% males). First, Social intelligence and EPQ were distinct (dimensions) variables viz.: Social information processing (SIP); Social awareness (SA); Social skills (SS); Psychoticism; and Neuroticism. Secondly, the result of hierarchical multiple regression showed

that some of both dimensions significantly predicted and account for variations in religious tolerance (Social Information Processing: $\beta = .150$, $R^2 = .081$, $p = .03$; Social Awareness: $\beta = -.260$, $\Delta R^2 = .001$, $p = .001$; Social Skills: $\beta = .397$, $\Delta R^2 = .102$, $p = .000$; Psychoticism: $\beta = -.117$, $\Delta R^2 = .012$, $p = .075$; Neuroticism: $\beta = .007$, $\Delta R^2 = .00$, $p = .916$). On the premise that good leadership entails many behavioural traits, we deduce that these dimensions are requisite to leadership qualities and have relationship with religious tolerance.

It is recommended that personnel who aspire to police leadership, and individuals in general should be well observed and screened for psychotic and neurotic tendencies to get things right with governance.

Keywords: Social information processing, social skills, social awareness, neuroticism, psychoticism, social intelligence, EPQ, religious tolerance, police cadets, leadership

Introduction

The Nigerian national goal is to overcome religious conflict by ushering in leaders must be sensitive and tolerant enough to bridge the gap among the various religious groups. Such leaders should be able to accommodate the diverse religious creed and be a role model towards the toleration of Nigerians' religious inclinations is desirable. Unfortunately, Nigeria being a pluralistic state has experienced her own fair own share of religious skirmishes.

It is no secret that religion creates its own tension in the country. Soyinka (2017) warned that "if we do not tame religion it will kill Nigeria". Such is the seriousness of the religious conundrum that is being faced in the country. Sampson (2012) pointed out that religious violence due to intolerance of others' religious beliefs camouflages as ethno-religious conflict and a lot of committees and panels of inquiry were set up to investigate both the cause and effects of these crises, and to proffer solution to avert same occurring in future. It will appear that leadership lacks the political will to implement the recommendations; a sensitive leader would have done otherwise and mandated the security and judicial agencies to put into effect these proposals.

Research has shown that there were numerous qualities associated with a leader either in an organization or within any group for that matter. Leadership qualities were examined in the educational sector (Amanchukwu, Stanley & Ololube, 2015); in business organizations (Caligiuri, & Tarique, 2012); multicultural diverse groups (Chuang 2013); and in political groups (Gaffney, 2001). Some of these characteristics are being displayed by a leader depending on the objectives to be achieved in a given situation within a group. Leaders give directions and take initiatives for the well-being of any group they lead. These leadership qualities are needed to combat social problems (Cleveland-Innes, 2012), one of which could be religious intolerance. The question is which leadership group is mostly required to show religious unbiasedness and detachment while carrying out their leadership duties? Police personnel is expected to play leadership roles while discharging their constitutional assignment of law enforcement and crime

prevention and detection. The Police are saddled with the task of “protecting lives and properties; employed for the prevention and detection of crime; responsible for the apprehension of offenders; and the preservation of law and order; and the due enforcement of all laws and regulations with which they are directly charged, and shall perform such military duties within and without Nigeria as may be required of them by, or under the authority of this or any other act” (Police Acts, 1979, Part II Section 4). These responsibilities require a great amount of toleration of citizens’ religious creeds and practices more so in a secular state such as Nigeria.

A few personality dispositions were identified (Mebu, Dauda, & Oluwafemi 2016; Mebu, Abu, Igboanusi-Ossai & Oluwafemi, 2017) but their sub-elements are yet to be explored. The present study adds to and complements these findings by introducing the dimensions of social intelligence viz. social information process, social skills and social awareness; and the EPQ personality factors of psychoticism and neuroticism as behaviours that are associated with the religious tolerance level of individuals in leadership position such as police personnel- specifically those still in training and waiting to be commissioned. This is informed by the popular parlance, “*Catch them young*”.

The first goal of this study is to delineate these personality dimensions and factors, and establish their distinctiveness from each other among the sample of the study. In other words, there are five different variables which are believed to be independent of one another; and the second goal is that their respective independent and collective influence on religious tolerance is being examined among the police cadets. Police cadets form the population of interest for this investigation.

Dimensions of Social Intelligence

Social intelligence is a pervasive construct which has been identified as a variable with several sub-elements (e.g. Marlowe, 1986; Goleman, 2007; Silvera, Martinussen, Dahl, 2001). However, researches demonstrate that these sub-elements vary and can be quantified and tapped from different orientations and perspectives (Vasil’ová & Baumgartner 2005). Social intelligence is the ability to act wisely in human relations- “an ability to understand people and cooperate with them” (Thorndike, 1920). This definition seems to be the simplest that has been tendered. The literature also varies about the definition and measurement of social intelligence (Vasil’ová & Baumgartner 2005).

Among these definitions are: the ability to understand other people and how they will react to different social situation (Silvera, Martinussen, Dahl, 2001); an individual’s fund of knowledge about social world (Kihlstrom & Cantor, 2000); the skills and facilitators that determine how effectively we understand and express ourselves, understand others and the social context, to interact with other people and cope with daily demands (Bar-On, 2006; Barnes & Sternberg, 1989). This study adopts the dimensions of social intelligence as conceptualized by Silvera et al. (2001) and assesses it as such. These three sub-dimensions include: Social Information Processing- the ability to read and predict the behaviours of others; Social Awareness- being conscious of people’s choices, comportment and behaving as they would expect; and Social Skills- the ability to interact effectively with others, being able to engage novel social settings and having a sociable and amiable disposition. The components of social intelligence were distinct entities (e.g. Vasil’ová & Baumgartner 2005; Grieve & Mahar 2013, Marlowe, 1986; Goleman, 2007; Silvera, Martinussen, & Dahl, 2001; Riggio & Reichard, 2008). In fact, the dimension of social skills has been employed to solely represent social intelligence (Riggio & Reichard, 2008; Cuadra-Peralta, Veloso-Besio, Iribaren & Pinto, 2017). The literature clearly supports that these dimensions are different entities.

Social awareness is the growth of interpersonal understanding and the development of capacities to comprehend and consider other's social perspectives (Selman, 2003). It presents social and moral dilemma that forces us to make complex decisions about conflicting principles, and loyalties occur in all our lives as a result (Selman, 2003). However, it is being approached, social awareness makes us conscious of peoples' choices, worldviews and belief systems. What an individual does with this understanding could be a subjective matter. Intuitively, the component of social awareness ought to make us come to terms with the religious views and opinions of others, but do we have any idea of what this knowledge will translate to in terms of accommodating those biases? It is hoped that some light will be shed on this question.

Social information processing, as a factor, was implicated in aggressive behaviour. Dodge & Crick (1990), using a children sample, pointed out that our behavioural response to problematic social stimulus (maybe having to interact with another individual with a different religious creed and values) is a function of five steps of social information processing: encoding of social cues, interpretation of social cues, response search, response evaluation, and enactment. Skillful processing at each step is hypothesized to lead to competent performance within a situation, whereas biased or deficient processing is hypothesized to lead to deviant social behaviour; and an adept execution or inappropriate management of such social stimulus has been found to predict individual differences in aggressive behaviour- religious intolerance is a form of unaccommodating and aggressive behaviour. In addition, Dodge & Rabiner (2004) suggested that social information processing could hamper or facilitate moral development. It has been submitted that all religion assists in moral development, hence similar tenets are expected of most religions. This ought to engender toleration among religious faithful and practitioners. Research has also strongly linked competent social information processing patterns with pro-social behaviour (Mayeux & Cillessen, 2003; Nelson & Crick, 1999) – religious tolerance is a form of pro-social behaviour.

Social skill is the capacity to relate and intermingle successfully with others, being able to fit into new societal situations and having a gregarious and friendly personality; and confidence in ones' social performing abilities. Training in social skills has reduced disruptive and destructive behaviours in autistic children (Golzari, Alamdarloo & Moradi, 2015; Hotton & Coles, 2016). It has also been shown to facilitate academic performance (Comedis, 2014); and helps in negotiations in the labour market (Deming, 2017).

Dimensions of EPQ

Psychoticism is seen as reflecting behaviours such as tough-mindedness, non-conformity, inconsideration, recklessness, hostility, anger, impulsiveness, aggressiveness, depressiveness and criminality (Eysenck, 1992). Egan, Kroll, Carey, Johnson & Erickson (2004) posit that there are no significant evidences that a relationship exists between psychoticism and religiosity, and even if any exists it is since the sample is from a student population. There had been reported relationship between psychoticism and religiosity (Eysenck, Eysenck & Barrett, 1985; Allport & Ross 1967), though without much empirical backing. Studies have however shown a negative relationship between psychoticism and intrinsic religious orientation (Maltby, Talley, Cooper & Francis, 1995). Psychoticism has been especially found to be negatively related to many pleasant religious variables (Hills, Francis, Argyle & Jackson, 2004; Mebu et. al, 2016). Specifically, Mebu et. al (2016) found a significant negative relationship between psychoticism and religious tolerance in a sample of prospective cadets. This study attempts to examine its relative influence among other variables in a sample of ASP police cadets.

The EPQ dimension of neuroticism constitutes traits such as being moody, anxious, worried, fearful, angry, frustrated, envious, jealous, guilty, depressed, and lonely (Thompson,

2008). Bech, Lunde, & Møller (2012) recommended that all the items on the EPQ Neuroticism dimension should be considered symptoms as informed by Eysenck & Eysenck (1969) observation about the scoring format of the questionnaire. Hills & Argyle (1998) observed relatively significant low neuroticism scores among church (members) goers compared to non-church (members) goers. This suggests that churchgoers are less neurotic than non-churchgoers. A similar result was obtained by Taylor & MacDonald (1999); they found that neuroticism scores on the BFI were less for those with religious affiliation compared with those without religious affiliation among a sample of around 1100 Canadian students, implying that those with healthy attachment to their religious beliefs are less neurotic compared to those who are loosely and unwholesomely connected to their religious ideas. In contrast to this finding, Singh & Gupta (1996) found that neuroticism was positively associated with religious values among a sample of Indians. Religious Tolerance is a positive religious behaviour and should be associated with balanced emotional indices and communal acumen. Therefore, we expect fewer neurotic scores among more tolerant individuals. Mebu et. al (2016) gave support for the position when they observed a negative correlation between neuroticism and religious tolerance among intending police cadets. Albeit, without the consideration of other factors, this research explored the extent of this relationship alongside social intelligence measures.

This study tested the following hypotheses:

1. Social information processing will significantly predict religious tolerance among cadets;
2. Social awareness will significantly predict religious tolerance among cadets;
3. Social skill will significantly predict religious tolerance among cadets;
4. Psychoticism will significantly predict religious tolerance among cadets;
5. Neuroticism will significantly predict religious tolerance among cadets;
6. Social intelligence dimensions and EPQ dimensions will significantly jointly predict religious tolerance among cadets.

Method

Participants: Two hundred and twenty-seven (227) police cadets of the Nigeria Police Academy were randomly selected to form the sample for this study. Their age ranges from 17 to 27 years, Mean = 23.01, Standard Deviation = 3.433, 80% males. This study employed a correlational design.

Measures: Participants were assessed using a measure on Religious Tolerance Index developed by Winseman (2004); which has five (5) (unidimensional) statements pertaining to the extent of toleration of others' religion. Essentially, it measures how individuals accept and interact with people which religious faiths are different from their own. Example of an item is: "I always treat people of other religious faiths with respect". Each statement was accompanied by response options ranging from one (1) "strongly disagree" to five (5) "strongly agree"; higher scores reflect more religious tolerance (Cronbach Alpha $\alpha = .71$). It has enjoyed good reliability coefficients in two previous studies (study one, $\alpha = .75$; study two, $\alpha = .77$), Mebu et. al (2016; 2017).

Social intelligence dimensions were measured with the Tromso Social Intelligence Scale. It is gender and age unbiased (Silvera et al. 2001). The scale has been well used and its validity and reliability extensively tested. The scale includes three 7-item subscales (dimensions) of social intelligence: social information processing ($\alpha = .80$), social skills ($\alpha = .79$), and social awareness ($\alpha = .72$). Each item describes a social ability or skill (e.g., "I can predict other people's behaviour"). Cadets rated on a 7-point scale by asking them how well each statement

describes them. The response pattern ranges from: “this statement describes me extremely poor (1) to this statement describes me extremely well (7)” (Cronbach Alpha $\alpha = .754$).

The Psychoticism and Neuroticism personality dimensions of the Eysenck Personality Questionnaire were assessed using the appropriate subscales of the personality questionnaire. The Psychoticism subscale has a total of twenty-five (25) items formatted as questions to be responded to as “YES” or “NO”. “Yes” stands for one (1) point and “No” stands for zero point (0). Of the twenty-five (25) items, twelve are meant to be reverse scored, that is answering “No” to the questions attracts one (1) point each. Examples of the items are: “Do people who drive carefully annoy you?” and “Would it upset you a lot to see a child or animal suffer?” The norm (mean) score in a Nigerian adult sample is 4.62 for male and 2.97 for female. In an English adult sample, the norm (mean) score is 3.78 for male and 2.63 for female. For the present study mean score is 3.8238. Whereas, the Neuroticism subscale has a total of twenty-three (23) items also formatted as questions to be responded to as “YES” or “NO”. “Yes” stands for one (1) point and “No” stands for zero (0) point. Here no item is reverse scored. Examples of items are: “Do you often feel life is very dull?” and “Are you an irritable person?” The norm (mean) score in a Nigerian adult sample is 6.43 for male and 8.42 for female. The norm (mean) score in an English adult sample is 9.83 for male and 12.74 for female. For the present study, mean score is 7.4846. Furthermore, Costa & McCrae (1995) and Furnham, Jackson, Forde, and Cotter (2001) have examined the reliability and validity of the EPQ (EPP) and found it acceptable.

Ethical consideration: We took into consideration the contentious nature of religion in the country; hence we did not obtain the demographic variables of religion and states of origin from the sample to free the researchers and readers from forming any bias.

Results

The result of this study on the influence of social information processing, social awareness, social skills, psychoticism and neuroticism on religious tolerance is presented in this section. Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics for the study’s variables of interest:

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of the Study’s Variables

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>Minimum</i>	<i>Maximum</i>	<i>Range</i>	<i>N</i>
<i>Social Information Processing</i>	33.2599	5.58746	.37085	13.00	42.00	29.00	227
<i>Social Awareness</i>	25.3260	5.39743	.35824	11.00	37.00	26.00	227
<i>Social Skills</i>	32.1718	5.59642	.37145	13.00	42.00	29.00	227
<i>Psychotic EPQ</i>	3.8238	2.83698	.18830	.00	18.00	18.00	227
<i>Neurotic EPQ</i>	7.4846	4.24509	.28176	.00	22.00	22.00	227
<i>Religious Tolerance</i>	17.5463	2.38382	.15822	4.00	20.00	16.00	227

SD- Standard Deviation, SE- Standard Error

In order to test the hypotheses of this study, a hierarchical multiple regressions test was conducted. Each dimension of social intelligence and EPQ were entered the regression equation; religious tolerance was regressed on each of the dimensions one after the other. That is, the

dimensions were used to independently and jointly predict religious tolerance. Table 2 shows the relevant statistics obtained after these analyses were performed. As seen on Table 2, R^2 is the amount or proportion of variation in the criterion variable (religious tolerance) accounted for by each step (hierarchy). Three of the dimensions showed significant independent prediction of religious tolerance (that is when other dimensions were held constant):

1. Social information processing: $\beta = .150$, $R^2 = .081$, $p = .03$, 95% CI for b [.006, .122]; social information process shares a positive relationship with and accounts for 8.1% of the variation in religious tolerance. This result supports hypothesis 1.
2. Social awareness: $\beta = -.260$, $\Delta R^2 = .001$, $p = .001$, 95% CI for b [-.180, -.050]; social awareness accounts for 1% variation and shares a negative relationship with religious tolerance. Hypothesis 2 is supported.
3. Social skills: $\beta = .397$, $\Delta R^2 = .102$, $p = .000$, 95% CI for b [.100, .238]; social skill accounts for 10.2% variation and shares a positive relationship with religious tolerance. Hypothesis 3 is supported.
4. Psychoticism: $\beta = -.118$, $\Delta R^2 = .012$, $p = .075$, 95% CI for b [-.208, .010]; psychoticism accounts for 1.2% variation and is negatively related to religious tolerance but it is not significant. Hypothesis 4 is not supported given the data obtained in this study.
5. Neuroticism: $\beta = .007$, $\Delta R^2 = .000$, $p = .916$, 95% CI for b [-.072, .080]; neuroticism accounts for no variation in religious tolerance. Hypothesis 5 is not supported by the data gathered in this study.
6. Lastly, the last step (5) of the hierarchy where all the predictors (dimensions) were introduced into the equation accounts for the most variation in religious tolerance, $R^2 = .196$, $F(5, 221) = 10.750$, $p = .000$. Their combination accounts for 19.6% of the variation in religious tolerance, this proportion is the highest variation of all the steps and it is statistically significant. Therefore, this result supports hypothesis 6.

Table 2: Result of Hierarchical Multiple Regression of Religious Tolerance on the Dimensions of Social Intelligence and EPQ

<i>Hierarchy</i>	<i>Step 1</i>		<i>Step 2</i>		<i>Step 3</i>		<i>Step 4</i>		<i>Step 5</i>		<i>p-value equal</i>	<i>Confidence Interval 95% for b</i>		<i>Correlation Coefficients</i>	
	<i>b</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>b</i>	β	<i>b</i>	β	<i>B</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>B</i>	β		<i>LL</i>	<i>UL</i>	<i>Zero-Order Correlation</i>	<i>Partial Correlation</i>
<i>Social Information Processing</i>	.121	.284	.125	.294	.069	.163	.063	.149	.064	.150	.030	.006	.122	.284	.146
<i>Social Awareness</i>			-.016	-.037	-.107	-.242	-.115	-.261	-.115	-.260	.001	-.180	-.050	.038	-.228
<i>Social Skills</i>					.178	.418	.168	.395	.169	.397	.000	.100	.238	.351	.310
<i>Psychoticism</i>							-.098	-.117	-.099	-.118	.075	-.208	.010	-.209	-.120
<i>Neuroticism</i>									.004	.007	.916	-.072	.080	-.155	.007
<i>Standard Error of Estimate</i>	2.29053		2.29404		2.16790		2.15720		2.16202						
<i>R²</i>	.081		.082		.184		.196		.196						
ΔR^2	.081		.001		.102		.012		.000						
<i>F-ratio</i>	19.784		10.018		16.753		13.949		10.750						
ΔF -ratio	19.784**		.313		27.824**		3.218		.011						

Standardized coefficient Beta- β Unstandardized coefficient- b Durbin Watson Statistic = 1.938 ** p = .000 LL – Lower Limit UL – Upper Limit

Discussion

The findings of the study- which sought to examine the influence of social intelligence dimensions and EPQ dimensions on religious tolerance- show that the combination of dimensions did predict the criterion, that is, the joint prediction of religious tolerance by the five predictors was significant and this contributed to the variations in religious tolerance, such that the portion of the variation explained is the greatest compared to any other combination of the predictor variables. In addition, social skill independently accounted for the highest variation in religious tolerance compared with other dimensions and the direction of this relationship is positive, signifying that the more social skills a cadet possesses the more he/she can tolerate the religion of others. Being socially adept entails making compromise and concession with individuals, social groups and persons of other religious standpoint for peaceful co-existence; ultimately, we all become the better for it as we achieve a desired non-violent and serene society. The possession of social skills will bring about this.

Social information processing also explained some portion of the variation in religious tolerance and shared a positive relationship with religious tolerance. This implies that if a cadet engages appropriate social information processing, he/she is better able to tolerate others' religious creed. An individual's thoughtfulness goes a long way to avert rash and impulsive actions which could include non-tolerance of others' divergent religious views. Adequate consideration and pondering on the cause and effect of destructive social actions reduces the chances of either endorsing it or engaging in it. Intuitively, one should think that social intelligence components should positively relate to religious tolerance, that is, high social intelligence should produce more tolerance for others' religions. But this seems not to be the case.

The extant literature supports the independence of these components of social intelligence (Silvera et. al, 2001; Riggio & Reichard, 2008; Grieve & Mahar 2013), but the composite social intelligence positively predicted religious tolerance (Mebu et. al, 2017) hence, it could be envisaged that all the dimensions ought to be positively related to the criterion-religious tolerance. On the contrary the dimension of social awareness showed a negative relationship with religious tolerance. Simply, what this association suggests is that the more a cadet is socially aware the less toleration of others' religions he/she shows.

Social awareness is the development of social (ethnic, religious, political, etc.) discernment and the evolution of abilities to grasp and bear in mind others' social viewpoints (Selman, 2003). And still in the reasoning of Selman (2003), it appears that this fact presents individuals with social and moral dilemma that forces them to make complicated choices about incompatible principles, and allegiances arise in their lives as a result. Social awareness brings to our consciousness peoples' choices; worldviews and belief system that vary from ours and it probably creates a bias. This is exactly what the study's result suggests. Social awareness, rather than bringing us together, tears us further apart.

It seems that what an individual does with his/her understanding and perception of others' religious belief is more subjective than objective. Reasonably, the component of social awareness (being a part of social intelligence) ought to make us come to terms with the religious views and opinions of others, which should translate into the accommodation of same, but the reverse seems to be the case.

Earlier studies have reported mixed and contradicting results about EPQ personality dimensions and religiosity measures. Egan et al. (2004) found no meaningful support that an association exists between psychoticism and religiosity, and even if there is any it occurs because

the sample is from a student population. Researches have however shown a negative relationship between psychoticism and intrinsic religious orientation (Maltby et. al, 1995). Psychoticism has been especially found to be negatively related to many pleasant religious variables (Hills et al., 2004; Mebu, et. al, 2016). When the result and findings in this study was observed, the bivariate correlation between psychoticism and religious tolerance was negative and significant (see zero-order correlation coefficient between psychoticism and religious tolerance in Table 2; and even the β (standardized coefficient) seems to show a meaningful negative relationship at p -value = .075); this is consistent with the findings of Mebu et al. (2016) and Fearn, Lewis & Francis (2003). But, after partialling out or controlling for the effect of other variables in this study, this relationship becomes insignificant. Anticipating that this could be the case Mebu et al. (2016) earlier suggested that the future study should be geared towards examining the role other factors could play while explaining tolerance of other peoples' religions. This study's results reflects this possibility.

The neuroticism dimension of the EPQ showed close to zero correlation with religious tolerance when the influences of other dimensions were controlled for. Before then in the preliminary statistical analysis neuroticism showed a significant bivariate correlation coefficient with religious tolerance (see Table 2) and this is consistent with what was found by Mebu et. al. (2016) and Francis (1992) since they only considered the relationship between the two variables. Most researches on relationship between EPQ and other religiosity variables seem not to look at the influence of other related variables that may suppress, mediate or moderate their association. This probably explains why the relationship is non-existence when considered along with other variables. The suspicion is that psychoticism mediates the relationship between neuroticism and religious tolerance. This is because both psychoticism and neuroticism share significant relationships when considered independently with religious tolerance but when the two are used as predictors of religious tolerance, the once significant path between neuroticism and tolerance tends towards zero. This is a condition for a mediational process. Future research should be directed at gathering data to test this idea.

Lastly, a factor (variable) cannot be solely responsible for a change in another variable. Therefore, the present study also attempted to determine the combined influence of all dimensions on changes observed in religious tolerance, in addition to the independent influence of each dimension. From the result obtained, the dimensions substantially explained the variation that is observed in religious tolerance, meaning that they are important behaviours to consider when we desire to expound the criterion variable. Individuals with more of social information processing abilities, more social skills and less social awareness tolerate other people's religious dispositions better. Likewise, to a little extent psychotic and neurotic trait predispose to religious intolerance. It is essential to also point out that these factors did not explain all the variations in religious tolerance, suggesting that several other factors can be explored relative to the criterion. In addition, the study's design limits and restricts cause and effect inference and the nature of the criterion could raise ethical questions if it is subjected to quasi-experimental venture.

The implication and conclusion of the study indicates that the presence and absence of these components of social intelligence are prerequisites for individuals saddled with the responsibility of providing leadership in any sector of private and governmental set-up. For instance, individuals who can continually engage in dialogue irrespective of prevailing grievances and perceived social anomaly, those who can think through the implications of their actions or/and inactions to the nation's well-being ought to be urged to vie for governance. While, characters that are aware or overly conscious of the issues (such as ethnicity, socio-

cultural background, political affiliations and religious inclinations) that cause a rift in our national life thereby exploiting the differences (rather than focusing on the strength that unity provides) and those having psychotic and neurotic tendencies should be dissuaded from aspiring to leadership status and governance.

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Influence of Social Intelligence and EPQ Personality Dimensions on Religious Tolerance among Cadets of Nigeria Police Academy

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Abstract

Toleration of another's religious creed is a sine qua non for good leadership. Similarly, certain personality traits facilitate or hinder the expression of good leadership qualities. The aim of this study is to isolate a few established personality traits believed to be associated with leadership qualities and determine if they are related to tolerating others' religions.

Specifically, religious tolerance was regressed on the dimensions of Social Intelligence and that of EPQ among the police cadets (N= 227, Age range = 17 to 27 years, Mean = 23.01, Standard Deviation =3.433, 80% males). First, Social intelligence and EPQ were distinct (dimensions) variables viz.: Social information processing (SIP); Social awareness (SA); Social skills (SS); Psychoticism; and Neuroticism. Secondly, the result of hierarchical multiple regression showed that some of both dimensions significantly predicted and account for variations in religious tolerance (Social Information Processing: $\beta = .150$, $R^2 = .081$, $p = .03$; Social Awareness: $\beta = -.260$, $\Delta R^2 = .001$, $p = .001$; Social Skills: $\beta = .397$, $\Delta R^2 = .102$, $p = .000$; Psychoticism: $\beta = -.117$, $\Delta R^2 = .012$, $p = .075$; Neuroticism: $\beta = .007$, $\Delta R^2 = .00$, $p = .916$). On the premise that good leadership entails many behavioural traits, we deduce that these dimensions are requisite to leadership qualities and have relationship with religious tolerance.

It is recommended that personnel who aspire to police leadership, and individuals in general should be well observed and screened for psychotic and neurotic tendencies to get things right with governance.

Keywords: Social information processing, social skills, social awareness, neuroticism, psychoticism, social intelligence, EPQ, religious tolerance, police cadets, leadership

Introduction

The Nigerian national goal is to overcome religious conflict by ushering in leaders must be sensitive and tolerant enough to bridge the gap among the various religious groups. Such leaders should be able to accommodate the diverse religious creed and be a role model towards the toleration of Nigerians' religious inclinations is desirable. Unfortunately, Nigeria being a pluralistic state has experienced her own fair own share of religious skirmishes.

It is no secret that religion creates its own tension in the country. Soyinka (2017) warned that "if we do not tame religion it will kill Nigeria". Such is the seriousness of the religious conundrum that is being faced in the country. Sampson (2012) pointed out that religious violence due to intolerance of others' religious beliefs camouflages as ethno-religious conflict and a lot of committees and panels of inquiry were set up to investigate both the cause and effects of these

crises, and to proffer solution to avert same occurring in future. It will appear that leadership lacks the political will to implement the recommendations; a sensitive leader would have done otherwise and mandated the security and judicial agencies to put into effect these proposals.

Research has shown that there were numerous qualities associated with a leader either in an organization or within any group for that matter. Leadership qualities were examined in the educational sector (Amanchukwu, Stanley & Ololube, 2015); in business organizations (Caligiuri, & Tarique, 2012); multicultural diverse groups (Chuang 2013); and in political groups (Gaffney, 2001). Some of these characteristics are being displayed by a leader depending on the objectives to be achieved in a given situation within a group. Leaders give directions and take initiatives for the well-being of any group they lead. These leadership qualities are needed to combat social problems (Cleveland-Innes, 2012), one of which could be religious intolerance. The question is which leadership group is mostly required to show religious unbiasedness and detachment while carrying out their leadership duties? Police personnel is expected to play leadership roles while discharging their constitutional assignment of law enforcement and crime prevention and detection. The Police are saddled with the task of “protecting lives and properties; employed for the prevention and detection of crime; responsible for the apprehension of offenders; and the preservation of law and order; and the due enforcement of all laws and regulations with which they are directly charged, and shall perform such military duties within and without Nigeria as may be required of them by, or under the authority of this or any other act” (Police Acts, 1979, Part II Section 4). These responsibilities require a great amount of toleration of citizens’ religious creeds and practices more so in a secular state such as Nigeria.

A few personality dispositions were identified (Mebu, Dauda, & Oluwafemi 2016; Mebu, Abu, Igboanusi-Ossai & Oluwafemi, 2017) but their sub-elements are yet to be explored. The present study adds to and complements these findings by introducing the dimensions of social intelligence viz. social information process, social skills and social awareness; and the EPQ personality factors of psychoticism and neuroticism as behaviours that are associated with the religious tolerance level of individuals in leadership position such as police personnel- specifically those still in training and waiting to be commissioned. This is informed by the popular parlance, “*Catch them young*”.

The first goal of this study is to delineate these personality dimensions and factors, and establish their distinctiveness from each other among the sample of the study. In other words, there are five different variables which are believed to be independent of one another; and the second goal is that their respective independent and collective influence on religious tolerance is being examined among the police cadets. Police cadets form the population of interest for this investigation.

Dimensions of Social Intelligence

Social intelligence is a pervasive construct which has been identified as a variable with several sub-elements (e.g. Marlowe, 1986; Goleman, 2007; Silvera, Martinussen, Dahl, 2001). However, researches demonstrate that these sub-elements vary and can be quantified and tapped from different orientations and perspectives (Vasil'ová & Baumgartner 2005). Social intelligence is the ability to act wisely in human relations- “an ability to understand people and cooperate with them” (Thorndike, 1920). This definition seems to be the simplest that has been tendered. The literature also varies about the definition and measurement of social intelligence (Vasil'ová & Baumgartner 2005).

Among these definitions are: the ability to understand other people and how they will react to different social situation (Silvera, Martinussen, Dahl, 2001); an individual’s fund of knowledge about social world (Kihlstrom & Cantor, 2000); the skills and facilitators that

determine how effectively we understand and express ourselves, understand others and the social context, to interact with other people and cope with daily demands (Bar-On, 2006; Barnes & Sternberg, 1989). This study adopts the dimensions of social intelligence as conceptualized by Silvera et al. (2001) and assesses it as such. These three sub-dimensions include: Social Information Processing- the ability to read and predict the behaviours of others; Social Awareness- being conscious of people's choices, comportment and behaving as they would expect; and Social Skills- the ability to interact effectively with others, being able to engage novel social settings and having a sociable and amiable disposition. The components of social intelligence were distinct entities (e.g. Vasil'ová & Baumgartner 2005; Grieve & Mahar 2013, Marlowe, 1986; Goleman, 2007; Silvera, Martinussen, & Dahl, 2001; Riggio & Reichard, 2008). In fact, the dimension of social skills has been employed to solely represent social intelligence (Riggio & Reichard, 2008; Cuadra-Peralta, Veloso-Besio, Iribaren & Pinto, 2017). The literature clearly supports that these dimensions are different entities.

Social awareness is the growth of interpersonal understanding and the development of capacities to comprehend and consider other's social perspectives (Selman, 2003). It presents social and moral dilemma that forces us to make complex decisions about conflicting principles, and loyalties occur in all our lives as a result (Selman, 2003). However, it is being approached, social awareness makes us conscious of peoples' choices, worldviews and belief systems. What an individual does with this understanding could be a subjective matter. Intuitively, the component of social awareness ought to make us come to terms with the religious views and opinions of others, but do we have any idea of what this knowledge will translate to in terms of accommodating those biases? It is hoped that some light will be shed on this question.

Social information processing, as a factor, was implicated in aggressive behaviour. Dodge & Crick (1990), using a children sample, pointed out that our behavioural response to problematic social stimulus (maybe having to interact with another individual with a different religious creed and values) is a function of five steps of social information processing: encoding of social cues, interpretation of social cues, response search, response evaluation, and enactment. Skillful processing at each step is hypothesized to lead to competent performance within a situation, whereas biased or deficient processing is hypothesized to lead to deviant social behaviour; and an adept execution or inappropriate management of such social stimulus has been found to predict individual differences in aggressive behaviour- religious intolerance is a form of unaccommodating and aggressive behaviour. In addition, Dodge & Rabiner (2004) suggested that social information processing could hamper or facilitate moral development. It has been submitted that all religion assists in moral development, hence similar tenets are expected of most religions. This ought to engender toleration among religious faithful and practitioners. Research has also strongly linked competent social information processing patterns with pro-social behaviour (Mayeux & Cillessen, 2003; Nelson & Crick, 1999) – religious tolerance is a form of pro-social behaviour.

Social skill is the capacity to relate and intermingle successfully with others, being able to fit into new societal situations and having a gregarious and friendly personality; and confidence in ones' social performing abilities. Training in social skills has reduced disruptive and destructive behaviours in autistic children (Golzari, Alamdarloo & Moradi, 2015; Hotton & Coles, 2016). It has also been shown to facilitate academic performance (Comedis, 2014); and helps in negotiations in the labour market (Deming, 2017).

Dimensions of EPQ

Psychoticism is seen as reflecting behaviours such as tough-mindedness, non-conformity, inconsideration, recklessness, hostility, anger, impulsiveness, aggressiveness, depressiveness and

criminality (Eysenck, 1992). Egan, Kroll, Carey, Johnson & Erickson (2004) posit that there are no significant evidences that a relationship exists between psychoticism and religiosity, and even if any exists it is since the sample is from a student population. There had been reported relationship between psychoticism and religiosity (Eysenck, Eysenck & Barrett, 1985; Allport & Ross 1967), though without much empirical backing. Studies have however shown a negative relationship between psychoticism and intrinsic religious orientation (Maltby, Talley, Cooper & Francis, 1995). Psychoticism has been especially found to be negatively related to many pleasant religious variables (Hills, Francis, Argyle & Jackson, 2004; Mebu et. al, 2016). Specifically, Mebu et. al (2016) found a significant negative relationship between psychoticism and religious tolerance in a sample of prospective cadets. This study attempts to examine its relative influence among other variables in a sample of ASP police cadets.

The EPQ dimension of neuroticism constitutes traits such as being moody, anxious, worried, fearful, angry, frustrated, envious, jealous, guilty, depressed, and lonely (Thompson, 2008). Bech, Lunde, & Møller (2012) recommended that all the items on the EPQ Neuroticism dimension should be considered symptoms as informed by Eysenck & Eysenck (1969) observation about the scoring format of the questionnaire. Hills & Argyle (1998) observed relatively significant low neuroticism scores among church (members) goers compared to non-church (members) goers. This suggests that churchgoers are less neurotic than non-churchgoers. A similar result was obtained by Taylor & MacDonald (1999); they found that neuroticism scores on the BFI were less for those with religious affiliation compared with those without religious affiliation among a sample of around 1100 Canadian students, implying that those with healthy attachment to their religious beliefs are less neurotic compared to those who are loosely and unwholesomely connected to their religious ideas. In contrast to this finding, Singh & Gupta (1996) found that neuroticism was positively associated with religious values among a sample of Indians. Religious Tolerance is a positive religious behaviour and should be associated with balanced emotional indices and communal acumen. Therefore, we expect fewer neurotic scores among more tolerant individuals. Mebu et. al (2016) gave support for the position when they observed a negative correlation between neuroticism and religious tolerance among intending police cadets. Albeit, without the consideration of other factors, this research explored the extent of this relationship alongside social intelligence measures.

This study tested the following hypotheses:

1. Social information processing will significantly predict religious tolerance among cadets;
2. Social awareness will significantly predict religious tolerance among cadets;
3. Social skill will significantly predict religious tolerance among cadets;
4. Psychoticism will significantly predict religious tolerance among cadets;
5. Neuroticism will significantly predict religious tolerance among cadets;
6. Social intelligence dimensions and EPQ dimensions will significantly jointly predict religious tolerance among cadets.

Method

Participants: Two hundred and twenty-seven (227) police cadets of the Nigeria Police Academy were randomly selected to form the sample for this study. Their age ranges from 17 to 27 years, Mean = 23.01, Standard Deviation = 3.433, 80% males. This study employed a correlational design.

Measures: Participants were assessed using a measure on Religious Tolerance Index developed by Winseman (2004); which has five (5) (unidimensional) statements pertaining to the extent of toleration of others' religion. Essentially, it measures how individuals accept and interact with

people which religious faiths are different from their own. Example of an item is: “I always treat people of other religious faiths with respect”. Each statement was accompanied by response options ranging from one (1) “strongly disagree” to five (5) “strongly agree”; higher scores reflect more religious tolerance (Cronbach Alpha $\alpha = .71$). It has enjoyed good reliability coefficients in two previous studies (study one, $\alpha = .75$; study two, $\alpha = .77$), Mebu et. al (2016; 2017).

Social intelligence dimensions were measured with the Tromso Social Intelligence Scale. It is gender and age unbiased (Silvera et al. 2001). The scale has been well used and its validity and reliability extensively tested. The scale includes three 7-item subscales (dimensions) of social intelligence: social information processing ($\alpha = .80$), social skills ($\alpha = .79$), and social awareness ($\alpha = .72$). Each item describes a social ability or skill (e.g., “I can predict other people’s behaviour”). Cadets rated on a 7-point scale by asking them how well each statement describes them. The response pattern ranges from: “this statement describes me extremely poor (1) to this statement describes me extremely well (7)” (Cronbach Alpha $\alpha = .754$).

The Psychoticism and Neuroticism personality dimensions of the Eysenck Personality Questionnaire were assessed using the appropriate subscales of the personality questionnaire. The Psychoticism subscale has a total of twenty-five (25) items formatted as questions to be responded to as “YES” or “NO”. “Yes” stands for one (1) point and “No” stands for zero point (0). Of the twenty-five (25) items, twelve are meant to be reverse scored, that is answering “No” to the questions attracts one (1) point each. Examples of the items are: “Do people who drive carefully annoy you?” and “Would it upset you a lot to see a child or animal suffer?” The norm (mean) score in a Nigerian adult sample is 4.62 for male and 2.97 for female. In an English adult sample, the norm (mean) score is 3.78 for male and 2.63 for female. For the present study mean score is 3.8238. Whereas, the Neuroticism subscale has a total of twenty-three (23) items also formatted as questions to be responded to as “YES” or “NO”. “Yes” stands for one (1) point and “No” stands for zero (0) point. Here no item is reverse scored. Examples of items are: “Do you often feel life is very dull?” and “Are you an irritable person?” The norm (mean) score in a Nigerian adult sample is 6.43 for male and 8.42 for female. The norm (mean) score in an English adult sample is 9.83 for male and 12.74 for female. For the present study, mean score is 7.4846. Furthermore, Costa & McCrae (1995) and Furnham, Jackson, Forde, and Cotter (2001) have examined the reliability and validity of the EPQ (EPP) and found it acceptable.

Ethical consideration: We took into consideration the contentious nature of religion in the country; hence we did not obtain the demographic variables of religion and states of origin from the sample to free the researchers and readers from forming any bias.

Results

The result of this study on the influence of social information processing, social awareness, social skills, psychoticism and neuroticism on religious tolerance is presented in this section. Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics for the study’s variables of interest:

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of the Study’s Variables

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>Minimum</i>	<i>Maximum</i>	<i>Range</i>	<i>N</i>
<i>Social Information Processing</i>	33.2599	5.58746	.37085	13.00	42.00	29.00	227
<i>Social Awareness</i>	25.3260	5.39743	.35824	11.00	37.00	26.00	227
<i>Social Skills</i>	32.1718	5.59642	.37145	13.00	42.00	29.00	227
<i>Psychotic EPQ</i>	3.8238	2.83698	.18830	.00	18.00	18.00	227
<i>Neurotic EPQ</i>	7.4846	4.24509	.28176	.00	22.00	22.00	227
<i>Religious Tolerance</i>	17.5463	2.38382	.15822	4.00	20.00	16.00	227

SD- Standard Deviation, SE- Standard Error

In order to test the hypotheses of this study, a hierarchical multiple regressions test was conducted. Each dimension of social intelligence and EPQ were entered the regression equation; religious tolerance was regressed on each of the dimensions one after the other. That is, the dimensions were used to independently and jointly predict religious tolerance. Table 2 shows the relevant statistics obtained after these analyses were performed. As seen on Table 2, R² is the amount or proportion of variation in the criterion variable (religious tolerance) accounted for by each step (hierarchy). Three of the dimensions showed significant independent prediction of religious tolerance (that is when other dimensions were held constant):

1. Social information processing: $\beta = .150$, $R^2 = .081$, $p = .03$, 95% CI for b [.006, .122]; social information process shares a positive relationship with and accounts for 8.1% of the variation in religious tolerance. This result supports hypothesis 1.
2. Social awareness: $\beta = -.260$, $\Delta R^2 = .001$, $p = .001$, 95% CI for b [-.180, -.050]; social awareness accounts for 1% variation and shares a negative relationship with religious tolerance. Hypothesis 2 is supported.
3. Social skills: $\beta = .397$, $\Delta R^2 = .102$, $p = .000$, 95% CI for b [.100, .238]; social skill accounts for 10.2% variation and shares a positive relationship with religious tolerance. Hypothesis 3 is supported.
4. Psychoticism: $\beta = -.118$, $\Delta R^2 = .012$, $p = .075$, 95% CI for b [-.208, .010]; psychoticism accounts for 1.2% variation and is negatively related to religious tolerance but it is not significant. Hypothesis 4 is not supported given the data obtained in this study.
5. Neuroticism: $\beta = .007$, $\Delta R^2 = .000$, $p = .916$, 95% CI for b [-.072, .080]; neuroticism accounts for no variation in religious tolerance. Hypothesis 5 is not supported by the data gathered in this study.
6. Lastly, the last step (5) of the hierarchy where all the predictors (dimensions) were introduced into the equation accounts for the most variation in religious tolerance, $R^2 = .196$, $F(5, 221) = 10.750$, $p = .000$. Their combination accounts for 19.6% of the variation in

religious tolerance, this proportion is the highest variation of all the steps and it is statistically significant. Therefore, this result supports hypothesis 6.

Table 2: Result of Hierarchical Multiple Regression of Religious Tolerance on the Dimensions of Social Intelligence and EPQ

<i>Hierarchy</i>	<i>Step 1</i>		<i>Step 2</i>		<i>Step 3</i>		<i>Step 4</i>		<i>Step 5</i>		<i>p-value equal</i>	<i>Confidence Interval 95% for b</i>		<i>Correlation Coefficients</i>	
	<i>b</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>b</i>	β	<i>b</i>	β	<i>B</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>B</i>	β		<i>LL</i>	<i>UL</i>	<i>Zero-Order Correlation</i>	<i>Partial Correlation</i>
<i>Social Information Processing</i>	.121	.284	.125	.294	.069	.163	.063	.149	.064	.150	.030	.006	.122	.284	.146
<i>Social Awareness</i>			-.016	-.037	-.107	-.242	-.115	-.261	-.115	-.260	.001	-.180	-.050	.038	-.228
<i>Social Skills</i>					.178	.418	.168	.395	.169	.397	.000	.100	.238	.351	.310
<i>Psychoticism</i>							-.098	-.117	-.099	-.118	.075	-.208	.010	-.209	-.120
<i>Neuroticism</i>									.004	.007	.916	-.072	.080	-.155	.007
<i>Standard Error of Estimate</i>	2.29053		2.29404		2.16790		2.15720		2.16202						
<i>R²</i>	.081		.082		.184		.196		.196						
ΔR^2	.081		.001		.102		.012		.000						
<i>F-ratio</i>	19.784		10.018		16.753		13.949		10.750						
ΔF -ratio	19.784**		.313		27.824**		3.218		.011						

Standardized coefficient Beta- β Unstandardized coefficient- b Durbin Watson Statistic = 1.938 ** p = .000 LL – Lower Limit UL – Upper Limit

Discussion

The findings of the study- which sought to examine the influence of social intelligence dimensions and EPQ dimensions on religious tolerance- show that the combination of dimensions did predict the criterion, that is, the joint prediction of religious tolerance by the five predictors was significant and this contributed to the variations in religious tolerance, such that the portion of the variation explained is the greatest compared to any other combination of the predictor variables. In addition, social skill independently accounted for the highest variation in religious tolerance compared with other dimensions and the direction of this relationship is positive, signifying that the more social skills a cadet possesses the more he/she can tolerate the religion of others. Being socially adept entails making compromise and concession with individuals, social groups and persons of other religious standpoint for peaceful co-existence; ultimately, we all become the better for it as we achieve a desired non-violent and serene society. The possession of social skills will bring about this.

Social information processing also explained some portion of the variation in religious tolerance and shared a positive relationship with religious tolerance. This implies that if a cadet engages appropriate social information processing, he/she is better able to tolerate others' religious creed. An individual's thoughtfulness goes a long way to avert rash and impulsive actions which could include non-tolerance of others' divergent religious views. Adequate consideration and pondering on the cause and effect of destructive social actions reduces the chances of either endorsing it or engaging in it. Intuitively, one should think that social intelligence components should positively relate to religious tolerance, that is, high social intelligence should produce more tolerance for others' religions. But this seems not to be the case.

The extant literature supports the independence of these components of social intelligence (Silvera et. al, 2001; Riggio & Reichard, 2008; Grieve & Mahar 2013), but the composite social intelligence positively predicted religious tolerance (Mebu et. al, 2017) hence, it could be envisaged that all the dimensions ought to be positively related to the criterion-religious tolerance. On the contrary the dimension of social awareness showed a negative relationship with religious tolerance. Simply, what this association suggests is that the more a cadet is socially aware the less toleration of others' religions he/she shows.

Social awareness is the development of social (ethnic, religious, political, etc.) discernment and the evolution of abilities to grasp and bear in mind others' social viewpoints (Selman, 2003). And still in the reasoning of Selman (2003), it appears that this fact presents individuals with social and moral dilemma that forces them to make complicated choices about incompatible principles, and allegiances arise in their lives as a result. Social awareness brings to our consciousness peoples' choices; worldviews and belief system that vary from ours and it probably creates a bias. This is exactly what the study's result suggests. Social awareness, rather than bringing us together, tears us further apart.

It seems that what an individual does with his/her understanding and perception of others' religious belief is more subjective than objective. Reasonably, the component of social awareness (being a part of social intelligence) ought to make us come to terms with the religious views and opinions of others, which should translate into the accommodation of same, but the reverse seems to be the case.

Earlier studies have reported mixed and contradicting results about EPQ personality dimensions and religiosity measures. Egan et al. (2004) found no meaningful support that an association exists between psychoticism and religiosity, and even if there is any it occurs because

the sample is from a student population. Researches have however shown a negative relationship between psychoticism and intrinsic religious orientation (Maltby et. al, 1995). Psychoticism has been especially found to be negatively related to many pleasant religious variables (Hills et al., 2004; Mebu, et. al, 2016). When the result and findings in this study was observed, the bivariate correlation between psychoticism and religious tolerance was negative and significant (see zero-order correlation coefficient between psychoticism and religious tolerance in Table 2; and even the β (standardized coefficient) seems to show a meaningful negative relationship at p -value = .075); this is consistent with the findings of Mebu et al. (2016) and Fearn, Lewis & Francis (2003). But, after partialling out or controlling for the effect of other variables in this study, this relationship becomes insignificant. Anticipating that this could be the case Mebu et al. (2016) earlier suggested that the future study should be geared towards examining the role other factors could play while explaining tolerance of other peoples' religions. This study's results reflects this possibility.

The neuroticism dimension of the EPQ showed close to zero correlation with religious tolerance when the influences of other dimensions were controlled for. Before then in the preliminary statistical analysis neuroticism showed a significant bivariate correlation coefficient with religious tolerance (see Table 2) and this is consistent with what was found by Mebu et. al. (2016) and Francis (1992) since they only considered the relationship between the two variables. Most researches on relationship between EPQ and other religiosity variables seem not to look at the influence of other related variables that may suppress, mediate or moderate their association. This probably explains why the relationship is non-existence when considered along with other variables. The suspicion is that psychoticism mediates the relationship between neuroticism and religious tolerance. This is because both psychoticism and neuroticism share significant relationships when considered independently with religious tolerance but when the two are used as predictors of religious tolerance, the once significant path between neuroticism and tolerance tends towards zero. This is a condition for a mediational process. Future research should be directed at gathering data to test this idea.

Lastly, a factor (variable) cannot be solely responsible for a change in another variable. Therefore, the present study also attempted to determine the combined influence of all dimensions on changes observed in religious tolerance, in addition to the independent influence of each dimension. From the result obtained, the dimensions substantially explained the variation that is observed in religious tolerance, meaning that they are important behaviours to consider when we desire to expound the criterion variable. Individuals with more of social information processing abilities, more social skills and less social awareness tolerate other people's religious dispositions better. Likewise, to a little extent psychotic and neurotic trait predispose to religious intolerance. It is essential to also point out that these factors did not explain all the variations in religious tolerance, suggesting that several other factors can be explored relative to the criterion. In addition, the study's design limits and restricts cause and effect inference and the nature of the criterion could raise ethical questions if it is subjected to quasi-experimental venture.

The implication and conclusion of the study indicates that the presence and absence of these components of social intelligence are prerequisites for individuals saddled with the responsibility of providing leadership in any sector of private and governmental set-up. For instance, individuals who can continually engage in dialogue irrespective of prevailing grievances and perceived social anomaly, those who can think through the implications of their actions or/and inactions to the nation's well-being ought to be urged to vie for governance. While, characters that are aware or overly conscious of the issues (such as ethnicity, socio-

cultural background, political affiliations and religious inclinations) that cause a rift in our national life thereby exploiting the differences (rather than focusing on the strength that unity provides) and those having psychotic and neurotic tendencies should be dissuaded from aspiring to leadership status and governance.

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Gender and self-perception predictors of adolescents' body appreciation in Ibadan, Nigeria: Implications for positive psychology and counselling practice

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Abstract

Body image has been conceptualised and assessed almost solely in terms of its negative dimensions like negative body image, body image disturbances, body image dissatisfaction, body shame and body preoccupation. However, a new wave of positive psychology seeks to put body image in positive perspectives. This view borders on positive body image, body satisfaction and body appreciation- in terms of acceptance and respect. The present study therefore, investigated the effects of gender and self-perception factors on body appreciation among adolescents in Ibadan-North Local Government Area, Ibadan, Nigeria.

The study adopted the descriptive research design of survey type. One hundred and seventy-seven male and female senior secondary school students were selected using the Multistage sampling technique. Data for the research were generated with the use of a questionnaire which contained the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale, the Self-Concept Clarity Scale and the Body Appreciation Scale. Data were analysed using the Pearson's product moment correlation and multiple regression analysis at 0.05 level of significance.

There was a significant relationship between body appreciation and self-esteem, as well as between body appreciation and self-concept of in-school adolescents. But there was no significant relationship between body appreciation and gender of in-school adolescents. All the three independent variables had a composite effect on body appreciation of the participants. A relative effect of the three independent variables on body appreciation of in-school adolescents was found. Self-esteem had the most effect while gender had the least effect on body appreciation of senior secondary school adolescents. The findings of the study certainly have implications for positive psychology counselling practice.

Keywords: Self-esteem, self-concept, body appreciation, senior secondary school adolescents

Introduction

Adolescence is a period with significant bodily changes to which a teenager has to continually adjust. One of the developmental tasks of adolescents is accepting their physique, but unfortunately, overcoming this task has been greatly negatively influenced by some of the present time's beliefs and media messages. The thought of ideal, flawless, perfect, and socially-adopted standard of beauty has been observed to be accepted erroneously leaving youngsters in a more confused world than ever. Thus, the developmental task of accepting one's physique might have been termed insurmountable at the period of adolescence. According to Grogan (2008), the context of body appreciation facilitates a focus of attention on the physical body which is analyzed, compared and evaluated against the appearance of peers and the social norms. Body appreciation, as "a person's perceptions, thoughts and feelings about own body", becomes one of the central focuses of adolescents (Grogan, 2008). According to Grogan (2008), the perceptive dimension refers to the mental representation of the physical body, while thoughts and emotions

contribute to the behavioural disposition in terms of attitude. Regarding the attitude toward body, researchers distinguish between appraisal of appearance (satisfaction/dissatisfaction) and the importance placed on appearance (Cash & Pruzinski, 2002).

Body appreciation is an aspect of positive, favourable satisfying body image. Body appreciation among adolescents is one of the major emerging issues that clinical/counselling psychologists, mental health professionals, and researchers have turned their attention to. This is because perhaps the body is the first thing perceived in social interactions, and so has a lot of influence on the social acceptance of people. It is observed that people's bodies are always in the limelight and may be open to other people's evaluations and approval. The perception, acceptance and appreciation of adolescents' bodies often are based on what other people think, since adolescents are still struggling with self-identity and ego formation. Beauty and physical attractiveness have always been highly valued human attributes, assumed to be connected with happiness, intelligence, and success (Rennels, 2012). Most of today's postindustrial societies share this mindset, and the ongoing obsession with physical appearance might be more intense than ever. The "appearance culture" (Jones, Vigfusdottir & Lee, 2004), the ceaseless flow of messages regarding how people should and should not look, exerts constant pressure.

Adolescents, who are at a stage in life in which their bodies, minds, and social lives are changing dramatically, are particularly vulnerable to the messages conveyed by appearance culture (Wertheim & Paxton, 2011). Body appreciation or positive body image is crucial for the development of the body self-respect and general self-respect (Pokrajac-Bulian & Zivcic-Becirevic, 2005). Body image represents a psychological construct with cognitive, behavioural and perceptual dimensions, including attitudes regarding people's own bodies (Thompson, Heinberg, Altabe & Tantleff-Dunn, 1999). Body appreciation is an important aspect of self-representation and self-evaluation during adolescence. Although body appreciation is a multidimensional construct, it is most frequently defined as the degree of satisfaction with one's current physical self (size, shape, general appearance (Cash & Deagle, 1997). The importance of body appreciation is evident in its relationship to risk status for eating disorders, depression, and low self-esteem (McCabe & Ricciardelli, 2001). Body image concerns may be manifested in many ways, ranging from a mild preference for other body characteristics, to pathological body appreciation disturbances such as eating disorders or pathological muscle dysmorphia (Pope et al. 2005). In addition, body appreciation concerns can be about the appearance of the total body (e.g., shape, muscularity, weight, or size) or, alternatively, about specific characteristics or parts of the body (e.g., facial characteristics, hair, body parts, fitness, and strength (Wertheim & Paxton, 2012). Furthermore, the body appreciation is a multidimensional structure representing feelings, thoughts and behaviours related to a person's own physical features (Muth & Cash, 1997; Dinç & Alisinanoğlu, 2010).

Body appreciation generally refers to how one perceives his/her body and the resultant feelings and acceptance about that perception. Body image appreciation can affect emotions, thoughts, relationships, and behaviours in everyday life (Pruzinsky & Cash, 2002). Body appreciation can also affect the images an individual has, and the self-languages he/she uses about themselves. Avalos, Tylka and Wood-Barcalow (2005) defined body appreciation as comprising several positive body appreciation qualities: favourable opinions of the body regardless of actual physical appearance; acceptance of the body despite its weight, shape, and imperfections; respect for the body by attending to its needs and engaging in healthy behaviours, and protection of the body by rejecting unrealistic body appreciations portrayed in the media. Body appreciation, as "a person's perceptions, thoughts and feelings about own body", becomes

one of the central focuses of adolescents (Grogan, 2008). The perceptive dimension refers to the mental representation of the physical body. Thoughts and feelings contribute to the attitude dimension. Regarding the attitude toward body, researchers distinguish between appraisal of appearance (satisfaction/dissatisfaction) and the importance placed on appearance (Cash & Pruzinski, 2002). Several studies have examined body appreciation, mainly in adult samples, but this study focused on adolescents, this is one of the gaps this study is filling.

The body appreciation field has always been a pathology-driven area of research concentrating on negative body appreciation and body appreciation disorders, but overlooking the concept of positive body appreciation (Smolak & Cash, 2011; Tylka, 2013). According to Avalos *et al.* (2005), research on body image traditionally has focused on describing and predicting negative body image such as body dissatisfaction, body shame, and body preoccupation, with less focus on identifying, predicting, and promoting adaptive body attitudes. It was long assumed that positive body appreciation was simply the opposite of negative body appreciation; however, more recent research suggests that positive body appreciation is more complex than that (Avalos *et al.* 2005; Wood-Barcalow, Tylka & Augustus-Horvath, 2010). While such research has produced a rich understanding of negative body appreciation, the understanding of positive body appreciation is still very poor. In fact, it was long assumed that positive body appreciation was simply the opposite of negative body appreciation, and that the concept therefore needed no further investigation. This study essentially sought to provide clarifications and further insights on body appreciation, especially as it concerns its possible links with gender, and self-perception factors (self-esteem and self-concept). As Smolak and Cash (2011) asserted that research focusing on positive, adaptive, or healthy body image is essential to the future of the field of body image.

Gender differences was hypothesized not to have links with body appreciation in this study. Gender in this study is used to mean being a male or a female (sex). Being a boy or a girl may have influence on the development and sustenance of body appreciation. The phrase “normative discontent” was first used almost two decades ago to describe the pervasive negative feelings that girls and women experience toward their bodies (Rodin, Silberstein & Striegel-Moore, 1985). Since then, there have been a large number of studies focusing on body image and its effects on quality of life for both sexes. However, recent research has indicated that the number of men and boys who have body dissatisfaction and who present for treatment of eating disturbances is increasing (McCabe & Ricciardelli, 2004). Interestingly, some studies have found inconsistent results in terms of sex differences in body image concerns. For instance, while Indonesian men had higher body image than did their female counterparts (Swami & Jaafar, 2012), there were no sex differences in body image among British adults (Swami, Hadji-Michael & Furnham, 2008). Lobera and Rios (2011)’s study submitted that girls experienced lower body image than did boys.

One factor that has been considered a central contributor to body appreciation is self-esteem. Several researches have linked self-esteem to other psychological constructs, one of these constructs is body image (Fortman, 2006). Self-esteem has been shown to be positively associated with physical (An, Ak, O’ Connor & Wexler, 2008) and psychological (Lyubomirsky, Tkach & DiMatteo, 2006) health. In both men and women, body dissatisfaction is strongly related to low self-esteem, a relationship that appears to be magnified at adolescence (Lennon, Lillethun & Buckland, 1999; Fortman, 2006). And it has been noted that greater body dissatisfaction lowers body appreciation. Therefore, as body dissatisfaction increases, body appreciation will decrease, thus lowering self-esteem. However, the relationship between body

dissatisfaction and self-esteem is much stronger in females (Lowery *et al.*, 2005).

Body appreciation has been associated with higher self-esteem (Swami, Airs, Chouhan, Leon & Towell, 2009; Swami, Stieger, Haubner & Voracek, 2008), greater psychological well-being, less body shame and body preoccupation, and fewer eating disorder symptoms (Avalos *et al.*, 2005). Lobera and Rios (2011) found that body appreciation was related to lower BMI, less stress and social withdrawal, and higher self-esteem and adaptive coping. McCabe and Ricciardelli (2001), (cited in Davidson & McCabe, 2006) found a strong association between body appreciation concerns and low self-esteem among adolescent girls, which has led to constructions of body appreciation as an important aspect of female self-esteem (Davidson & McCabe, 2006). Dorak (2011) found that there is a significantly stronger relationship between self-esteem and body appreciation. Lowery *et al.*, (2005) concluded that the relationship between body dissatisfaction and self-esteem is much stronger in females. In his study, Fortman (2006) opined that sex difference will likely make females' body appreciation more closely related to their self-esteem than that of males.

Self-concept is an individual's views and awareness of her/his own image and identity as a person. Self-concept is a composite cognitive description of one's attributes and affective evaluation of those attributes in comparison with others (Choi, 2005). In addition, self-concept, may be viewed as a hierarchical construct that includes several components, self-image (of what the person is), ideal self (what the person wants to be) and self-esteem (what the person feels about the discrepancy between what s/he is and what s/he would like to be) (Lawrence, 1996; Schmidt & Cagran, 2008). Self-image involves "a mixture of self-beliefs and self-feelings regarding general self-function" (Lent, Brown & Gore, 1997, p. 308); in more general terms, self-concept is what you know and understand about yourself in terms of your thoughts and feelings (Choi, 2005). Mercer (2011) pointed out that self-concept could be influenced or developed. Research is still growing in the area relationship between self-concept and body appreciation, which is one of the gaps the present study seeks to fill.

Self-concept at school seems to be affected by the image that other significant persons (teachers, parents, peers) have of the students (Cugmas, 1992) and by social comparison with others in the same setting (Schmidt & Cagran, 2008). Different social environments would therefore be expected to influence an individual's self-concept in different ways. Rohner's theory (Mrug & Wallander, 2002) postulates that feeling accepted or rejected by one's significant others will affect the way a person views and evaluates oneself and the world. Feeling rejected by others will lead to greater hostility, low self-respect, emotional instability and unresponsiveness, and a negative view of the world, whereas feeling accepted by others will lead to a lower feelings of hostility, higher self-concept, emotional stability and responsiveness, and a positive view of the world (Ali, 2012). Self-concept may have a great deal of effect on body-appreciation because perception does affect acceptance.

It has been observed that most of the studies conducted on gender, self-esteem, self-concept and body appreciation were done outside Nigeria and most of them shown that there is a positive correlation between the three independent variables and self-appreciation. Thus, this study is imperative, as it examined the relationship between the three independent variables and body appreciation on adolescents in the Nigerian context. Although body image has been the subject of many studies, there are still gaps in what is known about body appreciation and its influence on behaviour, attitudes, and quality of life of individuals. Much of the current literature includes women and girls as participants for body appreciation concerns, and there are fewer studies available that have investigated body appreciation issues in men and boys. In addition,

the literature on body appreciation has historically focused more on adult populations. There is still much information that is not known, such as when body image issues develop and the developmental course of body appreciation among adolescents. There is no gain saying therefore to submit that this study is filling gaps in literature and contributing to existing knowledge.

There have been several studies on adolescents and the manner they perceive their appearance, and the way it affects their behaviour. However, there is still paucity of empirical studies addressing body appreciation among adolescents in Nigeria. This gap in literature is disheartening especially considering the consequences poor body appreciation, because it could be a precursor for other disorders, especially eating disorders. Generally, the adolescence stage comes with much storm and stress as teenagers struggle with a lot unanswered questions while trying to understand the adult world. Adolescents also may have challenges with self-identity and ego formation. These rather never-ending struggles with developmental tasks could result in problems with identifying with self and appreciating their bodies. Lack of body appreciation has been observed to possibly lead to self-defeating statements, and self-hate. There can also be a lot of psychological and social problems resulting from poor body appreciation. Some of them include: anxiety, depression, self-hatred, non-suicidal self-injury, isolation, psychological withdrawal, suicidal ideation, social fat talks, suicide, body shaming and cyber bullying. The adolescence period of life which ought to be a time of high psychological well-being, adjustment, enjoyment and good sense of self, is now sadly characterised with weight preoccupation, appearance anxiety, low self-esteem and negative self-concept. The parents of adolescents who experience poor body appreciation could have the problem of despair as regards their children's identity and favourable body image development. These parents could also have disturbed concept of their parenting skills and low family worth in the society.

Hypotheses

The following directional null hypotheses were tested in this study at 0.05 level of significance:

Ho1: There is no significant relationship among gender, self-esteem, self-concept and body appreciation of senior secondary school adolescents.

Ho2: There is no significant joint contribution of gender, self-esteem and self-concept to the prediction of body appreciation of senior secondary school adolescents.

Ho3: There is no significant relative effects gender, self-esteem and self-concept to the prediction of body appreciation of senior secondary school adolescents.

Methodology

Design and Participants

This study adopted the descriptive research design of survey type. The researcher did not manipulate any of the variables in the study. Variables were studied as they existed in the participants as at the time of study. The participants comprised of adolescents in senior secondary schools I, II and III.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample for the study consisted of one hundred and seventy-seven adolescents in senior secondary schools within Ibadan-North Local Government Area. The participants were drawn from three public secondary schools, with sixty in each school. One hundred and eighty questionnaires were administered in total, but one hundred and seventy-seven questionnaires were correctly filled and found suitable for analyses. The sample was drawn using the Multistage

sampling technique: first a simple random sampling technique was used to select three public schools out of the forty-two public secondary schools in Ibadan-North Local Government Area; then a purposive sampling technique was used to select only students in the senior classes for easy comprehension of questionnaire items. The researcher went to the schools during school hours after taking permission from the schools’ Principals and was assisted by the school counsellors. The age range of the participants was 13-19, with an average age of 16 years.

Table 4.1: Distribution of Respondents by Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	98	55.4%
Female	79	44.6%
Total	177	100

Instrumentation

Data were collected with the use of a Questionnaire containing three sections. Section A consisted of Demographic information about the respondent’s, gender, age, school name and religion. Section B contained: the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale by Rosenberg (1965)-a 10-item instrument on a four-point rating scale, which was adopted and used to measure senior secondary school adolescents’ self-esteem; the Self-Concept Clarity Scale by Campbell, Trapnell, Heine, Katz, Lavalley and Lehman (1996)- a 12-item instrument on a Likert type ordinal scale, which was adopted to measure the self-concept of senior secondary school adolescents and The Body Appreciation Scale (BAS) by Avalos, Tylka, and Wood-Barcalow, (2005), a 13-item instrument on a five-point rating scale, adopted to assess senior secondary school adolescents’ acceptance of, favorable opinions towards, and respect for their bodies. In the present study, the scales yielded Cronbach alpha coefficients of: .84; .76 and .79 respectively.

Method of Data Analysis

Data collected for this study were analysed using the Pearson’s product moment correlation and multiple regression analyses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Hypothesis one: There is no significant relationship among gender, self-esteem, self-concept and body appreciation.

Table 4.2: Correlation matrix showing the relationship between body appreciation and the independent variables

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	1	2	3	4
Body appreciation	35.5593	10.22631	1			
Self-esteem	25.3785	5.46041	.256*	1		
Self-concept	29.0339	6.16063	.322*	.770	1	
Gender	1.4463	.49852	.147	.050	.980	1

*Correlation is significant at 0.05

Table 4.2 shows the inter-correlation matrix of the independent variables (sex, self-esteem and self-concept) and dependent variable (body appreciation) scores. Table 4.2 reveals that body appreciation has significant relationship with self-esteem ($r=0.256$, $p<0.05$) and self-concept ($r=0.322$, $p<0.05$). Body appreciation had no significant relationship with gender ($r=0.147$, $p>0.05$).

Hypothesis two: There is no significant joint contribution of all the independent variables to the prediction of body appreciation.

Table 4.3 Summary of Regression Analysis showing the joint contributions of the independent variables to the prediction of body appreciation

R=0.295 R Square=0.087 Adjusted R Square=0.071 Std. Error of the Estimate= 9.85453							
Mode		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
1	Regression	1605.280	3	535.093	5.510	0.001	Sig
	Residual	16800.347	174	97.112			
	Total	18405.627	177				

Table 4.3 revealed the combine contribution of the independent variables in the prediction of body appreciation. $F_{(3,174)} = 5.510$, $P<0.05$). The result yielded a coefficient of multiple regression R of 0.295 and Adjusted $R^2 = 0.071$ which implies that the three independent variables jointly accounted for 7.1% of the variation in body appreciation. The remaining percentage could be explained with reference to extraneous variables that were not part of this study.

Hypothesis three: There is no significant relative contribution of each of the independent variables to the prediction of body appreciation

Table 4.4 Summary of multiple linear regressions showing the relative contributions of each of the independent variables to the prediction of body appreciation

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	27.239	5.783		4.710	.000
	Self-esteem	.480	.136	.256	3.524	.001*
	Self-concept	.016	.122	.009	.129	.004*
	Gender	-2.981	1.509	-.145	-1.976	.050*

Table 4.4 shows the relative contribution of each of the independent variables on the dependent variable; self-esteem ($\beta = .256$, $p < .05$), self-concept ($\beta = .009$, $p < .05$) and gender ($\beta = -.145$, $p < .05$). Hence, all the predictor variables significantly relatively contributed to the prediction of body appreciation with self-esteem which contributed the most and was followed by self-concept, while gender contributed the least.

Discussion

Hypothesis one stated that there is no significant relationship among gender, self-esteem, self-concept and body appreciation. The findings revealed that there was a positive, significant relationship among self-esteem and self-concept and body appreciation, while there was no significant relationship between gender and body appreciation. This means that self-perception factors (self-esteem and self-concept) are related to body appreciation. The probable reason for this finding could be that body appreciation which is a multidimensional construct combining cognitive, affective and psychomotor aspects of an individual being, has both sense of worth and image tied to it. The participants in these study could be adjudged to always base their sense of worth and image of themselves on their physical appearances which in turn, affect the way they accept and appreciate their physique. The findings may not be far from the postulations of Robert Havighurst's Developmental task theory where he submitted that adolescents-both males and females alike have the task of accepting their own physique. The findings supported the findings of Fortman (2006) and Dorak (2011) who found that a high proportion of self-esteem and body image in female adolescents who are athletes or non-athletes. These findings agreed with the findings of Pisitsungkagarn, Taephant and Attasaranya (2013) that found a relation between body image satisfaction and self-esteem in Thai female adolescents. The findings also agreed with Black (2002) who asserted that there is no important significant relationship between body appreciation and sex.

There was no positive, moderately significant relationship between gender (sex) and body appreciation. This implies that gender (sex) was not related to body appreciation. In line with this finding, Rosenblum and Lewis (1999) had submitted that ratings of physical attractiveness and body image remain relatively stable across the early teenage years, but become increasingly negative around age 15-18 years because of pubertal changes equally in both boys and girls. The finding supported the findings of Lawler & Nixon (2011) who in their studies found that body dissatisfaction among adolescent boys and girls was not different in the effects of body mass, peer appearance culture and internalization of appearance ideals. The finding contradicts the findings of Tatangelo & Ricciardelli (2013)'s study which found areas of differences in the perception of attractiveness and body dissatisfaction among boys and girls. Tatangelo & Ricciardelli (2013) revealed that fitness is an important element of boys' and girls' body ideals. For boys the emphasis was on sport, and this was promoted by their peer interactions and the sportsmen they admired. For girls the focus was on looking good, and this was reinforced by their peer conversations, and the actresses and singers they admired. The findings of this study in the area of relationship among gender, self-esteem and body appreciation also differ from Gatti, Ionio, Traficante and Confalonieri (2014) and Lowery (2005)'s findings. According to these authors, females are more vulnerable than males in the realm of physical changes; and this vulnerability turns into a greater level of body and weight dissatisfaction, which reflects low self-esteem.

The second hypothesis stated that there is no joint contribution of gender, self-esteem and self-concept to body appreciation among in-school adolescents. The results revealed that the composite contributions of gender, self-esteem and self-concept on body appreciation were significant. There was a joint effect of gender, self-esteem and self-concept on body appreciation of in-school adolescents. This implies that when gender, self-esteem and self-concept were taken together, they jointly contributed to body appreciation. This result might not be surprising since the predictor variables all have significant relationship with the criterion measure in this study except for gender. This finding is in line with Harter (1999)'s study which confirmed that the perceptions of physical appearance and self-worth are inextricably linked, such that perceived appearance consistently emerges as the strongest single predictor of self-esteem among both male and female children and adolescents. Similarly, McCabe and Ricciardelli (2005) confirmed that physical appearance is critical for adolescent boys' and girls' development of self-confidence, which is a product of self-concept. Clay, Vignoles and Dittmar (2005), the perception of appearance and self-worth are linked and perceived appearance is a strong single predictor of self-esteem among both male and female adolescents.

Hypothesis 3 stated that there is no relative contribution of gender, self-esteem and self-concept to body appreciation among in-school adolescents. The result showed that there was a relative effect of the three independent variables on body appreciation of in-school adolescents. Self-esteem had the most effect while sex had the least effect on body appreciation of in-school adolescents. This implies that self-esteem and self-concept had more effect on body appreciation but sex did not. Both self-esteem and self-concept are both self-perception factors almost having the same root in behaviour. The similarity of these self-constructs might make it possible for both to jointly predict body appreciation leaving out gender. Body appreciation, acceptance and respect could be adjudged to be a function of internal-orientation of adolescents firmly rooted in self-perception. The findings of this study further means that being a male or a female does not have to do with body appreciation. The probable reason for this finding is that the adolescence stage unifies the experiences of both males and females. The society treats them the same way, they have same developmental tasks and all have issues with ego identity formation, thus all these might not account for differences observable in the relationship between gender and body appreciation among adolescents used in the study.

This finding is in line with that of Bearman, Presnell, Martinez and Stice (2006)'s study which did not find a significant relationship between gender of adolescent girls and boys, and body dissatisfaction. For both genders, the desire to alter shape or weight during adolescence is common, and is associated. Also, the finding supported the findings of Lawler & Nixon (2011) who in their studies found that body dissatisfaction among adolescent boys and girls was not different in terms of the effects of body mass, peer appearance culture and internalisation of appearance ideals.

Conclusion from Findings

It could be concluded from the findings of this study that self-esteem and self-concept had significant positive relationships with body appreciation, and also predicted body appreciation. Gender on the other hand did not have a relationship with body appreciation, and could not predict body appreciation.

Body appreciation is an essential part of an individual's personality make up and sense of self, which can be determined by the way the individual views his/her body, the influence of societal messages, culture, and personal experience. Body appreciation is affected by biological,

cognitive and emotional factors, with resultant effects on the physical and psychological wellness of individuals. Thus, adolescents concentrate on their bodies; they consider their body as an integral component of their self-esteem and self-concept.

Limitation of the Study

The study was limited in that the sample for the study is not sufficiently large enough considering the fact that adolescents in the senior secondary schools are rather too abundant for the small sample used in the study. Despite this limitation however, the findings of the study can still be said to be valid.

Implications for Positive psychology and Counselling Practice

Self-perception factors have a lot to do with body appreciation, acceptance and respect. Positive and counselling psychologists can use the knowledge of adolescents' developmental tasks and positive psychology interventions to assist school-going adolescents in self-identity and ego formation so that they can grow to become self-confident adults. There can be ego bolstering programmes organised and facilitated in schools for adolescents which would help their self-presentation and social competence. The school counsellors can help adolescents to improve their self-esteem in order to have more favourable body appreciation.

Also adolescents can be assisted in having a realistic and positive self-concept for proper body appreciation, and overall wellness and happiness in life.

Recommendations

The following are the recommendations put forward as a result of the outcome of this study:

1. Trained counsellors in secondary schools should endeavour to employ psychotherapeutic interventions to train and support adolescents in fostering positive perceptions about themselves and their bodies, and developing high self-esteem and self-concept.
2. Positive/Counselling psychologists and mental health professionals can organise group guidance programmes and extracurricular activities to educate and mentor students on the importance of having a healthy body image and body appreciation.
3. Parents should adopt healthy parenting competences and modelling strategies that would assist their children to develop and sustain high self-esteem and self-concept to help them in life generally.
4. Since, body appreciation is positively related to adolescents' feelings of well-being, it also has links with adolescents' academic achievement. In this way, teachers should always find ways of using labelling, and relationship with students that will enhance positive views of themselves, and create a good quality of school life.
5. The media in the forms of magazines, video games, social media, television, beauty pageants, radio, billboards (cosmetics advertisements) play major roles in the development and sustenance of self-perceptions, body love, and acceptance. Parents and parent figures should help in the control of consumption, internalisation, and belief of media messages among adolescents.

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Relationship between intervention strategies of non-governmental organisations and well-being of internally displaced persons in Adamawa state, Nigeria: Implications for social work

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Introduction

Individuals are being displaced all over the world due to several factors. Internal displacement is a phenomenon in which individuals are forced to leave their homes but remain within the borders of their countries. The key element that distinguishes IDPs from refugees, those who are forcibly displaced across the internationally recognized borders of the State, is that internally displaced persons remain within their borders (World Bank, 1994). Internal displacement occurs when there are situations such as armed conflict, persecution, widespread outbreaks of violence, natural and human disasters and, more recently, large-scale development projects (Mooney, 2005).

Internally displaced persons are persons who have been forced to leave their homes for various reasons but have not crossed international borders. They are often persecuted or attacked by their governments or other enemies who supposedly are more powerful than the original inhabitants, often the IDPs are in a more desperate situation than refugees. The number of displaced persons doubles the number of refugees. They are at the forefront of the humanitarian agenda. They are also known as "internal refugees" (Inter-Agency Standing Committee, 2007).

Nigeria has 36 states as her federating units, and out of these, there are 12 states with internally displaced persons (IDPs) due to sectarian wars, rebellions and pastoralists. The Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre estimates that there are approximately 2,152,000 internally displaced persons in Nigeria as of December 31st 2015. According to an assessment conducted by the International Organization for Migration (IOM) in 2016, it has been gathered that there are about 207 local government areas that suffer from this displacement phenomenon are spread in 13 northern states in Nigeria. Gombe had 25,332 internally displaced persons, Adamawa had 136,010 internally displaced persons and Kano had 9331 internally displaced persons, Kaduna had 36,976 internally displaced persons, Bauchi had 70,078 displaced persons, Plateau had 77,317 internally displaced persons, Taraba had 50,227 internally displaced persons, Zamfara had 44, 929 internally displaced persons, Nasarawa had 37,553 internally displaced persons, Borno had 1,434,149 internally displaced persons, Benue had 85,393 internally displaced persons and Yobe had 131,203 internally displaced persons (IOM, 2016). Of the total number of internally displaced persons, the assessment indicates that 12.6% were displaced by sectarian/communal clashes, 2.4% due to natural disasters and 85% due to insurgent attacks by Islamists. (Akinboye & Oloruntoba, 2017)

The Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) are created by citizens to bridge the gap left by States for provision of social services. World Bank, (2006) defines NGOs as private organisations characterised primarily by humanitarian objectives rather than commercial objectives by pursuit of activities to relieve suffering, promote the interests of the poor, protect the environment, provide basic social services, or undertake community developments. Therefore, NGOs are one group of players who are active in the efforts of development and increasing the welfare of needy people in communities. NGOs work both independently and alongside bilateral aid agencies from developed countries, private-sector, infrastructure operators, self-help associations, and local governments. This agrees with the views of Akinboye and Oloruntoba (2017) that the emergence of NGOs is the result of the state's failure to meet the aspirations of the people by providing the fruits of democracy to the masses. Thus, the last two decades represent a shift in the evolution of non-governmental organizations. They have been recognized as relief providers and promoters of human rights (Osaghae, 1997). The important role of non-governmental organizations is reflected in the roles they play, which intersect with the main aspect of human life, such as health, the social environment and economic development. The above activities of NGOs shows that without their involvement, there will be an overwhelming human rights violation (Ajayi, 2006), and debasement of wellbeing of some populace, especially the IDPs and the Refugees.

Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) in Nigeria have always been recognized for conducting interventions where the government cannot intervene in every matter pertaining to her citizens. Most of the times, they are sponsored by foreign organizations who attempt to ensure that the benefit of globalization reaches every community in every country. Some of these interventions could be necessary as a matter of urgency as it could be demanded in war zone areas, areas affected by natural disasters, and conflict-areas. Basically, the mission of NGOs is to alleviate people's problems, intervene in communal problems and help people in crises, including the internally displaced persons (IDPs). These activities are carried out in countries where the government cannot reach every citizen as exemplified mostly in developing countries. NGOs, in Nigeria for instance, are set-up to provide basic social services and advocate for the voiceless and marginalised in the society (Lathar & Prabhakar, 2010) including the IDPs. It is worthy of note that NGOs only complement the government but do not compete with it.

Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) are persons or groups of persons who have been forced or obliged to flee or to leave their homes or places of habitual residence, in particular as a result of or in order to avoid the effects of armed conflict, situations of generalized violence, violations of human rights or natural or human-made disasters, and who have not crossed an internationally recognized State border (Lathar & Prabhakar, 2010). IDPs have been recipients of intervention strategies of NGOs over the years due to several circumstances that have made them helpless and at their mercy, but have not really felt the impact of these intervention strategies (International Committee of Red Cross, 1999). Non-Governmental Organisations have in many ways intervened in the wellbeing of IDPs using intervention strategies like food and water; access to protection and security; educational services; and health services to cushioning the effects of the dilemma they face with resultant impact on their well-being.

Food and water are one of the basic necessities of every human, be it people living a normal life, not affected by conflict, wars, natural disasters and those that are affected. Those that are affected by the aforementioned factors no longer have means of livelihood that are basic necessities of life that are germane to their wellbeing and survival (Mooney, 2005). Housing is central to everyone for improvement of their quality of life and health. It is a very valuable asset

which has much wider economic, social, cultural and personal significance. Housing has an impact over development goals such as equity and poverty eradication and wellbeing. The ability to live in permanent houses has decreased sharply among the IDPs revealing that the IDPs will have their social status and quality of life affected negatively in the future. Permanent housing is indeed one of the main outstanding displacement-related needs of IDPs (IDMC, 2012). Hence, NGOs have come in to provide these basic necessities of food and water after housing for IDPs in different ways and approaches as a form of their intervention strategy.

Ministry of Home Affairs, Government of India (2005) found that intervention strategies of food, water and housing had a significant impact on displaced people's standard of living and access to basic services. The study found that securing immediate subsistence needs such as food, water and housing poses immense difficulties for IDPs. It concluded that the standard of living of IDPs is far from being adequate and affects their opportunity to exercise other rights, such as access to education and healthcare or opportunities. Internal Displacement Monitoring Committee (IDMC) (2012) also corroborated this finding that IDPs' livelihoods have been disrupted as a result of their displacement. IDMC (2007) also found that conditions in IDP camps were inadequate with reported problems with water, sanitation and shelter which led to disease outbreaks and reduction in the wellbeing of IDPs. Sumona (2004) established that children of displaced tribal families died of enteric diseases after consuming wild plants to stave off hunger. All Indian Women (2006) confirmed that lack of clean drinking water and poor living conditions have led to the outbreak of diseases such as malaria, jaundice, dysentery and influenza. These findings established the fact that the provision of these services has significant impact on the wellbeing of IDPs.

The concept of protection encompasses all activities aimed at obtaining full respect for the rights of the individual in accordance with the letter and the spirit of the relevant bodies' human rights, (International Committee of Red Cross, 1999). Basically, the protection and security of the citizenry lies with the government, but the less functional and effectiveness of the country's security system, has prompted NGOs in providing protection and security for people, particularly, IDPs who have earned this status as a result of insecurity and other factors thereby, making the intervention of NGOs very important for the wellbeing of IDPs (ICRC, 1999).

The results of Internal Displacement Monitoring Committee IDMC (2010) on protection and security revealed that displacement is destabilising and traumatic for all people that are uprooted from their natural habitat. It further confirmed that displacement exposes them to risks and lowers their wellbeing in all phases, that is, psychological, physical, social, and spiritual because of absence of protection and security. Graca (2006) found that the harmful effects of armed conflict upon a people's psychological and physical wellbeing are multiplied by the experience of displacement and absence of security. Also, Ager, Bremer & Boothby (2008) confirms from their finding that Internally Displaced Persons are vulnerable to sexual violence, especially during civil conflicts military conscription or abduction and in detention due to the absence of security. Therefore, protection and security of IDPs by NGOs from harm become imperative because of their subjection to various violence, assaults and abuse which had psychological, physical and emotional negative effects on their wellbeing (Hyder, 1998).

Access to education is another important intervention strategy of NGOs to IDPs. Education is one of the most important right of children in Nigeria and according to the Child Rights Act of 2003, a Nigerian child is entitled to at least universal primary education regardless of situations and circumstances surrounding the child therefore, IDPs are entitled to one form of education or another (Women's Commission for Women Refugee and Children, 2004). Conflict

and security have had a direct and compounding negative impact on children's access to education, the availability of education spaces, materials and the ability of teachers. As important as education is for every child, the inability to access educational services can have dire consequences on both the immediate and future wellbeing of a child (Mooney & French, 2003).

In many emergencies, schools are used to provide temporary accommodation for IDPs, reducing access to education for host communities. Tensions arise when IDPs are seen as being in competition for limited resources, or when they are seen as being given preferential treatment. IDMC (2008) found that education services intervention strategy provided for children in situations of armed conflict and when they are internally displaced prepare them for development and help ensure future opportunities. According to IDPs perceptual satisfaction which is largely positive over the quality of interventions and anticipated impact on quality of life improvement and overall development it could be presumed that the level of education is expected to contribute positively to overall development. Supporting the resilience of displaced persons through education is found to be one of the most effective ways to support IDP people's psychosocial well-being (Ferris & Winthrop, 2010)

A research conducted by Human Rights Watch (2003) on the effect of educational services on IDPs, showed that displacement often has a profound impact on the education of children due to the closure of schools, lack of facilities and difficult environment in the camps. Young people's opportunity of completing education is also sometimes affected by the need for them to work to contribute financially to their family's survival. The education of girls, already a low priority, suffers further during displacement and dire financial times. Women Commission for Women Refugee and Children(2004) concluded that for these displaced children not only are their educational development denied, but they are deprived of other important benefits as well such as provision of a degree of stability and normalcy, a critical source of psychosocial support, reduction in children's exposure to threats including sexual exploitation, physical attack and military recruitment and effective forums for conveying life-saving information about other risks including landmines and their well-being. It is observed that IDP children who take shelter in churches, schools or living with other family members are not often catered for which is very detrimental to the future wellbeing of the children and the country in general, as no child should be deprived education no matter the circumstance (Mooney & French, 2005).

Education is often cited as one important way of supporting the psychosocial well-being of children and youth during conflict and displacement. Many argue that education, if it is a safe and quality education – whether in an acute crisis or a chronic refugee context – can promote children's protection and welfare by providing, among other things, structured daily routines where children can play and interact with peers and adults in a positive manner, physically-safe spaces for children to go to every day that keep them out of other potentially harmful situations, and important information about safety and security (Nicolai, & Triplehorn, 2003).

Displaced children have often witnessed violence against family members or friends and, even after they have physically moved to another location, continue to feel afraid with resultant effect on their health. For example, some 34 percent of Iraqi refugee children surveyed in Jordan reported that they had witnessed violence in Iraq and nearly 40 percent said they had lost someone close due to violence (World Vision, 2007.) To make matters worse, Jordan lacks the professionals who are integral to catering to the psychosocial needs of these children (World Vision, 2007.)

Access to health services is one of the most important intervention strategies of NGOs to IDPs, lack of or inadequacy leads to serious health implications, affecting their wellbeing

negatively, while the adequate supply of health services, have positive effects on their wellbeing (WHO, 2005). NGOs provide two types of health services for IDPs, which could be classified into short-term services and long-term health services. The short-term health services provided by NGOs serve as immediate relief to the IDPs, with services ranging from provision of drugs, provision of materials to avert sicknesses like cough, catarrh etc which are common sicknesses among IDPs because of the unhygienic conditions they live in (Vincet & Sorenson, 2001).

The findings of Asher (2004) reported that there is a significant correlation between the health, wellbeing and the right to basic health services of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs). IDMC (2012) further corroborated that conflict leads to the destruction of health facilities and supplies, flight of health workers, and a breakdown in services for displaced persons with the effect on lowering their general wellbeing. In a study conducted by the World Health Organisation (2005) on the health and wellbeing of IDPs, it was found that mortality rates in the camps are well above emergency thresholds. Therefore there is the need for supply and maintenance of health facilities within the camp. Zoidze & Djibuti (2004) found that it appears that a majority of IDPs camps are publicly provided with health care benefits, much evidence suggests that the overall health status of IDPs is worse than that of the general population.

Factors responsible for displacement of people are multifaceted ranging from human right violation to wars and insurgencies. The displaced persons require the attention of authorities (government) to meet their needs. Nigeria, a federating unit with the presidential system of government, requires that the responsibility of taking care of Internally Displaced Persons should be borne by the federal, state and local governments. However, this duty has been underprovided by the authorities thereby making IDPs live in hopeless conditions. The absence or lack of these reliefs has dire consequences on both the present and future wellbeing of the IDPs. Lack of nutritive food and clean water leads to death, malnutrition and sickness. Absence or inadequate food and water in IDP camps makes their environment very dirty leading to several water-borne diseases like cholera, diarrhea etc. Similarly, the absence of security and protection also has varied consequences such as loss of life, exposure of women and children to abuse, rape, child labour etc. Furthermore, the consequences of lack of educational training for the children and adolescents in the IDP camps makes them become idle and get involved in anti-social behaviours the consequent disturbance of the camp. Furthermore, inadequacy of health services within the camps results in high morbidity and mortality rate. Intervention strategies of NGOs to the IDPs gave a life-line to the IDPs giving them hope in seemingly hopeless situations and also serve as coping mechanisms for them to overcome the traumatic situations experienced. It is against this background that this study investigated the effect of intervention strategies of NGOs on the wellbeing of Internally Displaced Persons.

Four hypotheses are raised for the study, they are:

1. There is no significant relationship between the provision of food and water by NGOs on the wellbeing of IDPs in Adamawa State, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant relationship between the provisions of protection and security by NGOs on the wellbeing of IDPs in Adamawa State, Nigeria.
3. There is no significant relationship between the provisions of educational training by NGOs on the wellbeing of IDPs in Adamawa State, Nigeria.
4. There is no significant relationship between the provisions of health services by NGOs on the wellbeing of IDPs in Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Methodology

Research Design

Descriptive survey research design of the *expost facto* type was used study. This is because it is an empirical method which presents a description of events as they are and there is no need to manipulate any of the variables. It also facilitates easy collection of factual information about the research problem.

Population, Sample and Sampling Techniques:

The population comprised mature Internally Displaced Persons (15 years and above) in camps in Mubi and Girei, Adamawa state, Nigeria.

Purposive sampling technique was used to select two large IDP Camps in Adamawa state namely Mubi and Girei. These camps were chosen because they are the best camps where all intervention strategies have been put in place. From each camp, the simple random sampling technique, using the fishbowl style, was used to select one hundred and fifty internally displaced persons from each of Mubi and Girei camps making a total of three hundred respondents for the study. The internally displaced persons who were participants in this study have been in the camps for a minimum of three months as at the time of this study.

Research Instrument

The main instrument used for the research is a questionnaire with six sub-sections on Intervention Strategies of Non-Governmental Organisations and Wellbeing of Internally Displaced Persons. It has an overall reliability coefficient of 0.83. The response to the questionnaire was measured with a four point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2 and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1.

Section A: Demographic Data – this comprise of demographic variable such as age, sex, marital status, educational qualification and the number of children.

Section B: Food and Water for Security Scale (FWSS) - This was made up of 7 items measuring the provision of food and water in the camp. The items were adapted and isolated from “Food and Nutrition Technical Assistance Project (FANTA)” (2007) by Academic for Educational Development and Agencia Espanola de Cooperacion Internacional para el Desarrollo by Waswa, (2012). The revalidated scale has a reliability coefficient of 0.85.

Section C: Protection and Security Scale (PSS) - This was made up of 7 items adapted from “Food and Nutrition Technical Assistance Project (FANTA)” (2007) by Academic for Educational Development and Agencia Espanola de Cooperacion Internacional para el Desarrollo by Waswa (2012). It has a revalidated reliability coefficient of 0.91.

Section D: Educational Training Scale (ETS) - This was made up of 7 items adapted from World Vision Need Assessment Report by Bekaa (2012). It has a revalidated reliability coefficient of 0.79.

Section E: Health Scale (HS) - This was made up of 7-item measuring Health Services provision. The items were adapted from Patient Satisfaction Questionnaire by Grant & Haye (2005). This scale has a revalidated reliability coefficient of 0.82.

Section F: Wellbeing Scale (WS): This was further sub-divided into:

i. Psychological Wellbeing Scale (PWS) - This was made up of 7 items measuring psychological wellbeing which was adapted from Ryff’s psychological wellbeing scale (2005). The scale has a revalidated reliability coefficient of 0.81.

ii. Emotional Wellbeing Scale (EWS) - This was made up of 7 items measuring Emotional wellbeing and adapted from Satisfaction with Life Scale by Diener, Emmons, Larsen, & Griffin, (1985). It has a revalidated reliability coefficient of 0.81.

Data gathering and analysis

The questionnaires were personally administered by the researcher through the assistance of Non-Governmental Organisations and its employees working in Internally Displaced Persons camps. This was done because of the situation of insurgency in Adamawa state which confers some security constraints which impeded the researcher from going into the camp personally. The questionnaire was left for 2 weeks for proper completion. Of the total, three hundred questionnaires administered, 243 were retrieved and two hundred and forty (240) were found usable for data analysis. Frequency counts, percentages were used to analyse the demographic data while Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to analyse the research hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Result and Discussion of Findings

Table 1: Frequency distribution of the Respondent by sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	102	42.5
Female	138	57.5
Total	240	100.0

In the table above, the female respondents were 138 (57.5%) while their male counterparts were 102 (42.5%). This implies that there are more females in the camps who are Internally Displaced than men. The implication is that war, conflicts and natural disaster adversely affect women more than men and that the men might have been killed in battle.

Table 2: Distribution of respondents by age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
15-24	25	10.4
25-34	74	30.8
35-44	78	32.5
45-54	33	13.8
55+	30	12.5
Total	240	100.0

From table 2, it was observed that 25(10.4%) of the respondents were within the age range of 15-24 years, 74(30.8%) respondents were within the age range of 25-34 years. 78(32.5%) respondents were within the age range of 35-44 years, 33(13.8%) were within the age range of 45-54 years, while 30(12.5%) were within the above 54 years. The implication is that majority of the Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) are in their middle ages and active years and they can still contribute immensely to the economy if they are not affected by war, conflict, natural disasters etc. Furthermore, it implies that the trauma and loss of displacement affect these middle-aged displaced persons with resultant long-term effect to their old age.

Table 3: Distribution of respondents by marital status

Marital status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	26	10.8
Married	89	37.1
Widowed	75	31.3
Separated	37	15.4
Divorced	13	5.4
Total	240	100.0

Table 3 shows that 26 (10.8%) are single, 89 (37.1%) were married, 75 (31.3%) are widowed, while 37 (15.4%) are separated. The implication is that there is no limit to who is affected by displacement, from singles to divorcees.

Table 4: Distribution of respondents by Educational qualification

Educational qualification	Frequency	Percentage
Primary	102	42.5
Secondary School	94	39.2
OND,NCE	22	9.2
HND	10	4.2
Degree	12	5.0
Total	240	100.0

Table 4 showed that 102 (42.5%) respondents had primary school leaving certificate, 94 (39.2%) had secondary school leaving certificate, 22 (9.2%) had OND/NCE certificate, 10 (4.2%) had HND certificate while 12 (5.0%) were Degree holders. This implies that most of Internally Displaced Persons have lower qualifications since they were home based as at the time of displacement, while highly educated ones have gone for greener pastures outside the war zones.

Table 5: Distribution of respondents by number of children

No. of Children	Frequency	Percentage
Nil	26	10.8
1-3	85	35.4
4-6	72	30.0
7 and above	57	23.8
Total	240	100.0

Table 5 shows that 26 (10.8%) had no children because they are single(see table 3); 85 (35.4%) had 1-3 children, 72 (30.0%) had 4-6 children, 57 (23.8%) had 7 and above children. The implication is that the population of IDPs in the camp consists of children and their parents.

Research Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between the provision food and water by NGOs and the wellbeing of Internally Displaced Persons.

Table 6: showing the relationship between the provision of food and water and the wellbeing of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs)

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	r	P	Remark
Provision of Food and Water	12.4292	2.9605	240	.166	.000	Sig.
Well-being of Displaced Persons	28.8833	6.8090				

Table 6 show that there was a significant relationship between food and water provision and the wellbeing of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) ($r = .166$, $n=240$, $P < 0 .05$). This means that food and water provision has influence on the wellbeing of IDPs positively.

The finding is supported by a number of scholars who found a significant relationship between the provision of food and water and the wellbeing of Internally Displaced Persons. Ministry of Home Affairs, Government of India (2005) found out that Internal displacement has a significant negative impact on displaced people’s standard of living and access to basic services. Securing immediate subsistence needs such as food, water and housing poses immense difficulties for them. Also, Sumona, (2004), found that four children of displaced tribal families, all below six years of age, had died of enteric diseases after consuming wild plants to stave off hunger. Furthermore, findings of All India Women (2006) corroborate this finding that lack of clean drinking water and poor living conditions have led to the outbreak of diseases such as malaria, jaundice, dysentery and influenza. International Committee of Red Cross, (2010), also found that IDPs are affected by a wide variety of needs in the short, medium and long term. These include food, water, shelter and other essential items, security, physical and psychological well-being.

Hypotheses 2: There is no significant relationship between the provision of protection and security by NGOs and the wellbeing of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs).

Table 7: showing the relationship between the provision of protection and security by NGOs and the wellbeing of Internally Displaced Persons

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	r	P	Remark
Provision of Protection and Security	10.6958	4.1513	240	.403	.000	Sig.
Well-being of Internally Displaced Persons	28.8833	6.8090				

Table 7 showed that there was significant relationship between provision of protection and security and the wellbeing of Internally Displaced Persons ($r = .403$, $n=240$, $< .05$). This means

that the protection and security provided by Non-Governmental Organisations have impact on the wellbeing of Internally Displaced Persons.

The finding is corroborated by Internal Displacement Monitoring Committee IDMC (2010) that absence of protection and security by Government or its agencies exposes IDPs to risks and lowers their wellbeing in all phases, that is, psychological, physical, social, and spiritual. Also, Graca (2006) confirm this finding when he found that the harmful effects of armed conflict upon an IDP’s psychological and physical wellbeing are multiplied by the experience of displacement and absence of security. Furthermore, finding is confirmed by Ager, Bremer & Boothby (2008) that Internally Displaced Persons are vulnerable to sexual violence, especially during civil conflicts military conscription or abduction and in detention due to the absence of security. Therefore, protection and security of IDPs by NGOs from harm become imperative because of their subjection to various violence, assaults and abuse which had psychological, physical and emotional negative effects on their wellbeing.

Hypotheses 3: There is no significant relationship between the provision of educational trainings by NGOs and the wellbeing of Internally Displaced Persons.

Table 8: showing the relationship between the provision of educational trainings and the wellbeing of Internally Displaced Persons.

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	r	P	Remark
Provision of Educational Trainings	11.6000	3.4213	240	.207	.001	Sig.
Well-being of Displaced Persons	28.8833	6.8090				

Table 8 showed that there was a significant relationship between the provision of educational trainings and the wellbeing of IDPs ($r = .207, n=240, p < .05$). This means the provision of educational trainings by the NGOs has impact on the wellbeing of IDPs.

Norwegian Refugee Council (2008) confirm this finding that education is critical in protecting displaced children and youth, contribute to their wellbeing and enabling them to contribute to the sustainable peace and recovery of their societies upon return, resettlement or integration. Also, Ferris & Winthrop, (2010) confirmed that supporting the resilience of displaced persons through education is found to be one of the most effective ways to support IDP people’s psychosocial well-being.

Human Rights Watch (2003) also established the finding that displacement often has a profound impact on the education of children, due to the closure of schools, lack of facilities and difficult environment in the camps. Women Commission for Women Refugee and Children, (2004) also confirmed that going to school is known to provide a degree of stability and normalcy in the traumatized lives of internally displaced children, and can be a critical source of psychosocial support. Finally, the daily act of mastering content and more importantly the belief that they were on the right path to a brighter future was central to the benefits of education and found to be supportive of the wellbeing of IDP children by Winthrop, & Kirk (2008).

Hypotheses 4: There is no significant relationship between the provision of health services by NGOs and the wellbeing of Internally Displaced Persons.

Table 9: showing the relationship between the provision of health services and the wellbeing of Internally Displaced Persons.

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	r	P	Remark
Provision of Health Services	12.5833	3.6398	240	.343	.000	Sig.
Well-being of Displaced Persons	28.8833	6.8090				

Table 9 showed that there was a significant relationship between the provision of health services by NGOs and the wellbeing of IDPs ($r = .343, n = 240, P < .05$). This means health services has impact on the wellbeing of IDPs.

The findings is confirmed by Asher (2004) that there is a significant correlation between the health, wellbeing and the right to basic health services of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs). IDMC (2012) further corroborated that with the destruction of health facilities and supplies, flight of health workers, and a breakdown in services for displaced persons there is the effect on lowering IDPs general wellbeing. Furthermore, the confirmation of this finding was established by World Health Organisation (2005) that mortality rates in the IDPs camps are above emergency thresholds hence the need for supply and maintenance of health facilities within the camp to sustain their wellbeing.

Implications for Social Work

- i. Professional Social Workers, who are likely to be on the field with the NGOs, should realise that the NGOs can be strengthen and made committed to ensure that the rights of internally displaced persons are protected. This could be achieved by setting standards for addressing security, forms of education and health education especially sexual and other forms of violence against the displaced persons.
- ii. Violators of IDPs right should be brought to justice.
- iii. Social workers become aware that the dignity of all the IDPs who have been forced to leave their homes and at great risk to themselves and the new communities they find themselves are to be protected through the intervention of the NGOs with the ultimate aim of guaranteeing their well-being.
- iv. Professional Social Workers become informed that people should be treated with dignity and respect in IDP camps, strengthen community and social interdependence and, above all, involve IDPs in all decision-making over their futures especially as related to security, food provision and education.
- v. Professional Social Workers should be made to provide a focused strategy that supports vulnerable groups within the IDP camps such as unaccompanied children and young people, older people and those with health issues so as to endow their wellbeing.
- vi. For Social work educators and researchers this research will assist in developing social work models that will support refugees in isolated or life threatening situations where the researched variables are not available. This includes assistance for food and water, protection and security, educational facilities and health services.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The findings conclude that the provision of food and water, protection and security, educational training, and health services are germane to the well-being of Internally Displaced Persons in the communities which host them, and the communities to which they will eventually return to. As a result of the findings and conclusion in this study, the following recommendations are made:

Social workers should advocate and ensure that the protection and wellbeing of IDPs through education are guaranteed. That Non-Governmental Organisations make educational services intervention, one of their utmost intervention strategies. This will help the IDP children to be gainfully engaged, rather than engaging in anti-social behaviours and focusing on their present state of displacement. The provision of such quality education can help to protect IDP children by:

- providing a safe space for children to spend time and feel relaxed for their wellbeing
- teach skills and knowledge to children to protect themselves from exploitation, health risks, gender-based violence, land mines, and other risks
- support children's psychosocial well-being through counselling and other interventions
- provide sites where children can receive other support such as vaccinations

Social workers should advocate for better health in IDPs camps because of its centrality to human happiness and well-being. The provision of good health facilities makes an important contribution to economic progress, as healthy populations live longer and are more productive thereby looking for better days on their return to their ancestral homes.

Social workers should be engaged in issues relating to displacement by providing psycho-education and trauma counselling for the traumatised Internally Displaced Persons, so as to bring them back to normal functioning.

Social workers in collaboration with Non-Governmental Organisations should ensure good and equitable distributions provision of food, water and housing for Internally Displaced Persons should in their respective camps to reduce mortality and morbidity rates. This can be achieved by the involvement of social workers on committees' overseeing the management and activities in the camps.

Social workers hand-in-hand with Non-Governmental Organisations should work closely with security agencies to seek for the protection of the camps. Social workers can serve as informants for the agencies through the use of interviews or focus group discussion with the IDPs for information regarding on issues that are important for peaceful environment in the camps.

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Self-efficacy, test of anxiety and examination malpractices in Ogun state

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Abstract

The study examined self-efficacy self-efficacy, test of anxiety and examination malpractices among secondary school students in Ogun State, Nigeria.

Three instruments on Examination Malpractice Questionnaire (EMQ), General Self-efficacy (GSE) scale and Test Anxiety Inventory (TAI) were used in the study. The instruments were administered to 210 randomly selected students from a stratified sample of three schools in Odeda Local Government Area of Ogun State, whereby 70 students were randomly selected from the population of SS 1 students of each school. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to answer research questions one and two, while Independent Sample t-test was used to answer research questions three and four and regression estimation technique was used to analyze research question five. The result showed that there was a significant negative relationship between self-efficacy self-efficacy ($r=-0.824$, $p<0.05$) and examination malpractice. It was also evident that, there was no significant relationship between test of anxiety ($r=0.074$, $p>0.05$) and examination malpractice. Also, the level of examination malpractice among secondary school students differs significantly across gender ($Df=198$, $N=200$, $t=2.477$, $P<.05$). The result also showed that, the level of examination malpractice among secondary school students differs significantly across age group ($Df=197$, $N=200$, $t=-11.445$, $P<.05$). Finally, a joint effect of self-efficacy self-efficacy, test anxiety gender and age ($r=0.834$, $R\text{-square}=0.690$) on examination malpractice was found among secondary school students.

Keywords: Self-efficacy, Test of Anxiety, Gender, Age, examination malpractice

Introduction

Examinations remain the best tool for an objective assessment and evaluation of what learners have achieved after a period of schooling and as such any action that undermines examinations poses a great threat to the validity and reliability of examination results and certification (Furo, 2015). Students see examinations as wars of survival and cheating as an effective means of winning the war because it remains the only means of obtaining certificates and the sole indices of educational growth (Isangedighi, 2007). Cheating, examination malpractice or other form of

examination misconduct undermines examinations and poses a great threat to the validity and reliability of examination results and certification (Furo, 2015). Examination malpractice is fast eroding the culture of hard work, academic excellence, honesty, decency in the present generation of youths in different institutions of learning. Its long terms effect is wrong placement in schools and employment of unskilled workers into various sectors of the economy (Joshua, Ekpoh, Edet, Joshua, & Obo, 2011). Examination malpractice include any of the following, impersonation, leakage, swapping of scripts, smuggling of answer scripts into examination halls, dubbing (direct copying of answers to questions and taking into examination rooms), results/certificate forgery and verbal or physical assault on examination administrators. It may also include mass cheating of students or a form of malpractice called “sorting” which involves alteration of examination grades with the use of money (Janet & Maureen, 2014).

There is array of literature on the factors responsible for examination malpractice in Nigeria (Animasahun & Ogunniran, 2014). According to Cornelius-Ukpepi, Ndifon and Enuokoha, (2012) the decision to cheat is traceable to pupils’ self-efficacy, the ability of students to perform in a difficult situation or carry out a difficult task. Pupils with low academic self-efficacy and low achievement need culminate in low self-esteem will find it difficult to resist cheating when faced with difficult tasks such as examination (Cornelius-Ukpepi *et al.*, 2012). Students who have low self-concept tend to encounter difficulties in almost every area. Low self-concept learners have a high level of anxiety, encounter difficulty in making friends, adjust less easily to school and tend to be hampered in school achievement (Ikediashi, 2010). Self-efficacy comprises beliefs people have about their capability to bring about particular outcomes. It is the confidence a person has in bringing about a specific outcome (Efklides, 2011). Biehler (1978) noted that students who attain high grades, develop positive self-concept and self-confidence and are less likely to indulge in cheating in examination whereas those who could not obtain high grades develop a sense of failure and rejection. The implication is that they may resort to all measures to ensure achievement.

In another perspective, Onuoha and Nwafor (2005) identified fear and anxiety experienced by the learners as factors associated with examination malpractice. Neils (1996) see anxiety resulting from the high stake and competitive nature of academic activities as being responsible for academic dishonesty. He stated that, such anxiety may be at the point of entry or graduation. Most students at different levels of education wish to come top of their class because of parental, peer, or self-induced aspirations and expectations which often placed them under undue strong pressure to achieve at a higher level than they can, resulting in strong anxiety dynamic. Anxiety is used so widely and is said to be a general feeling of fear and apprehension whereby an individual anticipates some dreadful happening not objectively predictable from his actual circumference (Nwamuo, 2005). Test anxiety on the other hand is seen to be a type of performance anxiety, that is, a feeling someone might have in a situation where performance really counts or when the pressure is on to do well (Nwamuo & Ihekwebaba, 2014). Anxiety is known to have both positive and negative impact on the behavior of a person depending on the level exhibited (Bette, 2014). Moderate anxiety serves as a driving force to motivate a person to work harder to attain set goals. Student preparing for examination require some moderate level of anxiety to give him the propensity to study harder (Bernstein, Alison, Penner, Roy & Wickens, 1994). This gives an indication that he has a task to accomplish that may not be easy but possible with adequate preparation. But when anxiety becomes high, it can be threatening both to the health of the person and the behavior that the person may exhibit (Bette, 2014).

The performance of every individual is not equal, due to a lot of variability and dispersions. The variability cannot be attributed to a single factor, but it is the outcome of a number of factors such as intelligence, study habits, self-concept, creativity, aptitude interests, socio economic factors, area etc. Along with these is the gender of an individual which is also an influential factor on Academic achievement (Bakare, 2012). Different views exist as to which sex involves most in examination malpractices. Lobel and Levanon (1988) argue that more males engage in examination malpractices than the females while Leming (1980) believes that there is more female involvement in examination malpractice than male. While tracing the mode of examination malpractice between the sexes, Oredein (2008) argued empirically that girls find it easy to inscribe information on any part of their body like thighs, baby pampers, purses and palms than their male counterpart. Cognitive development and maturity (which are associated with age) are necessary for a worthwhile performance of students. Age of the individual, as it increases usually affects the various developmental changes and also affects every area of human performance (Sharp, 2005). Maturation of the learner and exposure to different situations is a determining factor whether the student will involve himself or herself in examination malpractice (Amamize, 2003)

In the Nigerian educational system, the issue of examination malpractice has become endemic (Furo, 2015). It has now become a contemporary shame (Nwadiani, 2005). This is because it has greatly ridiculed the products and certificate churned out (Edukugbo, 2006). Nigeria is now graded with reliability of half-baked graduates, low productivity and poor job performance, certificate racketeering and qualification inflation (Nwaba & Nwaba, 2005). Although examination malpractice attracts ugly penalties in the country such as rustication, it nevertheless fails to increase in strength and sophistication (Isangedighi, 2007). The incidence of examination misconduct in Nigeria has become so widespread that there is almost no examination anywhere at all levels of the formal school system, without one form of sharp misconduct or the other (Folarin, 2013; Oluremi, 2014). Because the situation is worst in Nigeria, the country occupies the number one position in the world's examination malpractice index (Omeri, 2012). The most disturbing aspect of it all is that parents, teachers and leaders who are supposed to be actively involved in eradicating examination misconduct are instead aiding and abetting it in one way or the other, thereby increasing its' tendencies among students (Aderogba, 2011, Okorodudu, 2013). The menace is a cause of worry for all stakeholders as well as adherents of moral and ethical uprightness in the Nigerian society. For instance, Joshua, Ekpoh, Edet, Joshua, and Obo, (2011) noted that for every 100 candidates in the examination, 16-17 of them were caught cheating most of which are not even recorded and reported.

Against the analytical background, while some of the existing studies on examination malpractice have either focused attention on the prevalence, forms, trends, nature causes and effect and possible solution to examination malpractice (Janet & Maureen; 2014; Akinrefon, Ikpah & Bamigbala, 2016; Akaranga & Ongong, 2013; Emaikwu, 2012). Others dwell on the relationship between self-efficacy and examination malpractice (Okorodudu, 2012; Bette, 2014; Cornelius-Ukpepi, *et al.*, 2012; Ikediashi, 2010). In addition, some of the existing studies were on the relationship between test of anxiety and examination malpractice (Nyamwange, Ondima and Onderi, 2013; Ossai, 2011; Nwamuo & Ihekweba, 2014) while few of these studies looked at the role of self-efficacy on examination malpractice (Jadesola, 2002; Sharp, 2005; Nwamuo & Ihekweba, 2014; Okorodudu, 2013). Based on the length of this review, no single empirical study have documented the effect of self-efficacy, test of anxiety on the prediction of examination malpractice among secondary school students in Ogun State. Against this

background, this study is motivated to examine self-efficacy, test of anxiety and examination malpractice among secondary school students. The study specifically analyzes the relationship between self-efficacy and examination malpractice; the relationship between test of anxiety and examination malpractice; examine the influence of gender on examination malpractice, investigate the influence of different age group on examination malpractice and examine the joint contribution of self-efficacy, test of anxiety gender and age on the prediction of examination malpractice among secondary school students.

In the light of empirical and theoretical literature underpinning the relationship among the self-efficacy, test of anxiety, gender, age and examination malpractices, the study poses the following hypotheses:

- H₀₁:** There is no significant relationship between self-efficacy and examination malpractice among secondary school students.
- H₀₂:** There is no significant relationship between test of anxiety and examination malpractice among secondary school students.
- H₀₃:** Male and female students do not significantly differ in terms of their participation in examination malpractice in secondary school
- H₀₄:** Examination malpractice tendency do not differ across different age group among secondary school students
- H₀₅:** Self-efficacy, test of anxiety gender and age do not have a significant joint contribution to prediction of examination malpractice among secondary school students.

Methodology

This study focused attention on self-efficacy, test anxiety and examination malpractice among secondary school students in Ogun State. However, due to the time, money and other limiting factors, the study was limited to only three schools in Saki West Local Government Area. This study utilized the ex-post facto survey design. The choice of this design was because the study is conducted to gather information already existing among the population under study.

Population and Sampling Process

The population of the study consists of all the seven hundred and fifty (750) secondary school students (350 males and 400 females) drawn from a stratified sample of three schools based on a purposive sample of all the secondary schools in Saki West Local Government Area of Ogun State, South West Nigeria. The population was limited to only three secondary schools in only one local government area of the state because of the time, money and other constraining factors to the enumeration of secondary school students in the state. The simple random sampling technique was used to select a sample size of two hundred and ten (210) SS 1 students out of a total population of three hundred and ninety five (395) in the three schools using the Yaro Yamani Sample selection technique but after administration of the instrument, two hundred (200) participants that completed the questionnaire correctly were used in the data analysis. The simple random sampling technique was used because it allowed for a fair means of selecting a sample from a given population since every member have equal opportunity of being selected. The choice of students who are fresher in the senior school level of secondary school is because they are relatively inexperienced hence, they freely exhibit symptoms of examination anxiety and attitude towards examination malpractices. As students' progress in academic years those with inappropriate examination anxiety level and notorious attitude towards examination malpractices may either drop out or are expelled or they improve (Ossai, 2012). This justify, the

reason why most studies on examination anxiety and examination malpractice focus on freshmen (see Okorodudu & Ossai, 2004; Diaz, Glass, Arnkoff & TanofskyKraff 2001)

Instrumentation

The instrument was in two parts. Part one comprised the demographic information of the participants such as age, self-esteem and sex, and Religion. Part two of the instrument had three sub units or sections: Section A consists of eleven item statements on examination malpractice Section B consists of item on self-efficacy and section C is on item on test of anxiety. In order to measure examination malpractice the original 24 item Examination Malpractice Questionnaire (EMQ) which elicit responses on students' personal perception and their opinion on the perception of significant others about examination malpractices developed by Alutu and Aluede (2006) was used. The instrument was validated and standardized through a test re-test method on six (6) weeks interval and the test-retest correlation coefficient(r) was 0.84 indicating that the instrument is a valid and reliable measure of examination malpractice. The instrument used to measure the participants self-efficacy was the General Self-efficacy (GSE) scale designed by Sshwarzer and Jerusalem (1995) with author reported Cronbach's alphas ranging between 0.79 and 0.90. The scale is on four point format where; not all true=1, hardly true=2, moderately true=3 and exactly true= 4. Test-retest re-validation of the scale for construct validity and reliability over a period of six (6) weeks showed a correlation coefficient(r) of 0.79. These indices were indicative of high construct validity and reliability. Face and content validity were ascertained by three experts in educational measurement and evaluation. To test the level of anxiety of the students when writing examinations, the twenty (20) item Test Anxiety Inventory (TAI) by Spielberger (1980) on four-point format with strongly Agree (AS) = 4 points; Agree (A) = 3 points, Agree (A) points, Disagree (D) = 2 points; and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1 was utilized. The author reported a Cronbach's alpha of 0.71 for the construct validity and internal reliability of the scale. The instrument was also re-validated based on a test re-test method on six (6) weeks interval and the test-retest correlation coefficient(r) was 0.81 indicating that the instrument is a valid and reliable measure of examination anxiety.

Method of Analysis

In the analysis of first two research questions which are to examine the relationship between self-efficacy and examination malpractice and test of anxiety and examination malpractice the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) analysis was employed. Correlation analysis provides a basis for determining the degree of association between two variables. Though, it does not allow for cause effect interpretation, it gives an indication of prediction of outcome in the relation between two or more variables. In the analysis of the third and fourth research questions which are to examine the influence of gender on examination malpractice and the influence of different age group on examination malpractice the Independent Sample t-test result on was employed while the fifth research question which was to examine the contribution of the independent variables on the prediction of examination malpractice was analysed using the regression estimation technique.

Results

The section of the study presents the result of the data analysis while drawing appropriate inference to answer each of the five research questions generated in the study.

Hypothesis one: In the analysis of the relationship between self-efficacy and examination malpractice among secondary school students in Ogun State, the study used the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC). The result of the correlation analysis is presented in table 1 as follow:

Table 1. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Results

Variable	N	$\frac{\sum x}{\sum y}$	$\frac{\sum x^2}{\sum y^2}$	$\sum xy$	r-value	Sig.
Examination Malpractice	200	8.156	.041	1.237	-.824(**)	.000
Self-efficacy		.276	.001			

Source: Author Field Survey, 2019

As shown in Table 1, the Correlation coefficient ($r=-0.824$, $p<0.05$) is positive and statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected in favour of the alternate hypothesis. This means that there is significant negative relationship between self-efficacy and examination malpractice among secondary school students in Ogun State. It can therefore be deduced that, examination malpractice tendency reduce with increase in the level of self-efficacy of Students which implies that students with low self-efficacy engage more in examination malpractice compare to study with high level of self-efficacy.

Hypothesis two: This investigates relationship between test of anxiety and examination malpractice among secondary school students in Ogun State. To answer this research question, the study used the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC). The result of the correlation analysis is presented in table 2 as follow:

Table 2. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Results

Variable	N	$\frac{\sum x}{\sum y}$	$\frac{\sum x^2}{\sum y^2}$	$\sum xy$	r-value	Sig.
Examination Malpractice	200	8.156	0.041	0.563	0.074	0.295
Test of Anxiety		7.015	0.035			

Source: Author Field Survey, 2019

The results in Table 2 showed that there is no a significant relationship between test of anxiety ($r=0.074$, $p>0.05$) and examination malpractice among secondary school students in Ogun State at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. It can therefore be deduce that examination malpractice tendency does not change with changes in the level of examination anxiety which implies that student engage in examination malpractice irrespective of their level of examination anxiety.

Hypothesis three: This examines the difference in examination malpractice of male and female secondary school students in Ogun State. This comparison was carried out using the independent student t-test method of analysis. The result of the correlation analysis is presented in table 3 as follow:

Table 3: Independent Sample T-Test Result

Variables	Gender	N	Mean	St. Dev	DF	T-value	Sig
Examination Malpractice	Male	154	0.4338	0.20033	198	2.477	0.014
	Female	46	0.3507	0.19835			

Source: Author Field Survey, 2019

The result in Table 3 indicates that, the level of examination malpractice among secondary school students differs significantly across gender (Df=198, N=200, t=2.477, P<.05). The mean score of male students (0.4338) in examination malpractice is significantly higher than the mean score of female students (0.3507). Hence, the result showed that, there is a significant difference among gender in terms of their participation in examination malpractice among secondary school student in Ogun State. Hence, it is evident that male students have greater tendency of being involve in examination malpractice than their female counterpart.

Hypothesis Four: This examine whether there is any difference in examination malpractice of secondary school students of different age group in Ogun State. This comparison was carried out using the independent student t-test method of analysis. The result of the correlation analysis is presented in table 4 as follow:

Table 4: Independent Sample T-Test Result

Variables	Gender	N	Mean	St. Dev	DF	T-value	Sig
Examination Malpractice	10-15yrs	85	0.2659	0.13780	197	-11.445	0.000
	16-20yrs	114	0.5227	0.16922			

Source: Author Field Survey, 2019

The result in Table 4 showed that the level of examination malpractice among secondary school students differs significantly across the two different age group (Df=197, N=200, t=-11.445, P<.05). The mean score of students who are between the ages of sixteen and twenty years (0.5227) in examination malpractice is significantly higher than the mean score of students who are between the ages of ten and fifteen years (0.2659). Hence, the result showed that, there is a significant difference across different age group in terms of participation in examination malpractice among secondary school student in Ogun State. Hence, it is evident that older students have higher tendency of being involve in examination malpractice than their younger counterpart.

Hypothesis Five: This investigates the joint contribution of self-efficacy, test anxiety gender and age to the prediction of examination malpractices among secondary school students in Ogun State using the regression analysis. The result of the correlation analysis is presented in table 5 as follow:

Table 5: Summary of regression Results

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	R	R Square	Adj. RSquare
Regression	5.676	4	1.419	111.577	.000(a)	.834(a)	.696	.690
Residuals	2.480	195	.013					
Total	8.156	199						

a Predictors: (Constant), test of anxiety, self-efficacy, gender, Age

Source: Author Field Survey, 2019

Table 5 indicates that the independent variables self-efficacy, test anxiety gender and age are joint predictor of examination malpractice among secondary school students. In the table the multiple correlation coefficient r is 0.834 and that of the multiple adjusted R-square 0.690. This implies that, 69% of the variations in examination malpractice of the students is accounted for by all the five predictors when considered jointly while the remaining 31% variations in examination malpractice is accounted for by other variable outside the model. The ANOVA F-ratio ($F=111.577$, $Df=4/195$, $P<.05$) was also significant. This implies that the overall model have the adequate goodness of fit.

Discussion

Hypothesis One: This hypothesis stated that; “There is no a significant relationship between self-efficacy and examination malpractice among secondary school students”. The result of the data analysis revealed that there is significant negative relationship between self-efficacy ($r=-0.824$, $p<0.05$) and examination malpractice among secondary school students in Ogun State. By implication, examination malpractice tendency reduce with increase in the level of self-efficacy of Students which implies that students with low self-efficacy engage more in examination malpractice compare to study with high level of self-efficacy . The finding is consistent with the result in the study conducted by Okorodudu (2012) on the relationship between parental motivation, self-efficacy and students’ examination dishonesty. The outcomes of responses of 1000 respondents showed parental motivation and self-efficacy highly predicted students’ examination dishonesty. It is also in line with the result of Bette (2014) on the predictive influence of academic self-concept and motivational arousals on examination cheating tendency among senior secondary students (SS III) in Cross River State Nigeria. The results of the findings revealed a significant relationship between students’ academic self-concept and their cheating tendency in examination and a significant relationship between motivational arousals and cheating tendencies in examination among students.

Hypothesis Two: This hypothesis stated that; “There is no a significant relationship between test of anxiety and examination malpractice among secondary school students”. The result of the analysis showed that there is no a significant relationship between test of anxiety ($r=0.074$, $p>0.05$) and examination malpractice among secondary school students in Ogun State at 0.05 level of significance. By implication, the result showed that, examination malpractice tendency does not change with changes in the level of examination anxiety which implies that student

engage in examination malpractice irrespective of their level of examination anxiety. The findings disagree with the result in the study conducted by Nyamwange, Ondima and Onderi (2013) on whether competition, poor preparation, poor invigilation, inadequate facilities, ineffective teaching and anxiety had any influence on student cheating in secondary school examinations. The results of the study revealed that the major factors influencing examination cheating include: examination anxiety, lack of facilities, stiff competition, poor preparations, and inadequate invigilation of the examinations. The result also fails to give credence the findings of Ossai (2011) on the relationship between examination anxiety and students' attitude towards examination malpractices in tertiary institutions in Delta State. It was found that there is a positive relationship between examination anxiety and attitude towards cheating in examinations. Students who possessed high examination anxiety were more predisposed towards cheating in examinations.

Hypothesis Three: This tested whether there is a significant difference between male and female students' participation in examination malpractice in secondary school. The analysis showed that the level of examination malpractice among secondary school students differs significantly across gender ($Df=198$, $N=200$, $t=2.477$, $P<.05$). This result by implication suggests that, male students have greater tendency of being involve in examination malpractice than their female counterpart. The finding is consistent with the result in the study conducted by Maureen (2016) on the relationship between stress characteristics (academic, financial and personal social) and cheating tendencies among primary school learners. Result of the Pearson product moment correlation revealed significant relationship between stress (academic, financial personal social) and cheating tendencies of pupils. Result also suggested that sex difference influences stress and cheating tendencies of pupils. The finding also corroborates the result in the study conducted by Nwamuo and Ihekweba (2014) on the level of test anxiety among students in tertiary institutions using Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri, Imo State as a reference point. Result showed significant dependence of students' level of test anxiety on gender and age cohort but independence on the students' school of study.

Hypothesis Four: This tested whether there is a significant difference across different age group in terms of participation in examination malpractice among secondary school students. The analysis showed that the level of examination malpractice among secondary school students differs significantly across the two different age group ($Df=197$, $N=200$, $t=-11.445$, $P<.05$). The implication of this result is that older students have higher tendency of being involve in examination malpractice than their younger counterpart. The finding is also consistent with the result in the study conducted by Nwamuo and Ihekweba (2014) on the level of test anxiety among students in tertiary institutions using Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri, Imo State as a reference point. Result showed significant dependence of students' level of test anxiety on gender and age cohort but independence on the students' school of study.

Hypothesis five: This hypothesis stated that; "Self-efficacy, test of anxiety gender and age do not have a significant joint contribution to prediction of examination malpractice among secondary school students". The result of the analysis showed that the independent variables self-efficacy, test anxiety gender and age jointly predict examination malpractice among secondary school students ($r=0.834$, $R\text{-square}=0.690$). The implication of this result is that, 69% of the variations in examination malpractice of the students is accounted for by all the five predictors when considered jointly while the remaining 31% variations in examination malpractice is accounted for by other variable outside the model. The finding is consistent with the result in the study conducted by Nyamwange, Ondima and Onderi (2013) on whether competition, poor

preparation, poor invigilation, inadequate facilities, ineffective teaching and anxiety had any influence on student cheating in secondary school examinations. The results of the study revealed that the major factors influencing examination cheating include: examination anxiety, lack of facilities, stiff competition, poor preparations, and inadequate invigilation of the examinations.

Conclusion and Recommendations

On the basis of the result, it was clear that the low level of students' self-efficacy motivate them to engage more in examination malpractice. In addition, examination malpractice tendency does not change with changes in the level of examination anxiety. Also, there was evidence that, male student involve more in examination malpractice compare to their female counterpart. More also, there was evidence that, older students have higher tendency of being involve in examination malpractice than their younger counterpart. Finally, self-efficacy, test anxiety gender and age contribute jointly and significantly to the prediction of examination malpractice among secondary school students.

In the light of these findings, there is need for a collaborative role of the teachers, parent, government and counselors in the sensitization of the students on ethical values of self-worth, dignity of labour, integrity and personal responsibility. There is need for the society to shift their emphasis away from materialism and paper qualification as the only yardstick for appointment into the position of authority and encourage hard work as such emphasis has been associated with various misconduct in the process of acquiring educational qualification and material wealth. Hence, the societal effort and reward framework should be directed to encourage hard work, dignity and honesty. Not only is the need to ensure that only qualified and competent teacher are employed, but there is a need to ensure that the teachers are morally upright such that they can be a good role models in terms of ethical values of self-worth, dignity of labour, integrity and personal responsibility.

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Teachers' preferences and perception of effectiveness of teaching methods on secondary schools students' academic performance in Lagos state

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Abstract

This study examined preferences of teaching methods and their perceived impacts by secondary school teachers on students' performance in Lagos State. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. Questionnaire was used as the instrument for data collection. A sample size of fifty (50) teachers was selected for the study from the population of 250 within the education 11 District in Lagos state. The data collected was analyzed using mean.

The findings revealed that the prevalent teaching methods adopted by most teachers are discussion method, questioning method, demonstration method, peer tutoring method and field trip/excursion method. These teaching methods enabled the students to explore problem solving strategies and also develop the psychomotor skills of the students.

It is therefore, recommended that teachers should ensure they are familiar with appropriate teaching methods to use in teaching students.

Keywords: Teaching methods, Academic performance, Pedagogy.

Introduction

The poor performance of secondary school students in Lagos was a major concern for education stakeholders. Among these methods may be teaching methods used by school teachers. Most of the current literature that teaches teaching and learning in schools assumes that the teaching method has a direct impact on student performance. As part of school accountability for student achievement, teachers are required to become "highly qualified" in their area of study. The researchers showed a link between teachers using the preferred classroom teaching methods and their relationship to student learning.

Teaching methods are used to convey knowledge to students. They are the means by which the teacher tries to convey the required learning or experience. The choice of a specific method of teaching by the teacher is determined by a number of factors, including the content to be taught, the goals the teacher plans to achieve from the teaching and learning resources, the teacher's ability and willingness to improvise if traditional teaching methods are not available, assessment and follow- (2007).

Each student learns and responds to information uniquely (Chang, 2010). Teaching and learning methods improve student achievement (Stitt-Gohdes, 2001; Henson, 2004 & Hou, 2007). The Zepp (2004) study indicated that adapting student learning styles to teaching methods for teachers can lead to an improvement in academic achievement. Use the information obtained from evaluating teaching and teaching methods to help teachers adjust their teaching methods to accommodate different learning preferences, resulting in improved student test scores.

The methods used in teaching vary from country to country, depending on the information or skills being taught and also influenced by the student's attitude and enthusiasm. Various studies have been conducted on teaching methods, for example Asikhia (2010), found that teacher qualification and environmental factors for students do not affect the performance of weak students but the methods of teaching teachers affect weak academic performance. Moreover, teaching methods are dictated by the teaching method, for example, where English is used, the teaching method must be more interactive than negative (Pillar and Skilling, 2005). It was also said that classroom teachers need to know more about effective strategies for teaching different materials (Thomson, 2004). The commonly used method of teaching, especially in developing countries, is teacher-oriented (Guloba, Wokodola, and Bategeka, 2010), which is seen to be somewhat ineffective in knowledge transfer.

These methods are no longer used in other provinces. Lifelong learning is increasingly recognized as an increasingly teaching method in educational institutions as a tool to address deficiencies in traditional teaching methods, as their curricula do not encourage students to participate in the learning process (Teo and Wong, 2000). However, more recently, there has been an argument in the education industry to adopt a paradigm shift that focuses on the specialist (Ndirangu, 2007), while other think tanks call for participatory approaches to teaching (Sajjad, 2011).

The teaching method of the teacher and its impact on students is one of the most important aspects of the educational process, but the most neglected. Educational research reveals this through direct observation of teachers and students within the classroom. Privacy and independence enable each teacher to manage and organize classes in the way he or she prefers to deal with them. Personal relationships between teachers and students are involved in this teaching style and attitudes relate to learning. The method of teaching expressive control of students and management of classroom activities as well as negative or positive feelings towards teaching. Otherwise, this teaching method is also related to a sense of trust in students and understanding of the purpose of education in general.

Cornsten and Miller (2000), have categorized two types of teaching styles and they are expressive teaching methods and instrumental teaching method. Expressive method refers to the emotional relationship created by the teacher to the student or the class as a whole, including warmth, authority, sympathy, trust and some emotional aspects shown by the teacher.

In selecting teaching method, the teacher's analytical ability comes to play, considering the situation at hand. There are some factors that will guide the teacher's choice of method to use in teaching a particular lesson; such factors include: The subject matter, instructional objectives, the learner, the teacher, Time, instructional material and the classroom environment.

The academic performance of a child could be defined as the learning outcomes of the child. This includes the knowledge, skills and ideas, acquired and obtained through their course of study within and outside the classroom situation (Epunam, 2000). It is the outcome of determination, hard work, of student in academic pursuit. Pandney (2008) defined academic achievement as the performance of the pupils in the subjects they study in the school. This

determines the pupils' status in the class. Academic performance refers to excellence in all academic discipline, in a class as well as extra-curricular activities. It includes excellence in sporting behaviour, it includes excellence in sporting behaviour, confidence, communication skills, and others. Steinberger (2005) posit that academic performance encompasses students' ability and performance; it is multidimensional; it is intricately related to human growth and cognitive, emotional and social physical development; it reflects the whole child; it is not related to a single instance, but occurs across time and levels, through a student's life in public school and into post-secondary years and working life. Academic performance refers to how well a student is accomplishing his tasks and studies.

Academic performance in school is evaluated in a number of ways. For regular grading student students demonstrate their knowledge by taking written and oral tests, performing presentations, submission of homework and participating in class activities and discussion. Teachers evaluate in the form of assignment, test and examination to describe how well a student has done. Poor academic achievement is a performance that is adjudged by the examiner and some significant others. Studies have shown that there is a relationship between teaching methods and students' academic performance, for example it has been found that teachers who used a specific style of evidence-based teaching and operate within a developmental learning paradigm had an increase effect on student learning outcome (Griffin, 2007) thus teaching methods play an important role in producing good students' performance.

Some of the teaching methodologies that enhances the learning of students include; Role plays, case Studies, projects based on Research, learning in teams, group discussions, visits to industries, audiovisual aids and problem-based methods of learning, seminars and workshops, PowerPoint presentations, written exercises, Field trips, Problem-Based Learning, Seminars and Workshops etc.

The hope of every serious-minded student is to obtain higher grades in educational activities while in school but this hope is dashed as a result of the teaching methods employed by the teachers. These challenges have resulted in some of them not getting the required subjects for them to get admission in universities.

Against this backdrop, this study, examined preferences of teaching methods and their perceived impacts by secondary school teachers on students' performance in Lagos State.

Specifically, this study

- determined the prevalent teaching methods mostly adopted by teachers
- ascertained benefits of the teaching methods to the students
- established the determinants of the choice of teachers teaching methods
- explored the teaching methods that can be effectively used in teaching in order to increase students' academic performance

Research Questions

In consideration of the purpose of the study, the following questions will guide the study:

1. What are the prevalent teaching methods mostly adopted by teachers?
2. What are the influences of the teaching methods on the academic performance of students?
3. What are the determinants of the choice of teachers teaching methods?
4. What are the perceived teaching methods that can be effectively used in teaching in order to increase in students' academic performance.

Method

The study adopted a survey research design. This was aimed to describe and interpret the teaching methods and students’ academic performance. The study covered junior secondary schools within the Education District IV Yaba, Lagos. The population for this study consists of all junior secondary school under Education District IV Yaba, Lagos.

The sample size was a representative of all junior school teachers under Education District IV Lagos state. This study used fifty (50) teachers in public junior secondary schools within Education District IV. The sampling technique used for the study was simple random sampling technique.

The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire, titled Teacher's questionnaire on Teaching methods and student's academic performance. The questionnaire consists of thirty-two (32) structured items divided into two major section labeled A and B. Section A contained three (3) items which seek for bio-data of the respondents while section B represented the main body of the questionnaire having twenty-eight (28) generated statements. Each item of the questionnaire was designed using 4-point scales method. These include Strongly Agree= SA, Agree =A, Disagree= D, Strongly Disagree= SD.

Data Analysis

Percentage, Frequency table and mean method were used to compute and analyse the data obtained from the questionnaires in order to provide answers to the research questions.

$$SA = 4, A = 3, D = 2, SD = 1 = 10$$

$$\text{The mean value therefore } X = \frac{4+3+2+1}{4} = 2.5$$

Therefore, any mean result below 2.5 was disagreed and rejected while from 2.5 upward was agreed and accepted.

Research question one (1): what are the prevalence teaching methods mostly adopted by teachers?

Table 1 Mean responses of respondents on the prevalent teaching methods adopted by teachers.

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	SD	D	X	C	Remark
1	Discussion method	20	25	2	3	3.26	2.5	Accept
2	Questioning method	10	17	10	13	2.54	2.5	Accept
3	Role playing method	5	9	16	20	2.06	2.5	Reject
4	Simulation method	4	3	13	30	1.96	2.5	Reject
5	Demonstration method	23	17	4	6	3.18	2.5	Accept
6	Inquiring method/discovering method	4	2	15	29	1.9	2.5	Reject
7	Case study method	2	1	37	10	1.36	2.5	Reject
8	Peer tutoring method	18	21	6	5	3.02	2.5	Accept
9	Field trip/ Excursion method	24	19	2	5	3.3	2.5	Accept
10	Debating method	2	4	20	24	1.76	2.5	Reject

Key: X = mean response of all respondents, C = Cut- off point, N = 50

From the table above, respondents affirmed that the prevalent teaching methods adopted by teachers are discussion method, questioning method, demonstration method, peer tutoring method and field trip/excursion method.

Research question two (2): what are the benefits of the teaching methods to the students?

Table 2. Mean responses of respondents on influences of the benefits of the teaching methods to the students.

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	SD	D	X	C	Remark
1	An effective teaching method aids the students' involvement in Business Studies class	20	27	0	3	3.34	2.5	Accept
2	It triggers the critical thinking of the students	18	16	6	10	2.92	2.5	Accept
3	It arouses the interest and curiosity of the students	22	15	4	9	3.02	2.5	Accept
4	An appropriate teaching method enables the students to explore problem solving strategies in Business Studies	15	12	9	14	2.66	2.5	Accept
5	It helps the students to practice the skills necessary for their successful adult life	17	19	7	5	2.66	2.5	Accept
6	It helps in developing the psychomotor skills of the students	13	22	6	9	2.84	2.5	Accept

Key: X = mean responses of all the respondents, C = Cut- off point, N =50

From the table above, the respondents agreed that the prevalent teaching methods such as discussion method, questioning method, demonstration method, peer tutoring method and field trip/ excursion method trigger the critical thinking and arouse the interest and curiosity of the students. They also agreed that these prevalent methods enable the students to explore problem solving strategies and also develop the psychomotor skills of the students. The table also revealed that the prevalent teaching methods aid the students' involvement in class.

Research question three (3): what are the determinants of the teachers' choices of the teaching methods?

Table 3. Mean of responses on the determinants of the teachers' choices of teaching methods

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	SD	D	X	C	REMARK
1	Instructional objectives	23	17	2	8	3.2	2.5	Accept
2	Availability of teaching and learning aids	19	21	4	6	3.1	2.5	Accept
3	Cultural aspect of the society	12	17	8	13	2.7	2.5	Accept
4	The age of the learners	21	25	1	3	3.3	2.5	Accept
5	Psychological needs of the students	15	13	10	12	2.7	2.5	Accept
6	The size of the class	24	18	3	5	3.3	2.5	Accept

Key: X =mean responses of all the respondents, C = Cut- off point, N = 50

From the table above, the respondents affirmed that the determinants of the choice of teaching methods adopted by teachers include instructional objectives of the lesson to be taught, the availability of teaching and learning aids in the school, cultural aspect of the immediate society, the age of the learners to be taught, psychological needs of the learners, the size of the class and quality of in-service training programme attended by the teachers.

Research question four (4): what are the perceived teaching methods that can be effectively used in teaching in order to increase in students' academic performance?

Table 4 Mean of respondents on the perceived teaching methods that can be used to improve students' academic performance

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	SD	D	X	C	REMARK
1	Guided discovery method	4	6	11	19	1.7	2.5	Reject
2	Simulation method	18	15	5	12	2.9	2.5	Accept
3	Field trip/ excursion method	20	20	8	2	3.0	2.5	Accept

4	Group discussion method	15	19	10	6	2.8	2.5	Accept
5	Peer tutoring method	7	10	9	24	2.3	2.5	Reject
6	Debating method	3	8	20	19	1.9	2.5	Reject

Key: X =mean responses of all the respondents, C = Cut- off point, N = 50

From the table above, the result suggested that the academic performance of the students can be improved upon when the teachers adopt simulation method of teaching, engaging students into a group discussion of the lessons to be taught and involving them on a field trip or excursion to get a firsthand information as per the activities of the subject matter discuss in class. And methods such as guided discovery method, peer tutoring method and debating method were rejected as teaching method that can lead to the improvement of learners’ academic performance.

Discussion of findings

The results confirmed that the prevalent teaching method adopted by teachers are discussion method, questioning method, demonstration method, peer tutoring method and field trip/excursion method. This is in alignment with Moore (2004) who investigated the historical teaching methodologies and found three major teaching style approaches discussion approaches, demonstration approach, and excursion approach, he concluded that these approaches have been in use from the late 1970s till date. Weinberg (2003) work on teaching methods also corresponds with the findings of this work. He identified direct (discussion) teaching method and peer teaching method as the prevalent methods adopted by teachers in conveying their subject matters to their students.

This study established that the prevalent teaching methods such as discussion method, questioning method, demonstration method, peer tutoring method and field trip/ excursion method trigger the critical thinking and arouse the interest and curiosity of the students, it is discovered that these teaching methods enables the students to explore problem solving strategies and also develop the psychomotor skills of the students in business studies, its’ also revealed that the teaching styles aid the students’ involvement in class. This finding is in support to Dressel and Marcus (2000) and Woods (2001) who submitted that discipline based and teacher- centered (excursion and discussion method) encourages students to absorb learning materials They also stated that demonstrations, peer grouping and discussion teaching methods create students with positive learning environment to clarify their understanding and present their ideas

It was revealed that the determinants of the choice of teaching methods adopted by teachers include; instructional objectives of the lesson to be taught, the availability of teaching and learning aids in the school, cultural aspect of the immediate society, the age of the learners to be taught, psychological needs of the learners, the size of the class and quality of in-service training programme attended by the teachers is critical to the learning style and age of those being served by the instruction”. There is an assumption that students learn with different styles, at different speeds, different levels of prior knowledge and different environments when the subject matter is given by way of a variety of teaching strategies (Ndirangu, 2007).

Results showed that the perceived teaching methods that can be used to improve students’ academic performance include simulation method of teaching, engaging students into a group discussion of the lessons to be taught and involving them on a field trip or excursion to get firsthand information as per the activities of the subject matter discuss in class. Several studies conducted on teaching methods in many parts of the world have demonstrated that teaching styles impact students’ performance. For example, in USA (Haas, 2002), Nigeria (Asikia, 2010, Bategeka, 2012) . These studies clearly indicate that teaching method used by the teacher has an

impact on students' performance and medium of instruction also impacts on students' performance (Senkoro, 2004 and Canton, 2007).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the previous discussion, the following conclusions were drawn.

A large number of teachers tend to use discussion method, questioning method, demonstration method, peer tutoring method and field trip/excursion method in their teaching and learning environments.

The study revealed that participation of professional activities (e.g., workshops, training) favor more student-centered approach. Various kinds of professional activities related to teaching and learning would shape teachers' teaching preferences and methods and these activities also provide teachers with specific, practical materials and strategies for giving students systematically more instructional choices in the classroom.

Based on the finding of this research study, the following recommendations were made:

- (a) The teacher should not be discouraged by the population of the students in the class. He/she should be able to maintain a cordial relationship with the students irrespective of the class size since classroom population determines the teaching methods to be adopted.
- (b) The teacher should ensure he/she is familiar with the effective teaching methods such as simulation, field trip /excursion and group discussion teaching methods in other to ensure effective teaching/learning environment in the classroom which will enhance positive academic achievement. He/she should always adopt these methods in his/her day to day lesson.

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Incident of Risky Driving Behaviour and Its Psycho-Social Predictors among Traffic Offenders in Osun State

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Abstract

Accidents are a common phenomenon on Nigerian roads. These are attributed to individual, environmental and contextual factors including excessive speeding, disobeying traffic laws, among others. This study investigates the incident cum pattern of risky driving behaviour and its Psycho-social predictors among traffic offenders in Osun state. The study was a cross-sectional survey design. Multi-stage sampling technique was used to select 283 participants docked in four traffic offenders' tribunal. Driving Behaviour Survey (DBS), Big-five Personality Inventory, Awaritefe Psychological Index (API) and demographic questionnaire were used in data collection. Data was analyzed using the descriptive statistics, t-test for independent samples, multiple regression analysis at $p \leq 0.05$. 75.6% traffic offenders exhibited severe to moderate risky driving behaviour. Personality traits of extraversion ($\beta=.45$; $t= -6.99$); agreeableness ($\beta= -41$; $t = -3.98$, $p<.05$); conscientiousness ($\beta=-.17$; $t = -3.68$, $p<.05$); and openness to experience ($\beta=-.27$; $t= -4.20$), predicted risky driving behaviour, [$F(5, 283) = 87.54$, $R^2 = .61$]. This study concluded that there was high incidence of risky driving behaviour among traffic offenders; Extraversion, Agreeableness personality traits were predictors of risky driving behaviour. Psychological assessment and the use of CBT and Meseron Therapy for behavioural adjustment of traffic offenders were recommended.

Keywords: Personality traits, psycho-behavioural intervention, risky driving behaviour, traffic offenders

Introduction

Risky driving alludes to the use of motor vehicles in a way which exposes self and the public to accident, injury or death (Duhaime.org, 2018), has turned out to be conspicuous and achieve pandemic dimensions in Nigeria. This deviant conduct comprises hazardous or risky driving conduct. In Nigeria, risky driving is the demonstration of driving a motor vehicle in a way that falls far beneath that normal of an experienced and watchful driver and subsequently puts the life of the driver and the lives of other road users in danger (Thisday, 2017). The FRSC (Establishment) Act in its translation segment (i.e. area 30), characterizes unsafe driving as "driving in a way that is risky, dangerous, hazardous, indiscreet, rash, careless, and perilous in

any conditions of the case" (FRSC ACT, 2017). The primary issue being raised is that risky driving behaviour includes neglectful driving and aggressive driving. Aggressive driving conduct is regularly characterized as "any conduct planned to physically, inwardly, or mentally hurt another road user while driving" (Hennessy and Wiesenthal, 2001). The unequivocal practices include: tailgating, weaving through traffic, overtaking (e.g., cutting in unreasonably close before vehicle being overtake), failure to horn, shielding drivers from passing, running stop signs, running against red lights, driving at rates (Tasca, 2000; James & Nahl, 2000).

Given that past investigations have gained ground in distinguishing different indicators for perilous and negative driving practices because of such conduct, the following vital advance is to more readily comprehend the basic social and psychological components of such practices. Driving is a complex and objective coordinated conduct that depends on different higher-orders subjective procedures and hence is enveloped by official capacities (Hayashi et al, 2018). Road mishaps and the related mass losses are one of the difficulties of the human culture that compromise the wellbeing of individuals and force tremendous expenses on the states. The role of human factors in car accidents has prompted extraordinary enthusiasm for distinguishing the social and intellectual factors related with perilous driving practices and negative driving results (e.g., motor vehicle crashes, passing, vehicle fix and captures).

Developing nations have the biggest number of unfortunate casualties because of street mishap and are considered as one of the primary driver of death. The level of wounds and the recurrence of real street mishaps are to such degree that it is known as the "Road carnage". Nigeria is positioned second most astounding in the rate of road accidents among 193 nations of the world. World Health Organization expresses that the aggregate number of death from road mishap remains unsatisfactorily high at 1.24 million every year. In this way, risky driving still is standout amongst the most imperative factors causing road mishaps throughout the world (WHO, 2015). The lists of psychological predictors of dangerous driving are long and involve a series of behaviours and mental states that can result in accidents. Researchers concur that personality can impact how people approach and act in certain driving circumstances. It is trusted that specific identity attributes influenced driver's risky driving. Much more, personality qualities are the fundamental factor for impression of the outcomes of deliberate traffic rules violations. (Richer & Bergeron, 2012), such as aggressive driving (e.g., tailgate other drivers), negative cognition and emotions while driving (e.g., anger, rumination, frustration), and risky driving (e.g, driving above the speed limit; Dula & Ballard, 2003; Willemsen, Dula, Declercq, & Verhaeghe, 2008).

Personality is related to traffic accidents because drivers with certain personality characteristics drive more dangerously. Various ongoing meta-investigations have, with expanding thoroughness, endeavored to join the connection between Big Five personality qualities (i.e., Openness to experience, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Agreeableness, and Neuroticism – OCEAN) and safety behaviour (Clarke & Robertson, 2005; Chrisitan et al., 2009; Beus et al., 2015). There is without a doubt a connection between Big Five personality qualities and safety. Specifically, people who drive more carefully present higher scores in traits as agreeableness, conscientiousness, openness to change, and introversion (Harris et al., 2014). Agreeableness has reliably appeared at be the biggest and most powerful predictor of safe driving conduct. It is speculated that conscientiousness, how organized and mindful we are, also played significant relationship between risky driving behaviour. People with conscientiousness are more likely to drive safely than those with low conscientiousness. Extraversion and neuroticism indicated an important associations with hazardous driving conduct, to such an

extent that the more extraverted and neurotic people are, the almost certain they are to drive dangerously. The connection among extraversion and unsafe driving conduct was to a great extent driven by a component of extraversion called sensation seeking. In the interim, the highlights of neuroticism that were driving the relationship are outrage and hastiness, while nervousness really decreased unsafe driving conduct. Unsafe driving conduct is related with lower agreeableness and conscientiousness, and higher impulsiveness (Šucha and Černochová, 2016). Another investigation found a positive direct impact of neuroticism on resentment while driving, and an indirect outcome on forceful driving. Likewise, agreeableness had a negative circular impact on driving indignation and forceful driving (Jovanovic', Lipovac, Stanojevic', and Stanojevic, 2011).

Aggressive driving is associated with high neuroticism, low agreeableness and low conscientiousness (Dahlen et al., 2012, Qu et al., 2015). A vital element of a hazardous driving style is over speeding. Higher driving speed exacerbates the danger of accidents (Aarts and van Schagen, 2006). Tao, Zhang, and Qu (2017) observed speeding to be related with higher neuroticism, higher psychoticism, and lower extraversion. Linkov, Zaoral, Řezáč, and Pai (2019) exhibited that conscientiousness connected with a lower speed levels. Extraversion and sensation seeking were associated with driving more on the right side of the lane. In Osun state road crashes is frequent among youthful and middle aged men who have been linked to age –related factors and personality variables. Presently, the contribution of personality traits is yet to be connected to risky driving behaviour. The primary objective of this study is to investigate predictive influence of personality traits among traffic offenders in Osun state. The specific objectives of the study is to:

1. Observe the patterns and prevalence of risky driving behaviour among offenders
2. Determine if personality traits have predictive influence on risky driving behaviour
3. Find out if age, gender, educational level predicts risky driving behaviour

Research Hypotheses

1. Personality traits (OCEAN) will jointly significantly predict risky driving behaviour among the participants.
2. Demographic factors –age, marital status, and education will jointly significantly predict risky driving behaviour among the participants.

Research design

The study was an ex post-facto which utilized the cross-sectional survey method to gather data.

Research Setting:

Federal Road Safety Corps office in Oshogbo. The Osun state command is and up of six sectors headed by a commander. Six mobile courts were created in each zone to try traffic offenders. The Mobile court is to facilitate the trial of road traffic offenders thereby ensuring discipline on the highways.

Participants

The study recruited individual with traffic offenses. Multi-stage sampling technique was employed in the selection of the offenders. First three clusters out of six were selected through balloting. These centres included Oshogbo, Ife and Gbongan centres. At these centres, offenders were selected through systematic sampling technique. Every third offender, arraigned by FRSC officers at the tribunal were interviewed and questionnaire administered on them after their

judgement have been delivered. A total of Two hundred and eighty-three (283) male and female participants (mean age =34.34 years, standard deviation =10.31; range: 15–70 years; median: 32.00 years) took part in the study. Participants were recruited from February 2018 to April 2018.

Research Instruments:

The questionnaire used in the study was segmented into three sections. Respondents' socio-demographic and history of traffic related offenses obtained include; age, sex, level of education, marital status, employment status, type of offense, etc. Driving Behaviour Survey (DBS) (Clapp, Olsen, Beck, et al., 2011) was used to measure Risky driving behaviour. This measure consists of 21 items that index the frequency of risky driving behaviour across three domains: Anxiety-based performance deficits; Exaggerated safety/caution behaviour: and; Hostile/aggressive behaviours. Items are rated on a 1 to 5 Likert-type scale with higher mean scores indicating greater frequency of anxious behaviour. In the current sample, all three dimension showed good to excellent internal consistency ($\alpha = .85-.93$) and good test– retest reliability between posttreatment assessments ($r = .80-.85$). Personality traits was measured using the big-five inventory (BFI).The version of the five inventories includes 44 questions with short phrases that are graded on a five-degree scale, from completely disagree=1 to completely agree=5. Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the five factors of neuroticism, extraversion, conscientiousness, agreeableness and openness were 0.78, 0.61, 0.68, 0.74 and 0.75 respectively.

Procedure: Approval for this study was obtained from the Federal Road safety corps (FRSC) . The researcher was duly introduced to the offenders who were waiting their turn to attend the mobile court. The researcher then educates the officers and offenders on the aims and objectives of the study, the inherent benefits, risk involved and the right to withdraw whenever they choose. Participants were randomly selected through the systematic sampling technique. Every third offender that appears before the court is summarily examined and assessed with the questionnaire. Copies of the questionnaire were retrieved immediately after completion. Only the Two hundred and eighty-three questionnaires that were well completed were used in the data analysis.

Method of data Analysis

The data was analyzed using the statistical package for social sciences SPSS 20.0 Software. Both the descriptive and inferential statistics were use in the study. Frequency count, simple percentage and multiple regression analysis were used to test the hypothesis at $p \leq .05$ level of significance.

Results

Socio-demographics characteristics study sample

Larger percentage of the respondent (44.9%) were between age 31-40 years, 26.1% were age 21-30 years, 22.3% were age 41-50 years,2.8% were 10-20 years while 3.9% were on the age range of 51 and above. The greater percentage of respondents (80.9%) were males while 19.1% were females. 72 .8% of the respondents were married while 27.2 % were singles. 14.8% were teachers, 3.9% were fashion designers, 20.5% were drivers/transporter, 7.8% were student, 28.6% were civil servant, 4.2% were farmers, 1.1% were retiree, 1.8% were engineer, 1.1% were mechanic, 15.9% were business/trader, while 0.4% were unemployed. 65.4% of the respondents has been driving for 1-10 years, 31.1% has been driving for 11-20years, 1.4% has been driving

for 21-30 years 2.1% has been driving for 31 years and above, 52.7% of the respondents reported that they did not use seat belt, 5.7% overload, 3.5% were overspreading, 7.4% has no extra tyre, 16.6% has no driver license, 0.7% has no fire extinguisher, 13.4% caused road obstruction, 87.3% reported that they were involved in accident once, 10.6% were involved twice, 1.1% were involved thrice, 1.1% were involved six times.

Assessment of Risky Driving Behaviour

Percentage proportion confidence interval analysis and the result presented in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Prevalence rate for Risky driving among sample (n =283)

Risky driving	Frequency	Percent	Mean	S.D
Low	58	20.5		
Moderate	163	57.6	69.14	15.23
Severe	62	21.9		
Total	283	100.0		

The analysis revealed that based on the normed scores (≤ 69.14) which yielded that 75.6% (225) of the present sample selected have severe to moderate risky driving behaviour. This suggests that the larger percentage of the drivers were risky driving behaviour based on assessment.

Table 4.2: Averaged score on the dimensions of risky driving behaviour and its incidence rates

	Anxiety based performance		Exaggerated safety caution behaviour		Hostile aggressive behaviour	
Mean	19.2014		25.3534		24.5901	
Std. Deviation	5.79359		8.68043		5.28226	
	Anxiety based performance		Exaggerated safety caution behaviour		Hostile aggressive behaviour	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Low	68	24.0	85	30.0	58	20.5
Moderate	153	54.1	139	49.1	174	61.5
High	62	21.9	59	20.8	51	18.0
Total	283	100.0	283	100.0	283	100.0

The pattern of averaged scores on risky driving behaviour shows that the drivers have moderate to high scores on anxiety based performance, exaggerated safety caution behaviour and hostile aggressive behaviour. 75.9% of the offenders had moderate Anxiety based performance driving behaviour, 69.9% traffic offenders reported exaggerated safety caution driving behaviour and traffic offenders reported 79% hostile aggressive driving behaviour. This shows that a larger percentage of the traffic offenders were moderate to severe risky drivers.

Hypothesis 1 :

Personality traits (openness to experiences, consciousness, extroversion, agreeableness and neuroticism) will significantly jointly predict driving behaviour. This was tested using multiple regression analysis for testing composite relationship of the independent variables and the result is shown on table 4.3.

Table 4.3: Summary of Multiple Regression table showing joint and independent influence of personality traits on driving behaviour.

Predictors	β	T	P	R	R ²	F	P
Extraversion	.459	6.99	< .05				
Agreeableness	-.408	-3.98	< .05				
Conscientiousness	-.173	-3.68	< .05	.783	.612	87.54	< .05
Neuroticism	.141	1.49	> .05				
Openness to experience	-.269	-4.20	< .05				

From table 4.3, the results indicate that there was significant joint influence of personality traits, on risky driving behaviour, [F(5,277) = 87.54, R² = .612; p < .05] with the variables accounting for 61% of the variance in driving behaviour. Further results show that high extraversion (β =.45; t= -6.99, p<.05), low agreeableness (β = -.41; t = 3.98, p<.05), and low conscientiousness (β =.17; t = 3.68, p<.05), and openness to experience (β =-.27; t= -4.20, p<.05), significantly predicted driving behaviour while neuroticism (β =-.14 p>.05) did not significantly predict driving behaviour. Based on this premise the hypothesis is thus supported that personality traits influence risky driving behaviour among traffic offenders.

Hypothesis II

Demographic variables (age, sex, marital status, education, religion and years of training) will significantly jointly predict risky driving behaviour of the traffic offenders. This was tested using multiple regression analysis for testing composite relationship of the independent variables and the result is shown on table 4.4:

Table 4.4: Summary of Multiple Regression table showing joint influence of demographic variables on driving behaviour.

Predictors	β	T	P	R	R ²	F	P
Age	.041	.505	> .05				
Sex	.007	.115	> .05				
Marital status	-.046	-.613	> .05	.168	.028	2.25	< .05
Occupation	.050	.821	> .05				
Educational level	-.054	-.906	> .05				
Driving experience	-.156	-2.236	< .05				

From Table 4.4, the results indicate that there was no significant joint influence of demographics variable on driving behaviour, [F(6,276) = 1.34, R² = .028; p < .05] with the variables accounting for 3% of the variance in driving behaviour. Further results show that years driving experience (β -.16; p<.05) significantly influence driving behaviour. Decreasing driving experience was associated with risky driving behaviour. However, age (β =.04; p>.05), sex (β =.007 p>.05), marital status (β =-.046; p>.05), occupation (β =.050 p>.05), educational level (β =-.054 p>.05) did not significantly influence driving behaviour. The hypothesis is thus rejected.

Discussion

The study assessed the pattern of risky driving behaviour and the role of Personality – Traits and socio-demographic characteristics in risky driving-behaviour among traffic offenders in arraigned Osun state. 75.6% of the present sample selected has severe to moderate risky driving behaviour. This suggests that the larger percentage of the drivers were risky driving behaviour based on assessment.. This shows that a larger percentage of the traffic offenders were moderate to severe risky drivers. This finding is similar to trend Fergusson et. al. (2003) found that over 90% of drivers occupied engaged in risky driving conduct. Sudha et. al. (2014) also found that 59.4% risky driving behaviour among a sample of adult drivers in Kuwait. Tien et. al., (2018) demonstrated that 81.4% depicted one or more risky driving conduct. Dangerous driving (not wearing a safety belt) was the most widely recognized risky driving conduct noted in a TV serials survey.

The first hypothesis was supported. Results demonstrated that dimensions driving behaviour was predicted by personality factor (extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism and openness to experiences). The findings support studies that have demonstrated that people who drive more carefully present higher scores in traits as agreeableness, conscientiousness, openness to change, and introversion (Harris et al., 2014). In the same vein the findings of Šucha and Černočová, (2016) that found associations between lower agreeableness and conscientiousness, and higher compulsiveness risky driving. The second hypothesis stated that demographic variables (age, sex, marital status, education, religion and years of training will significantly jointly predict driving behaviour was rejected. There was significant influence of demographic variables on driving. Driving experience was to have found significant associations with risky driving behaviour. This finding was in contrast with studies which demonstrated that gender, age was associated with greater likelihood of engaging in aggressive driving behaviour (Vanlaar, Simpson, Mayhew, & Robertson, 2008; Wickens, Mann, Stoduto, Ialomiteanu, & Smart, 2011).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Taking everything into account, our examination investigates to what degree how personality characteristics can impact hazardous driving. We explored the relations of personality attributes with risky driving and association that has not been done in past research. Relationships observed in the current study identify personality traits as a common vulnerability factor for risky driving behaviour among individuals with a history of traffic collisions. Results from this study useful in better handling on the prevalence of aggressive driving, to help understand the issue better, and – on a more practical level – to better reach target groups in advertising campaigns. This study suggests the use cognitive behavioural and Meseron therapies in the management of anger driving behaviour among the offenders. These interventions have been found useful the reductions of driving anger generally and in day-to-day driving behaviour (Awaritefe, 1995; Ofovwwe, 2005; Deffenbacher et al. 2002). Future studies might explore scale developments that include a social desirability measure correction. A check for social desirability is recommended for evaluating possible distortions of self-presentation. A cross-cultural studies should become more the norm and less the exception, as it seems there are universal driving experiences/issues and driver types. This of course, needs to be confirmed with more research. Similarities and differences across cultures could provide meaningful insights.

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Effect of cognitive behaviour therapy on mathematics performance of secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the effect of Cognitive Behaviour Therapy on Mathematics Performance of Secondary School Students. Sixty Senior Secondary School II (SSS II) students were used for the study. The research adopted a pretest, post-test and control group quasi-experimental design with a 2x2 factorial matrix. Two schools were randomly selected from two different Local Government Areas in Ibadan. Thirty participants each with anxiety were randomly selected from the two selected schools for the treatment and control group respectively. The instruments used for the study were Mathematics Anxiety Scale and Mathematic Achievement Test. The data was analyzed with the aid of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) tested at the 0.05 level of significance. The finding indicates that the participants exposed to Cognitive Behaviour Therapy showed a significant improvement in their mathematics performance when compared to the control group. Also, it is found that mathematics anxiety if not managed well has a significant effect on mathematics performance of students. It was recommended that counselling psychologists should deploy cognitive behaviour therapy in remediation of poor academic performance among students.

Keywords: Cognitive behaviour therapy, Mathematics performance, Secondary school students

Introduction

The performance of students in mathematics at both internal and external examination are to be reconciled by stakeholders, organizations, and researchers in the education setting since the performance of students is the feedback of effectiveness and efficient teaching and learning in the school system. Moreover, students' performance is a noticeable behaviour after undergoing a certain programme of instruction in the school.

Poor performance in mathematics has been attributed to its nature as a difficult subject to comprehend or learn or abstract without looking for the ability of students in interpreting, explaining, analyzing and evaluating mathematics questions set for them in the examination (National Council for Curriculum Assessment, 2005). A cursory look at the Nigeria Senior Certificate Examinations results in mathematics over the years shows little or no improvement in the performance of students. Researchers have identified different factors adduced to be responsible for the consistent in poor performance of students in Mathematics as, anxiety, teacher, and school factors, orientation, school adjustment, self-concept, self-efficacy among others (Amadalo, Shikuku & Wasike, 2012).

Consequently, this result is disheartening that research and data from National Examination bodies like West African Examinations Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO) have given a consistent report in poor performance in this subject. Majority of Senior Secondary School students often dread and exhibit negative attitudes towards learning Mathematics and the trends of their performance in the Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSSCE), is also a source of worry to the stakeholders in education (Ajayi & Muraina, 2011; Adejumo, Oluwole & Muraina, 2015). In 2014, report of the Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination results showed that less than 42% of registered candidates for SSCE obtained credit pass in Mathematics. Out of a total of 529425 candidates, 31.28% had credit in mathematics (Uwadiae, 2014). Olatoye (2002) also found that the students' achievement in Mathematics secondary schools was generally poor with the overall mean score of 31.3%. It is noted that when compared to the 2012 and 2013 May/June WASSCE results, there was a marginal decline in the performance of candidates as 38.81 percent recorded in 2012 and 36.57 percent in 2013 (Uwadiae, 2014). In 2015, out of 1,593,442 candidates that sat for the Senior School Certificate Examination, 758,849 representing 47.62% obtained six credits, and above including mathematics, 40,86 representing 59.61% obtained five credits and above, while 1,114,988 students representing 69.97% obtained credit in four subjects, and above and 37.26% of 300,134 students failed mathematics (West Africa Examination Council, 2015).

The Science Teachers of Nigeria (1992) referred to mathematics as the central of the technological societies. It is one of the compulsory subjects that students must offer and pass in secondary school before gaining admission into the higher institution. Mathematics has four goals for teaching it in schools namely, utilitarian, personal development, economic growth and cultural values (Yara & Otieno, 2010; Xia, 2008; Scopes, 1973). Mathematics is being used in various measurement activities, transport and communication manipulations, in the management of organization by preparing daily routines, timetables and leave schedules and that is why it is a requirement in many careers and training (Aguele & Agwagah, 2007).

The rate of mathematics performance among secondary school students shows the level of their thinking and reasoning in handling any challenges that may be facing them in other subjects' area (Aguele & Agwagah, 2007). Elekwa (2010) remarked that students exhibit poor performance in Mathematics, even when they know that they need it to proceed with their studies. The avoidance of Mathematics as a result of poor performance restricts students from the opportunity to fit into the choice of discipline and career (Adejumo, Oluwole & Muraina, 2015; Wang & Ye, 2015).

Based on the premise, the present study was designed to facilitate performance in mathematics among Senior Secondary School students using Cognitive Behaviour Therapy as an intervention to change students' behaviour towards learning. Cognitive Behaviour Therapy (CBT) is a popular form of psychotherapy based on the concept that emotions results from cognitive processes; it emphasizes how our thinking interacts with how we feel and what we do; it is possible for human beings to modify such to achieve different ways of feeling and behaving. It is a structured, time-limited, present-focused approach that is a well-known and widely used as means of helping people overcome problems such as depression, anxiety, anger, low self-esteem, self-defeating behaviours. The difficulty with coping is usually an exaggerated way of thinking. These negative behaviours may be corrected by reducing erroneous and maladaptive beliefs.

Therefore, being able to identify and challenge these beliefs can assist a person to reduce distress and enhance their ability to cope with everyday life situations. In simple words, Cognitive Behaviour Therapy refers to the class of interventions that is based on the principles that irrational thinking usually triggered maladaptive behaviour. This therapy involves clients developing modifying beliefs, identifying and changing dysfunctional thinking, relating to others in different ways, and changing behaviours (Beck, Wright, Newman & Liese, 2001).

Cognitive behaviour therapy (CBT) is a structured, goal-oriented therapy with a strong rationale for its use with children and adolescents (Knell, 2009). The focus of CBT is deficits or distortions in thinking, which are postulated to interfere with appropriate social skills. CBT intervention is adapted for delivery to groups of children and adolescents in the school setting (Flanagan, Allen, & Henry, 2010). CBT used with children and adolescents in the group setting can have beneficial effects such as peer modeling, interpersonal learning, or group cohesiveness (Yalom, 2005). Several global goals exist for CBT interventions about social skills. These goals may include increasing the student's ability to express feelings, decreasing maladaptive thoughts and perceptions, increasing the adaptive and realistic assessment of relationships, increasing positive self-talk, and increasing appropriate use of problem-solving skills (Kottman, 2011). CBT can be an integral piece for improving students' social skills in a group counseling setting.

Academic achievement in students is connected to their motivation, as well as the level of anxiety students experience at school (Roeser, Strobel, & Quihuis, 2002; Ergene, 2003; Fisher, Masia-Warner, & Klein, 2004; Keogh, Bond, French, Richards, & Davis, 2004).

Students must be motivated to use learning strategies, be engaged in learning, and apply the learning processes to academic tasks (Pintrich & De Groot, 1990; Mizelle & Hart, 1993). Pintrich and De Groot (1990) propose three aspects which impact student motivation: (a) Do the students believe they can perform the required task, (b) Does it align with their self-defined goals and beliefs; and (c) Do students have an emotional response to the task? These three processes help define the students if they can do the task and if they believe they are responsible for the it. The students beliefs that they can perform the task, and seems directly related to how they approach it, persist in it and master the task (Roeser, Strobel, & Quihuis, 2002). Further, these beliefs is then constructed as values, goals, and competence beliefs that directly create the motivation or lack of motivation within the student.

Mathematics anxiety is used as a moderating variable in this study. Mathematics Anxiety is a way of feeling tension, apprehension or fear that interferes with the manipulation of numbers and solving mathematical problems in an open variety of societal life and academic situations

(Richardson & Suinn, 1972; Ashcraft, 2002). It is also a state of discomfort, which occurs in involving mathematics (Trujillo & Hadfield, 1999). Nevertheless, potential causal factors include environmental variables, e.g., negative experiences in class, teacher characteristics; intellectual variables, e.g., the degree of abstract or logical thinking; and personality variables, e.g., self-esteem, learning style, attitude and confidence (Yüksel-Şahin, 2008; Newstead, 1998).

The objective of the study is to use Cognitive Behaviour Therapy to enhance mathematics performance among Senior Secondary School Students. The study also examined the moderating effect of mathematics anxiety on the causal link between Cognitive Behaviour Therapy and mathematics performance of Senior Secondary School students.

Hypotheses

Based on the articulated objectives of the study, it is hypothesized that the experimental group will not be significantly different from the control group on their measure of mathematics performance of Secondary School Students in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Methods

Design

The study used a pretest, post-test, and control group quasi-experimental design with 2x2 factorial matrix. The row consisted of Cognitive Behaviour Therapy and Control group. The row is crossed with Mathematics anxiety varied at two levels (High and Low).

Participants

Sixty Senior Secondary School II students who have scored significantly on the anxiety scale were randomly drawn from two public secondary schools in two Local Governments in Ibadan. Twenty-six (43.33%) of the participants were males, and 34 (56.67%) were females. Their age ranged from 16 to 24 years with a mean age of ± 18.6 ; $SD = 2.3$ years. These participants with anxiety consisted of Senior Secondary School in SSS II who had consistent school records of low Mathematics performance for two terms, i.e., first term and the second term records.

Measures

Mathematics Anxiety Scale (MAS)

The measuring instrument is Mathematics Anxiety Scale developed by Mahmood & Khatoun (2011). It is a 14-item scale rated on a 4-point Likert type ranging from 4= Strongly Agree to 1= Strongly Disagree. The internal consistency of this instrument was established and found to be .89 and .87. The test re-test reliability was found to be .79 after a pilot study of three weeks.

Mathematics Performance Test (MPT)

This instrument is a self-developed scale by the researcher, and made up of a forty (40) multiple choice items with four options ranges from A-D. All the questions are to be answered by the participants within one hour and thirty minutes. Item analysis was also used to carry out for the difficulty/ability index (a) discriminatory power (b) and chance/guessing(c) (Parameters) of the test using student Item Response Theory Profession 3 (IRTPRO3). This item analysis is done between the two parameters and three parameters in Mathematic Test. The difficulty/ability index (a) of (0.75), the discrimination index (b) of (0.51), and chance/guessing (c) of (0.2) were obtained. However, writing of test items was followed by face and content validity. The face and content validity reduced the items from sixty (60) to fifty-five (55) after given the test to two Senior Mathematics teachers in public secondary schools for scrutiny; while item analysis further reduced the test items from fifty-five (55) to forty (40). The goodness fitted items is administered to thirty students. Kuder-Richardson formula (KR_{20}) was used to establish the internal consistency which was found to be 0.57.

Table 1: Goodness Fitted Items Distribution of Mathematics Performance Test in Table of Specification

Mathematics Areas	Total Weight	Knowledge (40%)	Comprehension (20%)	Application (15%)	Analysis (10%)	Synthesis (10%)	Evaluation (5%)	Total
Indices, Surd & Logarithms	25%	4	2	1	1	1	1	10
Equations	10%	1	1	1	1	0	0	4
Variations	20%	3	2	1	1	1	0	8
Polygon & Solid Measurement	25%	4	2	1	1	1	1	10
Trigonometric functions	20%	3	2	1	1	1	0	8
TOTAL	100%	15	9	5	5	4	2	40

Procedure

The training programme is conducted in the third term of 2016/2017 academic session among Senior Secondary School II students (SS II). The study was in four phases: pre-session activities,

pre-test, treatment, and post-test. Pre-session included the screening, recruitment and random assignment of participants to experimental and control group. At the pre-test stage, Mathematics anxiety scale and mathematics performance test was administered to the participants. The post-test is administered following the conclusion of the training programme. The participants in the experimental group are exposed to eight weeks of treatment of one session per week, and each session lasted for one hour. Though the control group was not treated, but was given a lecture on study skill technique. After the post-test, Mathematics Performance Test (MPT) is administered to the experimental and control groups as the criterion.

Mathematics Anxiety Training Programme

The approach employed in this study fashioned after mathematics anxiety training programme developed by Franklin, Biever, Moore, Clemons, and Scamardo (2001). The goal of the model is to educate and train participants in enhancing their performance in mathematics. The training programme lasted for eight sessions of one hour each.

Outline of the Mathematics Anxiety Training Treatment Package

The training session covered the following:

Session I: Introduction, objectives, and recruitment

Session II: Meaning, techniques, characteristics, and stages of Cognitive Behaviour Therapy

Session III: Identification of unrealistic situations that leads to poor performance in mathematics

Session IV: Self-determination and self-regulation to enhance mathematics performance

Session V: Behaviour modification towards mathematics

Session VI: Cognitive Behaviour Therapy in mathematics performance

Session VII: Rehearsal and application of treatment conditions

Session VIII: Overall review, post-experiment test administration, and conclusion

Data Analysis

Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was the statistical tool used to establish initial differences between the participants in the experimental and the control groups at the 0.05 level of significance while Multiple Classification Analysis was used in the study to explore the association between the instruments used.

Result

Table 2: Summary of 2x2 Analysis of Covariance on participants' Mathematics Performance and control group with Mathematics Anxiety as Covariate

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	2050.856	6	292.070	2.890	.009	.131
Intercept	474.055	1	474.055	4.676	.034	.963
Pre-score (Covariate)	4700.745	1	4700.745	4.683	.033	.326
TRT Group	1054.022	1	1054.022	3.537	.037	.131
Math Anxiety	247.600	1	247.600	2.430	.053	.027
Trt group*math Anxiety	221.245	1	221.245	1.088	.062	.003
Error	7314.033	53	138.001			
Total	24547.000	60				
Corrected Total	10364.890	59				

R Squared= .198 (Adjusted R Squared = .129)

As indicated in Table 2, the analysis of covariance of the participants' post-test scores on mathematics performance using their pretest as covariates indicates that there was the significant main effect of treatment ($F_{(1;53)} = 3.537$, $p < 0.05$, $\eta^2 = .131$). Consequently, upon this result, the null hypothesis which states that there would be no significant difference in the mathematics performance of experimental and control group was significant. There was the significant main effect of mathematics anxiety on the mathematics performance of the participants ($F_{(1;53)} = 2.430$, $p < 0.05$, $\eta^2 = .027$). There was also a two-way non-significant interaction effect of treatment on the mathematics performance of the participants ($F_{(1;53)} = 1.088$, $p > 0.05$, $\eta^2 = .003$). What the result is suggesting is that Cognitive Behaviour therapy was effective in enhancing mathematics performance of students and that the causal link between the treatment and criterion is not mediated by mathematics anxiety.

Table 1.3: Summary of Multiple Classification Analysis (MCA) showing the direction and magnitude of the contributions of Treatment group by Mathematics Anxiety on the Performance in Mathematics.

Grand mean= 51.11					
Variable + category	N	Unadjusted	Eta	Adjusted for independent+ deviation	Beta
Treatment Group:					
SFT	30	-5.47		-3.27	
CG	30	8.38		5.22	
			.65		.43
Mathematics Anxiety:					
High	62	3.98		1.52	
Low	28	-8.43		-2.51	
			.57		.25
Multiple R					.855
Multiple R ²					.731

The Multiple Classification Analysis (MCA) as can be seen in Table 3 shows the mathematics performance scores of the two groups. The experimental group has the adjusted post-test mean score of ($\bar{X} = 47.84$) while the control group recorded adjusted post-test mean score of ($\bar{X} = 66.33$). These values are obtained by summing the grand mean ($\bar{X} = 51.11$) with respective adjusted deviation.

The MCA as shown in Table 3 also indicates that the multiple R² is 0.731 while the Multiple R is 0.855. Thus, the treatment programme accounted for 73.1% of the variance of the criterion measure (mathematics performance) while the remaining 26.9% is due to other unexpected sampling error.

Discussion

The result of the present study established the effectiveness of cognitive behaviour therapy in enhancing mathematics performance of secondary school students. This finding is in tandem with previous research works (Kendall, 1994; Barrett, Dadds, & Rapee, 1996; Barrett, 1998; Dadds, Holland, Laurens, Mullins, Barrett & Spence, 1999; Flannery-Schroeder & Kendall, 2000; Kabat - Zinn, 2005) who found cognitive behaviour therapy effective, and efficient to change students’ poor performance to best of their potential. The probable explanation for this result could be that in some circumstance relating to the performance in mathematics;

mathematics anxiety does not always determine the performance of students in mathematics learning and the examination.

Another finding worthy of note in the present study is moderating influence of mathematics anxiety on the causal link between the intervention, and the criterion variable (mathematics performance) is not significant. The finding is an empirical foundation of Ma and Xub (2004); Hembree (1990) that effects of mathematics anxiety influence the performance in mathematics of students. The explanation for this may be that anxious individual may be avoiding any mathematics courses or subjects involving calculation. This means that such an individual does not gain competence or mastery of mathematics operations and this may directly influence their performance.

Mathematics anxiety had a significant effect on the Mathematics performances of the students. The finding corroborates the previous findings which report a significant relationship between Mathematics anxiety and Mathematics performances of the students (Clute, 1984; Hembree, 1990; and Lee, 1996). Ashcraft and Kirk (2001) also found that people with high mathematics anxiety demonstrated smaller working memory spans than people with less mathematics anxiety, especially in tasks that required calculation. In particular, they were much slower and made many more errors than others where they had to do mental addition at the same time as keeping numbers in memory. It means that students who have high mathematics anxiety tend to perform low in Mathematics. However, those who have mathematics anxiety aspire to score high in Mathematics performance.

The study also established that there was no significant difference in the posttest scores of high and low mathematics anxiety of participants exposed to cognitive behaviour therapy and control group. This finding agrees with previous research works (Ma & Xub, 2004; Richardson & Suinn, 1972) who deduced that mathematics anxiety is always a factor affecting students' mathematics performance even with the treatment. People may exhibit performance anxiety not only about tests and examinations but about a variety of school subjects. Mathematics is usually assumed to elicit stronger emotional reactions, and especially anxiety, than most other academic subjects, but this assumption needs more research (Punaro and Reeve, 2012). This report indicates that as mathematics anxiety scores increase, achievement scores decrease. Mathematics anxiety could develop as a result of a student's prior negative experiences learning mathematics in the classroom or at home. The probable explanation for this result could be that mathematics anxious individuals do not gain competence or mastery of mathematical operations and this may directly influence their performance in Mathematics.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study has implications for all stakeholders including teachers, schools, and parents. This study provides empirical support for the effectiveness of cognitive behaviour therapy in mathematics performance among students and researchers in education. The results found evidence that preventing poor performance in mathematics can be explained by students' ability to integrate skills against quitting behaviours that may distract them from learning.

The government should endeavour to provide an enabling environment, adequate learning materials, facilities, etc. for effective teaching and learning of mathematics in schools. Counseling psychologists should intensify their effort to make use of cognitive behaviour therapy in their strategies for counseling students. Provision of needed information through

workshops, seminars or conferences on the negative impacts of anxiety in learning mathematics. Students should be encouraged and trained on the usage of the intervention that will make them adopt learning skills towards learning Mathematics and reduction of examination phobia when writing tests in mathematics.

Therefore, this study recommends that parents and teachers should play a significant role in shaping students' perceptions and attitudes towards mathematics. That students should also not be discouraged by past experiences in lower grades by convincing them that they cannot do well in mathematics.

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